

Pop-Machina

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Pop-Machina Report on user requirements

Deliverable 2.5

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Abstract

This deliverable analyses the environment of Pop-Machina from a technical perspective complementing the social, urban, legal and taxation aspects analysed in the rest of the tasks of WP2. Considering the Pop-Machina overall architecture that comprises three main modules, namely, the social collaboration platform, the data collection and analytics tool and the open knowledge tool, this document presents the relevant business and user requirements, which have been extracted by the seven pilot partners of the consortium. User requirements from the academic partners are also recorded to reveal additional functionalities of the platform that can serve scientific and research purposes. Following the user requirements analysis, the system requirements, both functional and non-functional, have been elicited and are included in the current document. The result of this technical study is the design of the relational data model of Pop-Machina, on which all platform components will rely. Finally, a rich set of pilot use cases that will form the basis of Pop-Machina evaluation are defined for all involved cities.

This report constitutes Deliverable 2.5, for Work Package 2 of the Pop-Machina project.

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Contents

Executive summary	7
List of abbreviations	9
List of figures	10
List of tables	11
1. Introduction	12
1.1 Scope and approach	12
1.2 Document structure	12
2. Pop-Machina platform	14
3. Methodology	16
3.1 Business requirements analysis	16
3.2 User requirements analysis	17
3.3 Use cases analysis	17
3.4 Academic and technical user requirements analysis	18
3.5 System requirements elicitation	18
3.6 Data model design	18
4. City of Leuven	19
4.1 Introduction	19
4.2 Current situation	19
4.2.1 Overview	19
4.2.2 Current business process models	20
4.2.3 Stakeholder identification	21
4.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	25
4.3 TO-BE scenario	26
4.3.1 Overview	26
4.3.2 Business requirements	28
4.4 Use cases	30
4.4.1 Overview	30
4.4.2 Leuven pilot use cases	31
4.5 User requirements	35
5. City of Thessaloniki	40
5.1 Introduction	40
5.2 Current situation	40
5.2.1 Overview	40
5.2.2 Current business process models	41
5.2.3 Stakeholders' identification	42
5.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	43
5.3 TO-BE scenario	44
5.3.1 Overview	44
5.3.2 Business requirements	45
5.4 Use cases	46
5.4.1 Overview	46
5.4.2 Thessaloniki pilot use cases	46

5.5	User requirements	49
6.	City of Piraeus	51
6.1	Introduction	51
6.2	Current situation	52
	6.2.1 Overview	52
	6.2.2 Current business process models	53
	6.2.3 Stakeholders' identification	54
	6.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	62
6.3	TO-BE scenario	63
	6.3.1 Overview	63
	6.3.2 Business requirements	64
6.4	Use cases	65
	6.4.1 Overview	65
	6.4.2 Piraeus pilot use cases	66
6.5	User requirements	68
7.	City of Santander	70
7.1	Introduction	70
7.2	Current situation	71
	7.2.1 Overview	71
	7.2.2 Current business process models	71
	7.2.3 Stakeholders' identification	72
	7.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	73
7.3	TO-BE scenario	74
	7.3.1 Overview	74
	7.3.2 Business requirements	75
7.4	Use cases	77
	7.4.1 The Circular-Economy Makerspace	78
	7.4.2 Repair Café	80
7.5	User requirements	81
8.	City of Venlo	83
8.1	Introduction	83
8.2	Current situation	83
	8.2.1 Overview	83
	8.2.2 Current business process models	88
	8.2.3 Stakeholders' identification	90
	8.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	90
8.3	TO-BE scenario	91
	8.3.1 Overview	91
	8.3.2 Business requirements	92
8.4	Use cases	93
	8.4.1 Overview	93
	8.4.2 Venlo pilot use cases	93
8.5	User requirements	96
9.	City of Istanbul	97
9.1	Introduction	97
9.2	Current situation	97
	9.2.1 Overview	97
	9.2.2 Current business process models	99
	9.2.3 Stakeholders' identification	99
	9.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	100
9.3	TO-BE scenario	101
	9.3.1 Overview	101
	9.3.2 Business requirements	102
9.4	Use cases	103
	9.4.1 Overview	103
	9.4.2 Istanbul pilot use cases	104
9.5	User requirements	106

10. City of Kaunas	109
10.1 Introduction	109
10.2 Current situation	109
10.2.1 Overview	109
10.2.2 Current business process models	110
10.2.3 Stakeholders' identification	111
10.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas	112
10.3 TO-BE scenario	114
10.3.1 Overview	114
10.3.2 Business requirements	115
10.4 Use cases	116
10.4.1 Overview	116
10.4.2 Kaunas pilot use cases	117
10.5 User requirements	118
11. Academic user requirements	120
12. System requirements	126
12.1 Social collaboration platform	126
12.1.1 SCP functional requirements	126
12.1.2 SCP non-functional requirements	131
12.2 Data collection and analytics tool	133
12.2.1 DCAT functional requirements	133
12.2.2 DCAT non-functional requirements	138
12.3 Open knowledge tool	144
12.3.1 OKT functional requirements	144
12.3.2 OKT non-functional requirements	146
13. Data model	147
13.1 Conceptual model	147
13.1.1 Concepts	147
13.1.2 Relationships	150
13.2 Logical model	150
14. KPIs addressed by Task 2.5	153
15. Conclusion and next steps	154
appendix 1 Business requirements guidelines	155
appendix 2 User requirements guidelines	157
appendix 3 Academic and technical user requirements guidelines	158

Executive summary

Pop-Machina aims at creating a maker community and a collaborative production environment to facilitate the circular economy in seven pilot cities. The ambition of the project is to propose solutions and novel strategies that will set a paradigm for circular economy initiatives that are able to overcome scaling limitations imposed by various legal, taxation, social and urban factors. Therefore, key goals of the project are (i) the engagement of a large number of citizens, makers and local businesses in each pilot city, (ii) the establishment of new policies and strategies for empowering the maker movement, (iii) the training of the community with best practices and the assembly of a shared inventory of circular solutions towards a safe and educated collaborative production environment, (iv) the connection of individuals, authorities and local businesses for knowledge and effort sharing and (v) the impact assessment of the solutions proposed by Pop-Machina in all pilot cities and across a broad range of perspectives (social, legal, taxation, urban, etc.).

The objectives of the project will be supported by the Pop-Machina platform. The implementation of the Pop-Machina platform is the goal of WP4, but its foundations are laid in this document. The platform will offer three suites of IT tools, namely the social collaboration platform, the data collection and analytics tool and the open knowledge tool. The social collaboration platform will enable the connection of the participants in the maker movements of all cities, the exchange of ideas and expertise, the certification of materials, products and making processes with the help of blockchain technology, the exchange of products and services empowered by tokenisation and the Pop-Machina marketplace. The data collection tool will accept data input from various stakeholders involved in the project, will automatically monitor participants' activity across the platform, will produce statistics and visualisations and will further analyse this data with advanced machine learning methods to assist in decision making and policy building. Finally, the open knowledge tool will integrate an inventory of best practices and guidelines, will educate makers and communities through seminars and online courses, will promote cities' activities, will connect and collect feedback from Pop-Machina users and will disseminate events and positive results of the project.

In the scope of the Task 2.5, pilot cities extracted their profiles to guide the design of the Pop-Machina tool suite, considering the general architecture of the Pop-Machina platform. Pilot cities started with the analysis of their existing and desirable business process models, simultaneously identifying all stakeholders participating in their city processes. The result of this phase was the collection of the pilot cities business requirements together with the identification of authorities, local businesses, initiatives and existing maker communities that are relevant and may contribute or benefit from the project. In the next step, pilots elaborated further on their desirable to-be scenarios, thus, extracting their specific user requirements and devising a set of appropriate use cases (26 in total for all pilot cities) that will enable them to evaluate the platform in the future stages of the project. This phase resulted in the identification of the main user groups that are expected to interact with the platform (i.e., authorities, makers, local companies, entrepreneurs/traders/professionals/start-uppers, citizens, NGOs, administrators of makerspaces, managers of resources, universities/researchers and social cooperatives). For each user group, the functionalities, desirable to be offered by the system, were described in the form of user stories and amounted to 267 for the seven pilot cities.

A user requirements' elicitation process was also implemented by academic and technical partners of the project, so that the analysis of Pop-Machina results and the computation of project KPIs is

effectively designed in the scope of the impact assessment tool of the project, as well as for serving different research goals of the academic groups involved in Pop-Machina. This procedure revealed 69 additional requirements to be considered in the design of the Pop-Machina platform.

Scrutinising all this information, the technical partners of the consortium extracted the functional and non-functional requirements of Pop-Machina. Functional requirements define the functionalities of all tools integrated in the platform. On the other hand, non-functional requirements prescribe the quality and effectiveness of the system both per platform component and holistically for the integrated solution. After the 336 user requirements defined by pilot and academic partners were categorised per system module, they were translated to 197 functional and non-functional system requirements that sufficiently lay the ground for the development of the Pop-Machina platform.

The system requirements' analysis led to the design of the Pop-Machina data model, which follows the standard relational model paradigm. It comprises the concepts and relationships of Pop-Machina and enables the accurate, comprehensive and complete representation of the Pop-Machina ecosystem (stakeholders, materials, products, spaces, equipment, processes). It ensures the integration of the broad range of tools that will be employed in the implementation of the platform, under a common data perspective. This fact will allow the seamless data exchange among platform modules and the efficient integration of the Pop-Machina components.

List of abbreviations

DCAT	Data Collection and Analysis Tool
ER	Entity – Relationship
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
LMS	Learning Management System
OKT	Open Knowledge Tool
SCP	Social Collaboration Platform

List of figures

Figure 1.	Pop-Machina system architecture	15
Figure 2.	Four stages of development, waste treatment, recycling and new-material/technologies	51
Figure 3.	The envisioned exploitation of IoT technologies in the municipality of Piraeus	52
Figure 4.	Key stakeholder types that are expected to be involved in the PIR project development	54
Figure 5.	Social innovation for Germany	63
Figure 6.	Location of the city of Santander	70
Figure 7.	Santander innovation strategy summary	71
Figure 8.	Pop-Machina ER model	152

List of tables

Table 1.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Leuven	22
Table 2.	Challenges and Pop-Machina potential in the city of Leuven	26
Table 3.	Business requirements of the city of Leuven	28
Table 4.	User requirements of the city of Leuven	35
Table 5.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Thessaloniki	43
Table 6.	Business requirements of the city of Thessaloniki	45
Table 7.	User requirements of the city of Thessaloniki	49
Table 8.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Piraeus	61
Table 9.	Business requirements of the city of Piraeus	64
Table 10.	User requirements of the city of Piraeus	68
Table 11.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Santander	73
Table 12.	Business requirements of the city of Santander	75
Table 13.	User requirements of the city of Santander	81
Table 14.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Venlo	90
Table 15.	Business requirements of the city of Venlo	92
Table 16.	User requirements of the city of Venlo	96
Table 17.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Istanbul	99
Table 18.	Business requirements of the city of Istanbul	102
Table 19.	User requirements of the city of Istanbul	106
Table 20.	Stakeholders identified in the city of Kaunas	112
Table 21.	Business requirements of the city of Kaunas	115
Table 22.	User requirements of the city of Venlo	118
Table 23.	User requirements defined by academic partners	121
Table 24.	Functional requirements of the social collaboration platform	127
Table 25.	Non-functional requirements of the social collaboration platform	132
Table 26.	Functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool	134
Table 27.	Non-functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool	139
Table 28.	Functional requirements of the open knowledge tool	140
Table 29.	Non-functional requirements of the open knowledge tool	145

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope and approach

The foundations of Pop-Machina are set in the second work package (WP2) of the project. In this work package, the mapping of the maker community has been performed as well as the analysis of the collaborative production, urban maker ecosystems and the legislative, taxation and governance environment and procedures of all pilot cities.

The aim of Pop-Machina is to provide the means for the pilot cities to exploit existing resources and at the same time create new opportunities for circular economy growth in the involved cities. A key role in achieving this goal is played by the Pop-Machina platform. It will serve as (i) the central point of collaboration among stakeholders, (ii) an informative and educational endpoint supporting circular economy activities and (iii) an analysis framework extracting insights and conclusions on relevant procedures, in this way, enabling pilot cities to move forward with new strategies for expanding their regenerative capacity.

In this context, this deliverable reports the results of the work done in the scope of Task 2.5. Pilot cities investigated their business goals and relevant user requirements, and they designed the use cases that are going to be supported by the Pop-Machina platform. Based on this information, the system requirements of the Pop-Machina platform were identified, and, as a result, the data model to be employed by the Pop-Machina components was designed.

Although the version of this deliverable is the final one, it is expected that user requirements may be slightly adjusted throughout the duration of the project to incorporate needs that emerge during the implementation (WP4) of the Pop-Machina platform and the pilot cities' deployment (WP5). The Pop-Machina platform will be developed by synthesising different software components either open source or custom designed for Pop-Machina. The data model is anticipated to serve all these components and enable the data exchange among all platform modules. However, the platform implementation has only recently started. As a result, in this deliverable a high-level description of the data model is given. In-depth description of the data model will be reported in the deliverable D4.7 (to be submitted by January 2021), which is the first version of the data collection and analysis tool. Any refinements that may come up during the platform implementation, will be reported in the final version of that deliverable, i.e., D4.8 (to be submitted by July 2022).

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable is organised in fifteen chapters. The current chapter (Chapter 1) introduces the scope and the approach of the project and in particular of the work package 2 and of the Task 2.5. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the Pop-Machina platform, which provides the context for the analysis of the following chapters. Chapter 3 explains the methodology followed, in order to let the goals of Task 2.5 be fulfilled. Next, seven chapters follow, one for each pilot city. Each chapter from 4 to 10 contains the analysis of the business requirements, the user requirements and the use cases of one of the Pop-Machina pilot cities. In Chapter 11, additional user requirements from the academic and technical partners of the consortium are developed. Chapter 12 presents the functional and non-functional system requirements analysis of the Pop-Machina platform, per platform component, as a result of the user requirements study of the previous chapters. In Chapter 13, the data model of Pop-Machina

is described. The KPIs addressed by Task 2.5 are included in Chapter 14. Finally, Chapter 15 concludes by summarising the work in the scope of the current deliverable and the corresponding task and sets the goals of the next steps for developing the Pop-Machina platform.

2. Pop-Machina platform

The aim of the Pop-Machina platform is to enable maker communities and urban authorities to design and implement circular economy solutions in order to improve the urban metabolism of the involved cities. During this process, society is anticipated to get sufficiently engaged and economic benefits to emerge.

The means for accomplishing the project's goals will be appropriately designed makerspaces to be designed and developed in the pilot cities of Leuven, Thessaloniki, Piraeus, Santander, Venlo, Istanbul and Kaunas. These makerspaces will procure the equipment required by makers to build products maximising the reuse of recycled materials and accordingly minimising the usage of raw materials. The material flow will depend on and will be controlled by the local community, i.e., urban authorities and citizens. The vision of the functionalities implemented in makerspaces established in the scope of the project is to promote circular economy, propose best practices in the field and create the environment for collaboration and knowledge transfer among different groups of involved partners.

In this setting, a suite of ICT tools needs to be exploited to support the effective collaboration of different users of the system and to monitor the impact of Pop-Machina. Figure 1 illustrates the main components of the Pop-Machina platform.

The **social collaboration platform (SCP)** is the core of the system. This module will enable transactions among the stakeholders that exploit makerspaces. Material and equipment usage will be reserved by users through the system. Matchmaking algorithms will propose collaboration among stakeholders whose offer and demand are complementary. Blockchain technology will play the key role in keeping the ledger of material use in the production line of the products, which is the outcome of the making procedures. Relevant certificates for validating the circular economy processes will be issued and all transactions between pairs of users will be recorded. The value of the labour for making an object in a makerspace as well as of the materials necessary to build it will be assigned in tokens. The tokenisation of services and materials along with the smart contracts registered in the ledger of the blockchain sub-module will be the basis of the interactions among the system's users. End-products will be exposed in the Pop-Machina marketplace with appropriate descriptions and price in tokens.

The **data collection and analysis tool (DCAT)** will store and monitor the representations of all assets used by the Pop-Machina platform. The data collection will be gradually built and constantly updated by authorities, citizens, companies and organisations related to the Pop-Machina procedures. The data flow will be implemented by appropriately designed data connectors, which will integrate information from heterogeneous data sources as well as the other two platform components. At each point in time, the data stored in the system will reflect the urban metabolism of the city, registering materials, waste management information, involved users and relevant circular economy processes. The data collection and analysis tool will offer detailed visualisations and reports letting authorised users monitor statistics related to the materials and processes implemented in the makerspaces. The system will also provide decision support to authorities through the employment of sophisticated data mining algorithms for analysing social and economic aspects of the Pop-Machina cities' underlying environment.

The **open knowledge tool (OKT)** will complement the social collaboration component by letting Pop-Machina users share knowledge. It will consist of a learning management system (LMS) that will host skills and machinery training resources as well as best practices of the maker movement. At the

same time, the LMS will provide capabilities for organising webinars and workshops for disseminating knowledge built through the Pop-Machina actions and results. The system will also build a news channel for letting the community be informed about events, findings and outcomes of the work of the project. Finally, it will provide the means for collecting feedback from the end-users of the platform.

Figure 1. Pop-Machina system architecture

A high-level architecture of the Pop-Machina platform is illustrated in Figure 1. Although SCP and OKT will function using their own databases, information from all three components of the platform will be in principle stored in the DCAT back end. DCAT will also be responsible for transforming the data schema to and from the Pop-Machina data model. This integration on the data level will allow homogeneous storage, monitoring and analysis of Pop-Machina data towards an integrated system providing an overview of Pop-Machina activities across pilot cities.

3. Methodology

Seven pilot cities from six countries are involved in Pop-Machina for designing and implementing the project's circular economy approach, on top of long established urban, social and governance procedures. This creates a broad range of requirements and constraints that must be taken into account for designing a homogeneous system that will serve the goals of all cities. The process of the analysis of the profiles of the pilot cities and the design of the data model that will support the Pop-Machina platform followed the steps that are described in the next paragraphs.

3.1 Business requirements analysis

Pilot cities were initially asked to define their business requirements. The identification of the business goals and requirements was conducted through a series of conference meetings among pilots, their supporting partners as well as the technical partners of the consortium. The elicitation process was defined through guidelines provided by the technical partners and a relevant business requirements template that was created for that purpose (appendix 1). These guidelines ensured that, despite the variability of pilot cases, a common analysis model was followed. At the same time, the pilot cities' representatives were guided to the perspective under which they should consider their case, and specifically, by taking into account the components of the Pop-Machina system to be designed.

In accordance with the guidelines provided, each city was requested to provide (i) a freely expressed introduction of the case of the city, (ii) a description of its current status regarding relevant subjects to the project and (iii) a desirable future scenario towards which Pop-Machina could contribute.

The current status of each city was analysed around three pillars. The current business process models implemented by the city were the first one. Cities were asked to identify the established processes relevant to circular economy, making initiatives and waste management, and to describe them in terms of the city administration departments, stakeholders and systems or software involved. Secondly and starting from the business process models, the different stakeholders as well as their roles in the city processes were identified (city authorities, makers, citizens, makerspaces administrators, managers of resources and materials, companies, etc.). The last dimension of the current status of the cities was the description of the current problems and challenges faced by each city, which fall in the scope of Pop-Machina and for which Pop-Machina can provide solutions.

For the to-be scenario of each city, each pilot partner should develop its vision for the future of the city. Extending the solutions to problems and challenges already identified in the current status of the city, the desirable new processes and business process models were included in this part of their analysis. Besides freely describing their vision, they were guided to extract their business requirements in a structured form, allowing the requirements elicitation process to move to the next phase. For this reason, during the physical and remote meetings of the project, technical partners familiarised pilot city partners with the basic components of the envisioned Pop-Machina platform. This ensured that the elicited business requirements would aptly target realistic goals and at the same time would cover a broad range of functionalities, which are desirable to be offered by the system. Thus, for each business requirement, the following were defined: (i) the relevant problem, challenge or vision of the city identified in the previous sections, (ii) the business process that is affected by the specific problem, challenge or vision, (iii) the stakeholders involved from those identified in the current status of

the city and (iv) the platform component that they believe could prove useful to serve the particular requirement.

3.2 User requirements analysis

The user requirements elicitation process elaborated on the business requirements already extracted by the pilot cities. The principle is that each business requirement produces one or more user requirements. Pilot cities were asked to consider the Pop-Machina platform already from the business requirements extraction phase, in order to avoid falling out of scope of the project. In this phase, a clearer mapping of the requirements to specific platform components was necessary, in order to let technical partners transform these requirements into specific functional and non-functional system requirements.

As a consequence, the output of the user requirements elicitation process was again structured. Appropriate guidelines were prepared to assist pilot partners and their supporting partners in translating their business requirements into valid user requirements (Appendix 2). User requirements were extracted in the form of user stories. User stories are easily comprehensible by non-technical people and are simultaneously effective in conveying the necessary information to technical experts, who need to infer system requirements. A user story is reflected by a sentence of the following form:

'As a <user role>, I want to <goal>, so that <benefit>'

The 'user role' part of the sentence defines the stakeholder that will need to enjoy the particular functionality required. It corresponds to the stakeholder identified in the relevant business requirement. The user requirement itself is reflected by the 'I want to' part of the sentence, which corresponds to the goal of the user. This part lets someone express what is the specific action that one would like to be able to perform through the system. Complementing the goal of the user, the 'so that' part of the sentence reveals the actual intent of the user, when executing the specific action through the system. The intent, which coincides with the benefit that will be earned by the described functionality, provides additional information that may further clarify the functionality required or even extend the functionality with hidden actions, which are also anticipated by the user but they are not reflected in the expressed goal of the requirement.

3.3 Use cases analysis

Use cases of pilot cities complete the analysis of their profiles from a technical perspective. In Pop-Machina, they were the result of work done both in WP2 and WP5 of the project. After iterative meetings, discussions and city workshops, in addition to the business and user requirements elicitation process, pilot cities were in position to effectively describe a set of use cases they are interested to implement, in order to test and evaluate the Pop-Machina platform against their extracted requirements. At the same time, these use cases incorporate the totality of functionalities anticipated from the Pop-Machina system, combined, revealing also additional integration aspects of the platform to be designed. Finally and most importantly, the use cases will form the basis for the evaluation process of the platform and its deployment for each pilot city.

Use cases were freely developed by pilot cities. They revolve around the makerspaces that are going to be founded or enhanced in each city, if they already exist. Depending on the city, they may focus on different materials, products or making processes and they address the various city goals following a weighting scheme of importance that better serves each city. In all cases, they reflect the ways that users, spaces, equipment, materials and products are expected to be exploited and integrated with support from the Pop-Machina platform.

3.4 Academic and technical user requirements analysis

Pop-Machina, besides helping pilot cities accomplish their circular economy goals, will also offer a great opportunity to academic partners to extract valuable insights from Pop-Machina supported activity. This will enable the design of novel best practices and modification of city strategies on the subjects addressed by the project. For that reason, academic as well as technical partners were asked to record an additional set of user requirements in the form of user stories. To that end, appropriate guidelines were also created to assist them (appendix 3).

Academic partners have a significant interest in extracting conclusions from the Pop-Machina platform, by monitoring material flows, product circularity and user participation in the project's ecosystem. At the same time, they are the experts for defining the methodology of computing the project's KPIs.

3.5 System requirements elicitation

The system requirements are either functional or non-functional. Functional requirements reflect the actions that a system must support in order to satisfy the user requirements given. A functionality is basically an action performed on a given data input producing an expected output. On the other hand, non-functional requirements define the prerequisites on the quality and the performance of the system.

Following the analysis of the user requirements of Pop-Machina by city pilots and academic partners, the technical partners of the consortium extracted the system requirements for each one of the three main components of the system. For each one of the SCP, DCAT and OKT, a set of both functional and non-functional requirements were devised.

3.6 Data model design

In the Pop-Machina project, data from seven different pilot partners are going to be exploited to foster the dynamic circular economy activities designed in the scope of the project. Not only the provenance of data (authorities, local businesses, stakeholders, Pop-Machina users, etc.), but also the use cases that are going to be supported by this data, exhibit great variety in their nature and cover a broad range of environmental, urban, social and legal aspects. Thus, the main challenges faced are (i) the design of a broad homogenised data model, which will serve all purposes required, and at the same time (ii) the delimitation of the design to the context of the project.

At this stage of the project, the activity of WP4, where the implementation of the Pop-Machina platform is going to take place, has just started. As a result, the data model was designed in a preliminary form, and it is anticipated to change in course of the project. The system requirements of the three main platform components, i.e., SCP, DCAT and OKT, laid the ground for the basic concepts and relationships of the model. Integration aspects of the three components were also taken into account into this process. However, the model is expected to evolve in the next phase of the project and its finalised form will be reflected in the deliverables of WP4.

4. City of Leuven

4.1 Introduction

Leuven (www.leuven.be) is a highly dynamic and fast-growing region. It is the capital of the Belgian province Flemish-Brabant, at 20 km from Brussels, with over 100.000 inhabitants. Leuven is the home of the KU Leuven University, Europe's most innovative university, with more than 50.000 students (on top of the 100.000 inhabitants), high-quality spin-offs (IMEC, Bio-Incubator), the multinational Anheuser-Busch Inbev and the largest hospital in Belgium, the academic hospital Gasthuisberg. Leuven has the ambition to become a climate neutral, resilient city by 2030.

Pop-Machina can benefit the city of Leuven by:

- achieving a better understanding of the maker community ecosystem;
- stimulating and supporting circular business models in order to make the most of the opportunities for circular entrepreneurship;
- integrating circular principles and enhancing the capabilities of collaborative manufacturing;
- engaging and empowering local communities in circular collaborative production;
- creating a culture in which sustainable and circular consumption becomes the self-evident norm;
- establishing a 'validation scheme' for circularity to support product value and commercialisation opportunities;
- analysing the social and spatial urban environments and redesign production infrastructure;
- innovating with tokenisation in a local economy context.

4.2 Current situation

4.2.1 Overview

Over the last years and following big city development projects, the city of Leuven has become a key actor for realising projects on circular economy in waste management and waste prevention, circular demolition and using residual heat as energy source. The city of Leuven together with its main stakeholders, through the NGO Leuven 2030, are also facilitating multi-actor projects and supporting bottom-up projects.

Through the partnership, projects can be scaled-up or accelerated. City of Leuven is, as a large public authority, able to support all stakeholders and to ensure participation of citizens.

The main initiatives relative to the project are:

- **The Policy Agreement Leuven 2019-2025 'Pioneering Leuven'** (Baanbrekend Leuven)¹ where the vision of the municipality of Leuven on circular economy is embedded;
- **Programme 9 of the roadmap towards a climate neutral city: 'Circular Leuven'** where the municipality, together with its main stakeholders united in the NGO Leuven 2030, elaborated a roadmap, to serve as a guide for achieving climate neutrality by 2050 (which will require an emissions reduction of at least 80%). Within the programme 9 of the roadmap, called 'Circular Leuven' the municipality, together with its stakeholders, focus on 5 main aspects/domains within the circular economy;

¹ <https://www.leuven.be/bestuursnota>

- **the Vaartopia project** that aims to turn the Vaartkom area into a creative breeding ground where designers, starters, artists, production houses, cultural associations and craftsmen and makers can find affordable spaces;
- **the Circular Concept store** that is about to be developed in Leuven city Centre (Diestsestraat). It aims to raise awareness and make the circular way of life mainstream (share economy, repair, upcycling, reuse, recycling in the heart of the city, making the circular economy visible/feasible/eatable/doable in different kinds of ways: Circular coffee bar, juice bar and lunch corner (focussing on waste prevention and food consumption); Pop up store for circular start-ups (clothing library, baby gear library, etc.); Repair cafes on a regular basis, tool library.

There are also a number of initiatives of social enterprises and cooperatives active on circular waste management, such as:

- repair cafés. Small bottom-up projects for repair, re-use and waste prevention;
- SPIT- reuse centre. Large circular economy and social economy project on waste prevention and circular use of materials;
- SATE. Bottom-up pilot project, with support of the city, on circular demolition;
- VELO. Large social economy project on shared and sustainable mobility (repairing and renting of bikes), bike sharing;
- Warmtenetwerk Vaartkom. Project plan to reuse heat of the AB InBev brewery as a source for a heat network in a new climate-neutral district;
- Food strategy. Multi-actor project, starting from the food strategy, with the ambition to scale-up all sustainable food consumption projects and work on city agriculture.

4.2.2 Current business process models

Makers and citizens interact with the city authorities through the common communication channels offered by the city (citizen phone line, email, social media). The possibility to make an e-appointment with the city services is offered online.

Ecoerf, the inter-municipal authority responsible for waste collection, has developed the App Recycle! that provides information about waste collection. It includes a handy waste calendar with reminders, waste sorting information and an overview of the collection points in your neighbourhood, including the opening hours of the recycling park.

Regarding the processes and responsibilities of the city departments related to Pop-Machina, these are:

- the **Department for facility management**: this department is responsible for the management (building, refurbishment, maintenance, etc.) of public buildings and other municipal infrastructure. It is relevant to the urban regeneration activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Environment department**: responsible to issue Environmental permits and enforcement of environmental laws (nuisance avoidance and reduction). It is relevant to the technical management, ecosystem mapping and circular production activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Department for city cleaning**: responsible for waste collection and cleanliness of the public domain. It also focusses on waste prevention and sanitation. It is relevant to the technical management and circular production activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Department for spatial planning**: responsible for spatial planning, urban development plans and municipal regulation on spatial planning. It is relevant to the ecosystem mapping and urban regeneration activities of Pop-Machina;

- the **Department of Public Works**: [department responsible for construction and the maintenance of public domain \(roads, footpaths, sewage system, public lighting, etc.\)](#). It is relevant to the ecosystem mapping and urban regeneration activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Department for urban planning**: department responsible for building permits and enforcement of building regulations. It is relevant to the technical and financial management, ecosystem mapping and circular production activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Department of green management**: responsible for the construction and maintenance of the public domain (green areas). It is relevant to the financial and technical management, ecosystem mapping and circular production activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Department of sustainability**: department responsible for the policy on sustainable development and for supporting different departments, stakeholders and citizen in their efforts for sustainability. It is relevant to the financial and technical management, ecosystem mapping and circular production activities of Pop-Machina;
- the **Department for economy and trade**: responsible for stimulation and supporting local trade and industry. It is relevant to the financial and technical management, ecosystem mapping and circular innovation and entrepreneurship activities of Pop-Machina;
- **EcoWurf**, the inter-municipal environmental company, that is responsible for the processing of the household waste that is collected: it is managing recycling parks and is operating a waste processing composting plan. It is relevant to the financial and technical management, ecosystem mapping and circular production activities of Pop-Machina.

Makers and citizens interact with other external entities and with each other, through commonly used communication channels (face to face, email, social media).

There are no dedicated software systems used in the relevant business processes.

Note that the Department of sustainability also offers (for free) stickers that citizens can stick on their front-door or letterbox to indicate that they want to share certain tools like lawnmower, drilling machine, etc.

Citizens may also directly communicate with social and environmental organisations (i.e. SPIT reuse centre) to organise the collection of bulk waste.

Finally, the Belgian Government offers an online tool (a guide for entrepreneurs: permits and authorisations, (<http://procedures.business.belgium.be/>) providing information about the procedures and requirements that are imposed on Belgian and foreign companies who wish to establish themselves in Belgium or who wish to provide services temporarily in Belgium. This could be relevant to the financial and technical management and circular innovation and entrepreneurship activities of Pop-Machina.

4.2.3 Stakeholder identification

Preliminary research on identifying relevant stakeholders relating to the Leuven pilot case was already performed and is presented in the Pop-Machina proposal. Further research activity performed so far within the Task 2.4 has had a twofold focus aiming to:

- identify any other potential stakeholders at local as well as regional level (categories and individual stakeholders) that had not been considered at the proposal phase;
- identify individual (or representative groups) stakeholders per stakeholders' segment.

From these initiatives, a map of all the relevant stakeholders (at municipal and regional level) that will be used in the Leuven pilot deployment activities.

The user groups that interact for purposes relevant to the project are:

Table 1. Stakeholders identified in the city of Leuven

User group	Role
Local/regional authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the local needs and requirements, policy challenges and priorities to be addressed by the project - Actively support the development of the makers movement - Support stakeholders & ensure participation of citizens - Implement circular economy plans/regulations - Help identify and select urban areas and spaces that could benefit from DIY urbanism in the context of Pop-Machina - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Local makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Exchange good practices and know-how - Network and achieve cooperation between makers and communities for product or service development and exchange materials or services - Take part in project workshops and events - Develop circular products and services - Get informed and receive technical and business training in the circular production and provision of services - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Innovative R&D spin off companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Exchange good practices and know-how - Network and achieve cooperation between makers and communities for product or service development and exchange materials or services - Develop circular products and services - Get informed and receive technical and business training in the circular production and provision of services - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Entrepreneurs/traders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Collaborate in new product/service development - Cooperate in the proposal or identification of products and services that may be developed by the makers and start uppers of Pop-Machina - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Citizens/residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Take part in the identification of and highlight good practices and competent organisations working towards circular production - Cooperate in the proposal or identification of products and services that may be developed by the makers and start uppers of Pop-Machina - Validate the quality, usefulness and sustainability of the circular endeavours - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Makerspaces administrators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Acquire all legal permits for the operation of their makerspaces - Offer tools, methods and space for the operation of the maker movement - Provide feedback on good circular production practices - Uptake the task of hosting maker communities - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Managers of resources and materials (i.e. construction/demolition sector, waste management organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Manage resources and material flows - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Provide feedback on good circular production practices - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy

Table 1. Stakeholders identified in the city of Leuven (continued)

User group	Role
Higher education/universities and researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Provide scientific knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
Social economy organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide feedback on their needs and requirements that are related to the project and circular economy - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Provide feedback on good circular production practices - Offer their experience and knowledge in their practices on sustainable production and provision of services - Get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy

The specific stakeholders that fall into the abovementioned categories and who may assume a role in Pop-Machina follow:

- **Bio-incubator** (<http://www.bio-incubator.be/en>): The Leuven Bio-Incubator provides a dynamic and stimulating innovative environment in which biotech companies can develop their ideas and technologies;
- **Bond Beter leefmilieu** (<http://www.bondbeterleefmilieu.be>): Bond Beter Leefmilieu is the NGO working on climate and the environment in Belgium;
- **Buitenspoor** (<http://www.buitenspoor.be>): Buitenspoor wants to valorise Leuven's coffee grit by growing oyster mushrooms on it. In this way, organic waste streams, and thus CO2 emissions, are reduced. The used substrate is returned to the chain as compost, or can be processed in further applications (design, construction, packaging, etc.);
- **Camping Flamingo** (<http://nl-nl.facebook.com/Campingflamingoo/>): Camping Flamingo and HAL5 join forces and give a new impulse to the creative dynamism of Leuven: every month, the best of CAMPING FLAMINGO and HAL5 united under one roof: 40 passionate makers, builders, graphic artists or inventors, authentic crafts and original second hand;
- **Content** (package free food shop) (<http://www.contentleuven.weebly.com>): Package free food shop, cooperative model, focussing on zero waste;
- **FabLab Leuven** (<https://FabLab-leuven.be/>): FabLab-Leuven is a place to make everything with computer-controlled machines (CNC). FabLab-Leuven is accessible to anyone who wants to make something and share his knowledge with everyone;
- **Green Office**: Green Office for KU Leuven is the sustainability lab for and by students at the university. Students and staff members work together on campaigns, events, projects and activities to both make KU Leuven more sustainable and to inspire its population to adopt a more sustainable lifestyle.

The Green Office has started with a Student Repair Hub in atelier Vermeyleen, a project that makes partial and repair possibilities accessible for students. In this way, we want to highlight the Circular Economy at the university. In the Repair Hub, students can repair things and clothing on the spot, lend materials for the job via a materials library system and attend a workshop on a regular basis. Information about repair initiatives in Leuven is bundled and communicated. The hub is also a meeting place for visitors, Green Office members and student workers:

- **Harvest Club** (<http://www.harvestclub.be>): Concept Store brings ethical fashion for anyone who cares, i.e., Circular fashion;
- **Imec** (<http://www.imec-int.com/en/home>): Imec is the world's leading research and innovation hub in the field of nanoelectronics and digital technology;

- Interleuven (www.interleuven.be): Interleuven is an inter-municipal organisation that manages different industrial zones, within which different large-scale Circular Economy projects can be realised;
- **KU Leuven Onderzoeksgroep Life Cycle Engineering - Circulaire/duurzame economie:** The objectives of this research group are very broad and include eco-design, sustainable production processes, optimising waste processing processes as well as quantifying recoverability. Bringing educational material offline and online about recovery and its impact in a recovery economy: mapping of current materials and their problems in the current economy, tips & tricks on maintenance of computers/smartphones, introduction of reuse of RAM modules to extend the lifetime of computers;
- **Leuven 2030** (<http://www.leuven2030.be>): Leuven 2030 encourages residents, companies, schools, organisations and governments to take action and to work together towards a climate-neutral Leuven. Leuven 2030 works on different themes: buildings, mobility, energy, agriculture & food, nature and consumption;
- **Maakleerplek** (<http://www.leuven.be/maakleerplek>): MaakLeerPlek is an open workplace where schools, companies, (creative) organisations and people from Leuven meet, share space and materials, make things and learn from each other;
- **Maakbaar Leuven** (<http://www.maakbaarleuven.be>): Maakbaar Leuven is the network of citizens' initiatives focussing on the repair economy in Leuven, working towards it upscaling and professionalising. Many of the organisations listed below are members of Maakbaar Leuven;
- **MAAKbaar** (<https://www.makbaar.org>): MAAKbaar is a recently created pop-up in Leuven with a tool library, regular repair cafes, workshops on zero waste organised by citizens and organisations and where reuse is stimulated. MAAKbaar contributes to the visibility of the circular economy. It succeeds in working in an inclusive way; both newcomers and highly educated people come here and take an active part in the activities and operations;
- **Maekerij** (<http://www.maekerij.be>): Maekerij is the first talent café in Flanders. A place where young and old are welcome to come and admire themselves or work. An open space, in the middle of the city. Maekerij is committed to working with the makers' community in Leuven in this way contributing to the Circular Economy;
- **Kringwinkel Spit** (<http://www.dekringwinkel.be/>): Kringwinkel Spit is a re-use centre in Leuven;
- **LEJON** (<http://www.leuvenvoorondernemers.be/lejon>): Leuven Young Entrepreneurs, or LE(J)ON in short, shows young people between 18 and 25 years of age the wide range of initiatives around young entrepreneurship;
- **Leuven MindGate** (<http://www.leuvenmindgate.be/about-leuven-mindgate>): Leuven MindGate was founded in 2016 when 29 leading knowledge institutions, companies and the city of Leuven joined forces focussing on health, high-tech and creativity. These three parties represent the Leuven ecosystem in a so-called Triple Helix model: Companies cooperate with the government and knowledge institutions and create economic development, growth and jobs. Government invests in education to create a knowledgeable workforce, in infrastructure to create an ideal entrepreneurial climate and simplifies laws so local business can grow. Knowledge institutions develop talent and knowledge for the future and encourage innovation through cooperation and the creation of spin-off companies;
- **OVAM** (<http://www.ovam.be>): OVAM is the waste agency of the Flemish government. It covers waste, materials and soil in a well-considered and environmentally conscious manner. The agency is responsible for the policy on waste, materials and soil and thus influence the implementation of the legislation. They help families and companies to avoid and sort waste and they are working on a circular economy, in order to maximise the lifespan and reuse of products and raw materials;
- **Netwerk Bewust Verbruiken** (<http://www.bewustverbruiken.be/>): Network Aware Consumption inspires and activates people to a simple and sustainable lifestyle. It questions the value of property and the need for new purchases. Our activities stimulate the reuse, repair and sharing of

things. They focus on well-being instead of prosperity and make a social and ecological society more accessible. As a network, we set groups and citizens in motion. We connect organisations and individuals in innovative collaborative initiatives;

- **Reused** (<http://www.reused.be/>): Reused promotes sustainable, affordable and creative reuse of discarded materials;
- **UCLL** (<http://www.ucll.be>): UCLL is the college of the Moving Minds. Students and staff are moved and therefore set the world in motion towards a more just and sustainable society;
- **Vaude** (<http://www.vaude.com>): Sustainable innovative outdoor outfitter for all mountain and bike sports, working strongly on making its supply chain more socially and ecologically fair. Host of repair workshops in Leuven;
- **VITO** (<http://www.vito.be>): VITO is a Flemish independent research organisation in the field of cleantech and sustainable development;
- **Vizoog** (<http://www.vizoog.com>): Vizoog is an Innovative and experimental approach to the reuse of materials in - Designing and developing creative idea and Networking;
- **VOKA** (<http://www.voka.be>): The Flemish entrepreneurial network, representing companies in area of Leuven (Chamber of Commerce);
- **Wonen en Werken** (<http://www.wonen-en-werken.be>): ‘Wonen en Werken’ (Living and Working) is a social enterprise. It is an employment project where people with a long distance to the labour market can go for a sustainable job.

4.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

In the table below we describe the challenges the city of Leuven faces in the context of Pop-Machina and the potential of the project to address them.

Table 2. Challenges and Pop-Machina potential in the city of Leuven

Challenge	Pop-Machina potential
The process and volume of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem as well as their location sites are not known in detail	Collect and provide detailed mapping on needed information
There is no previous experience on how to promote the maker initiatives	Enable easy assessment, comparison and sharing of best practices amongst stakeholders Provide education and training to stakeholders on the development of circular initiatives
There is limited knowledge and lack of financial resources for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context	Provide training and information to local stakeholders on procurement mechanisms and relative financial instruments Provide the necessary means to stakeholders mainly the municipalities and actors of the makers movement to develop an appropriate and ad hoc exploitation plan that will provide the roadmap for the development of circular products and services
The European and National legal and regulatory framework is unclear on makerspaces, collaborative production, taxation, etc.	Identify the legal framework relative to the operation of makerspaces Suggest improvements on identified shortcoming of the legal framework and initiate policy discussions on circular economy based on concrete findings
Motivate, educate and actively involve citizens in circular practices	Plan an integrated approach on citizen motivation, education and involvement
Spaces that could be repurposed for makes spaces have not be fully identified or examined thoroughly for their suitability	Help identify the appropriate spaces based on data and knowledge acquired through the project and repurpose them according to identified user needs
Lack of viable business models and manufacturing to a sufficiently large scale, to support the commercialisation of maker products	Develop appropriate business models and business support services for the makers - entrepreneurs of Pop-Machina
Validating circular production of the maker products	Develop appropriate validation mechanisms that will verify the circularity of the materials and processes
Accrediting the safety and quality of the maker products	Provide standards and test protocols to accredit the product according to its intended use (i.e. repaired electric appliances)
Inability to monitor, document and quantify the impacts of 'urban metabolic' processes	Establish monitoring mechanisms and KPIs to document the outcomes and impact of the interventions To create mechanisms to enable easy – immediate assessment, comparison and sharing of best practice

4.3 TO-BE scenario

4.3.1 Overview

The vision of the city of Leuven in the context of Pop-Machina is 'to upscale the city's bottom up initiatives in the circular production section so as to nurture a circular carbon neutral urban ecosystem that safeguards and promotes urban regeneration'.

More specifically, Leuven envisions to work towards a **better management of urban resources** and **material flows** by experimenting with an 'Urban Resource Centre' (URC) and a city 'commodity or (raw) material broker'.

The scope of Leuven's pilot case is in line with the city's urban strategy on circular economy which embodies the concept of working towards an URC. The city aspires to create a 'building material platform', a physical depot/warehouse/library where secondary (reusable or recyclable) building materials will be stored (focusing on construction waste). It will be linked to a makerspace, where makers have access to equipment and also to a spare parts centre/storage room of e-waste that is recuperated from within the city.

Demand and supply for such a material centre will be brought together by the Pop-Machina digital platform, supporting the collaborative production of circular products and services. The main focus of the Leuven pilot is primarily on two waste streams, **construction waste and e-waste**. However, it will be further enlarged, supporting the elaboration of multi-actor projects in the field of **food consumption and food waste preventions** (which is also embedded in a specific programme of roadmap of the city towards climate neutrality).

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project;
- issuing materials 'passport' and validation of products circularity;
- supply and demand of products and services connection;
- networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services;
- transactions of secondary raw materials and circular products;
- organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers and policy makers;
- e-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors;
- inventory of local circular actors;
- connection to public services for citizens requests for waste collection;
- smart contracts for trading and validation circularity;
- community applications/forums;
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives;
- announcements – notifications of the material flows (which ones are available and which ones are requested);
- a solid registration and reservation platform to use workspaces.

4.3.2 Business requirements

Table 3. Business requirements of the city of Leuven

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
The process and volume of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem as well as their location sites are not known in detail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issuing materials 'passport' and validation of products circularity - Supply and demand of products and services connection - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Transactions of secondary raw materials and circular products - Connection to public services for citizens requests for waste collection - Announcements – notifications of the material flows (which ones are available and which ones are requested) - A solid registration and reservation platform to use workspaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Local makers - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Entrepreneurs/traders - Citizens/residents - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Social economy organisations - Higher education/universities and researchers
There is no previous experience on how to promote the maker initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project. - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers and policy makers - E-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Higher education/universities and researchers - NGOs
There is limited knowledge and lack of financial resources for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and validation circularity - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers and policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Local makers - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Citizens/residents - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Social economy organisations - Higher education/universities and researchers
The European and National legal and regulatory framework is unclear on makerspaces, collaborative production, taxation, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers and policy makers - E-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Social economy organisations - Higher education/universities and researchers - NGOs

Table 3. Business requirements of the city of Leuven (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
It is hard to motivate, educate and actively involve citizens in circular practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issuing materials 'passport' and validation of products circularity - Supply and demand of products and services connection - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Inventory of local circular actors - Connection to public services for citizens requests for waste collection - Announcements – notifications of the material flows (which ones are available and which ones are requested) - Community applications/forums - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Citizens/residents - Entrepreneurs/traders - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Social economy organisations - Higher education/universities and researchers - NGOs
Spaces that could be repurposed for makes spaces have not been fully identified and their suitability has not been thoroughly examined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project - E-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors - Inventory of local circular actors - Community applications/forums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Makerspaces administrators - Social economy organisations - Higher education/universities and researchers
Lack of viable business models and manufacturing to a sufficiently large scale, to support the commercialisation of maker products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issuing materials 'passport' and validation of products circularity - Supply and demand of products and services connection - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Transactions of secondary raw materials and circular products - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers and policy makers - E-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors - Smart contracts for trading and validation circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local makers - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Entrepreneurs/traders - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Social economy organisations
Validating circular production of the maker products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project - Issuing materials 'passport' and validation of products circularity - Inventory of local circular actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Local makers - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Entrepreneurs/traders - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Higher education/universities and researchers

Table 3. Business requirements of the city of Leuven (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Accrediting the safety and quality of the maker products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors - Good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local/regional authorities - Local makers - Innovative R&D spin off companies - Entrepreneurs/traders - Managers of resources and materials (i.e. Construction/Demolition sector, waste management organisations) - Higher education/universities and researchers

4.4 Use cases

4.4.1 Overview

The Leuven pilot will focus on two circular economy initiatives.

The **building materials platform**: In the [Urban Mining](#) case of Leuven, valuable building materials from an urban environment are ‘mined’. Urban Mining intercepts these materials for the recycling process, stores them in a materials bank and offers them for reuse to new construction projects. Leuven will create a ‘building material platform’, a physical depot/warehouse/‘library’ where secondary (reusable or recyclable) materials will be stored. The focus is mainly, but not exclusively, on wood and steel. Demand and supply for such a material centre will be brought together by the digital platform. The aim is to create a permanent platform, a Pop-Machina spin-off that can support the breakthrough of collaborative production by Leuven’s citizens.

The **Maakleerplek**: This makerspace will have its own infrastructure, including equipment such as a 3D printer, a laser cutter, a machine for conditioning secondary building streams to prepare them for recycling, and/or other equipment. It is a place that stimulates the pioneering spirit and where failure and retry are allowed. It is an open place where sharing experience and knowledge is central and where everyone is welcome, for whatever purpose. The professionalisation of business models of circular makers, the link with the spatial development of the city to support collaborative production, and cooperation with local makers/stakeholders are also focus elements of the Makerspace (Maakleerplek).

The objective is to combine the buildings material platform with several other maker initiatives in the same location, turning it into an integrated, central makerspace (‘collaborative production hub’) with high visibility for Leuven and the surrounding communities.

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- good practices and success stories case studies as well as examples developed in the frames of the project;
- issuing materials ‘passport’ and validation of products circularity;
- supply and demand of products and services connection;
- networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services;
- transactions of secondary raw materials and circular products;
- organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers and policy makers;
- e-library to access applicable legislation, technical guides, data and good practices for circular economy actors;
- inventory of local circular actors;
- connection to public services for citizens requests for waste collection;

- smart contracts for trading and validation circularity;
- community applications/forums;
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives;
- announcements – notifications of the material flows (which ones are available and which ones are requested);
- a solid registration and reservation platform to use workspaces.

4.4.2 Leuven pilot use cases

The following use cases have been created to be used as examples of how the aforementioned business process would come to practice in typical situations of the Leuven Pop-Machina pilot. To this end a general description is presented in the form of proposed use cases of the two initiatives in order to extract the needed user requirements.

4.4.2.1 The Building Materials Platform

This initiative has as an objective that is in line with the city’s urban strategy on circular economy to create an urban resource centre – building materials platform. The Building Materials Platform is a Physical Warehouse of Construction Materials that can be recycled and reused. The goal is to feed the city’s makerspace with materials and collect materials in cooperation with the city and citizens engaging thus the participation of citizens from Leuven in the circular economy and the Maker Movement

The main goals for this case are described as follows:

- to foster a thriving community of Urban Miners in Leuven and establish a physical depot where building materials are stored;
- to link citizens with urban miners and promote the circular economy by providing materials that can be reused;
- to bring together demand and supply for construction materials and support the collaborative production of circular products and services.

Use case 1: Urban mining

Mark is a citizen from Leuven who wishes to renovate his house. He will need to discard construction waste as well as his old furniture. However, Mark is a person of high environmental awareness, and thus he wishes to see all his construction products recycled or upcycled. Other users in this use case scenario are the Municipality, the Urban Miners and the Building Materials Platform (BMP) administrators.

Mark contacts the Municipality in order to request the collection of construction materials. The user provides the location and conduct details and gives consent to handle the process using the Pop-Machina platform. The user registers in the platform to initiate the process. He then completes an application for urban mining that is forwarded through the platform to the Urban Miners. He registers the address, contact data (and if possible), he uploads pictures of the house or even furniture he would like to give away. Along with the pictures he uploads a small description of ‘the story’ of what he would like to give away. The user will receive a message through the platform to make arrangements (date and time) for the urban mining. Once the mining of the building is complete the user is provided with a certificate for the materials that were collected, and the credits/coins awarded in the Pop-Machina platform for purchases within the platform.

The Municipality follows the process and gets data on the quantity and type of materials collected.

Urban Miners receive the application through the platform and by the pictures and the ‘stories’ uploaded by Mark and they decide whether they wish to proceed with the mining. The miners publicly post materials’ pictures that might be of interest to other users of the platform, and they organise

collections according to requests (so as to avoid temporary storage). Then, they contact Mark to book an appointment using the relative form in the platform. The miners access data on space availability in the warehouse and materials requests from the Pop-Machina application and are thus able to organise their activities. Through the open knowledge module, Urban Miners access the safety regulations required for the specific project.

Urban Miners collect materials (wood – metal – electronics) and products from Mark's house. Materials that may be upcycled are sorted in categories based on the specifications available on the platform and possible requests for specific products uploaded by local maker citizens. Specific requests are handled directly through the platform and the rest selected materials are led to the BMP. Based on the quantities delivered to the BMP the miners can also be awarded credits/coins for purchases and services within the platform.

Once the mining process starts the BMP automatically (based on the mining set date) receives input from the platform in order to start organising a collection and storage area.

Upon delivery at the warehouse their circularity is accredited (materials passport issued – traceability) and materials are registered in the system.

Both the miners and the warehouse use the option to upload pictures - details for materials on stock to enable the flow of materials.

Materials on the platform are presented in a menu that includes wood – metals – electronics and other products (i.e. tables, cupboards, desks) for all users to be able to filter the searches.

4.4.2.2 Maakleerplek makerspace

The Maakleerplek makerspace has as an objective that is in line with the city's vision 'to upscale the city's bottom, up initiatives in the circular production sector'. The makerspace is a learning place that, from a local basis, stands for cooperation across sectors, domains and target groups. It is an open place that stimulates the pioneering spirit and a place where sharing experience and knowledge is central.

The main goals for this case are described as follows:

- to support the collaborative production of circular products and services;
- to upscale the city's bottom up initiatives into circular production and foster the thriving maker community in Leuven;
- to link citizens among them and to support collaboration in a common makerspace.

Having in mind these goals, the 'Maakleerplek' use case will host a series of activities in which citizens from Leuven will be invited in a common space to be engaged in circular maker activities, share their knowledge and help each other. Maakleerplek will be supported by the Building Materials Platform for the supply of materials.

Use case 2: Daily basis makers

George is a maker from Leuven with years of experience who wishes to use the available tools at the Prototyping Lab of the Maakleerplek. He wants to repair the plastic cover and screen of his mobile phone that broke. Firstly, he creates an account in the Pop-Machina platform, obtaining an initial set of credits. Then, he books the machine he wants to use during an available timeframe. As he already has some knowledge using 3D printers, he creates the design and prints the plastic cover for his mobile at the Prototyping lab facilities, which will cost him most of the credits available in his account. In addition, to earn some more credits for future use, he decides to upload his design into the platform, making it available to other users of the Maakleerplek.

At the same time, through the Pop-Machina platform, he checks the database of URC for spare parts for his mobile. He finds a replacement screen, which costs him some more credits. He nonetheless needs a connecting part that is not available in the URC and to this end he makes an announcement in the platform for the specific electronic part. John who is also a member of the Pop-

Machina platform has the spare part George is looking for and sends a direct message. They agree to exchange the spare part for an hour of training in 3D printing. George can be recognised as a contributor to the Pop-Machina platform once the transaction is complete.

John has heard about the Maakleerplek, but he neither has any knowledge about the usage of the available tools and machinery, nor about creating any design for them. Nonetheless, the Maakleerplek offers the opportunity for training. Thus, John creates an account and exchanges spare parts of electronic devices for a certain amount of credits. Using these credits, John can now receive training on the use of the machines and get access to available designs. This exchange will give part of the credits to other makers, while John can use the prototyping lab.

Use case 3: Organised initiatives

User X is an established maker initiative. User X wishes to use the lab (low tech/prototyping) in Maakleerplek on a regular basis to create circular products. Firstly, the user creates an account in the Pop-Machina platform, obtaining an initial set of credits (which is higher for initiatives than for individual users). Then, the user books the lab and machines needed to use on a specific timeframe. Booking the lab costs a specific number of tokens/credits.

The initiative purchases materials from the Building Materials Platform (wood - metal) and/or the Spare Parts Centre in exchange for credits.

Products produced from circular materials in the makerspace lab can be traced and are thus accredited as circular.

The initiative then uploads pictures and availability of products in the platform at a given cost (in credits) so as to receive additional credits for the use of the makerspace laboratories. Registered users of the platform place their orders. The initiative also organises trainings in the use of equipment and uploads designs in the platform to receive additional credits.

Use case 4: Networking

The Maakleerplek wishes to build its network of interest of circular actors. They need to be able to contact and interact with makers and circular actors as well as have a dynamic communication with them. As stakeholders of the Leuven Maker Community, the NGO decides to take on the opportunity offered to registered members to establish contact among them depending on their needs. The Maakleerplek draws a profile in the Pop-Machina platform and initiates interaction with members of the platform. Their goal to build a network of interest is successful and they manage through the platform to promote their work in circular economy. In exchange, they offer their services to the platform (trainings, participation in events, and addition of new members). Makers and circular actors gain from this interaction as they can discuss policy issues, ask questions in the field of the NGO expertise and interact with an extended network of makers.

Use case 5: Training (synchronous and asynchronous)

Asynchronous training

Jack is an amateur maker and is interested in repairing his blow dryer. He has heard of the Maakleerplek and registers in the Pop-Machina platform to be able to access all available information. Upon his registration he receives a number of credits. Initially he goes through the section of the platform where information on repair guidelines is openly available (i.e. legislation, safety issues, good practices).

Once he gets a good idea on basic repair guidelines, he realises he needs to access specific designs and instructions. A specific section is available in Pop-Machina that has been uploaded by other users. To access this information, he exchanges some of his tokens. Jack is also able to exchange materials for a certain number of tokens.

Synchronous training

John, who is subscribed to the mailing list of the platform, receives an email with an invitation for a training opportunity. This email was not only showing the next training activities to be held in the Maakleerpleek, but also the possibilities of becoming a trainer for the maker community. As the user already has some knowledge on machinery used in the high-tech lab, decides to apply, and prepare a talk for the event. The platform registers this request and reserves an available spot in the training event.

On the other hand, another user wants to improve his knowledge on laser cutting to be able to create his own products in the future. Thus, once he receives the notification about the next training event, he registers as an attendant. As part of this event and the activities related to them, it is required to bring some materials (such as HDPE i.e. plastic cups from water bottles) to the event to be reused.

Once the event is finalised, the trainers receive credits for the community support, and they are acknowledged as ‘training experts’ in the social networks and website from the Pop-Machina platform.

Use case 6: Organisation of Events

The makerspace administration organises an event and contacts the maker community and the general public to take part through the platform, in order to raise awareness on circular economy. The maker community is invited to host a laboratory or a training session or to exhibit its products. The makers who will help in or support the event will be awarded with tokens. Citizens taking part in the training events are asked to offer products (e.g. plastics, old electrical appliances) in exchange.

After their participation in the event, makers become known to the community and are able to promote their products.

4.5 User requirements

Table 4. User requirements of the city of Leuven

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that I ...
URL01	Local - Regional Authorities	know the stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	can monitor the upcycling process
URL02	Local - Regional Authorities	know the stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	can monitor legislation development
URL03	Local - Regional Authorities	know the stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	can quantify the interest in raw materials and build favourable environment for further growth
URL04	Local - Regional Authorities	map the network ecosystem	can monitor the upcycling process
URL05	Local - Regional Authorities	map the network ecosystem	can help connect them to citizens and I can assist in networking
URL06	Local - Regional Authorities	map the network ecosystem	can assist in networking
URL07	Local - Regional Authorities	have a database of good practices	can organise the promotion of maker activities
URL08	Local - Regional Authorities	have a database of developed strategies (by different cities)	can enhance exchange of communications between cities under the same region
URL09	Local - Regional Authorities	have a database of applicable legislation	can facilitate training and business support sessions
URL10	Local - Regional Authorities	technical, safety and quality guides	can facilitate training and business support sessions
URL11	Local - Regional Authorities	learn more on procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context	can promote green procurement
URL12	Local - Regional Authorities	connect public services to citizens requests	can actively involve them in circular practices
URL13	Local - Regional Authorities	produce documentation and quantification of circular activities	can inform the public of the impact of circular activities
URL14	Local - Regional Authorities	be able to validate products circularity (product passport)	can support the promotion of maker products
URL15	Local Maker	have data on the materials origin	know that materials I purchase are circular
URL16	Local Maker	be able to search for raw/secondary materials availability	can decide if I can make a product
URL17	Local Maker	be able to search for raw/secondary products availability	can schedule my production
URL18	Local Maker	know if there are workspaces available	can produce specific products
URL19	Local Maker	be able to book a workspace	can schedule production
URL20	Local Maker	know if citizens want to give away materials	can collect them if they are of interest to me
URL21	Local Maker	get training/education	can promote my products

Table 4. User requirements of the city of Leuven (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that I ...
URL22	Local Maker	get training/education	can procure services and products
URL23	Local Maker	get training/education	can improve my products and processes
URL24	Local Maker	have access on the regulatory framework	can run my business lawfully
URL25	Local Maker	have access on the regulatory framework	accredit the safety and quality of my products
URL26	Local Maker	be able to contact and interact with other makers	can exchange information and good practices
URL27	Local Maker	be able to contact and interact with other makers	can scale up my production and increase my sales
URL28	Local Maker	be able to subcontract part of the production process to other makers	yo improve my production yield
URL29	Local Maker	be able to contact and interact with citizens/companies/shops/makers	to provide information on my products
URL30	Local Maker	be able to contact and interact with citizens/companies/shops/makers	to sell my products
URL31	Local Maker	have data on the quality and technical specifications of material	know that materials I purchase are safe to be used *
URL32	Local Maker	have dynamic communication/ask questions	get prompt responses from other makers/citizens or the platform admin*
URL33	Local Maker	get mentoring on how to develop my project/built my product	can build my products
URL34	Local Maker	have a workflow or methodology to define the price of my product	now what price I can sell my product
URL35	Local Maker	be able to upload pictures of material I want to give away	inform people what material is available
URL36	Local Maker	know about regulatory framework	find info about subsidies I can get to start a social business; open a makerspace
URL37	Local Maker	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL38	Innovative R&D spin off company	have access on good practices and success stories	gain knowledge
URL39	Innovative R&D spin off company	be able to contact and interact with actors of the makers ecosystem	to network with them and achieve cooperation to study and research circular product and service development
URL40	Innovative R&D spin off company	be able to contact and interact with actors of other R&D companies	can exchange information and good practices
URL41	Innovative R&D spin off company	be able to contact and interact with actors of the makers ecosystem	can cooperate in product and service development
URL42	Innovative R&D spin off company	be able to contact and interact with actors of the makers ecosystem	can provide technical knowledge and know how
URL43	Innovative R&D spin off company	get technical and business training	can improve my service and processes
URL44	Innovative R&D spin off company	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy

Table 4. User requirements of the city of Leuven (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that I ...
URL45	Innovative R&D spin off company	know about regulatory framework	find info about subsidies I can get for innovative activities
URL46	Entrepreneur/trader	be able to search for products availability	can schedule my production
URL47	Entrepreneur/trader	get training/education	can procure services and products
URL48	Entrepreneur/trader	be able to contact and interact with other entrepreneurs /traders	can exchange information and good practices
URL49	Entrepreneur/trader	be able to contact and interact with makers	can purchase circular products
URL50	Entrepreneur/trader	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL51	Entrepreneur/trader	have data and documentation on the materials/products origin	know that materials I purchase and trade are circular
URL52	Entrepreneur/trader	get training/education	can procure circular services and products
URL53	Entrepreneur/trader	get mentoring on how to develop my project/built my service	provide a service in circular economy
URL54	Entrepreneur/trader	be able to upload pictures of material I want to give away	inform people what material is available
URL55	Entrepreneur/trader	know in advance the expected material to arrive in the physical warehouse	can plan timely my activity in trading
URL56	Entrepreneur/trader	know how /where I can give away my waste	inform the correct people
URL57	Citizen/resident	know the different maker movements and what they do	know whom to contact if I want to give away material
URL58	Citizen/resident	know the different maker movements and what they do	know whom to contact if I want to become part of a movement
URL59	Citizen/resident	know about regulatory framework	start a maker place
URL60	Citizen/resident	know about regulatory framework	find info about subsidies I can get to start a social business; open a makerspace
URL61	Citizen/resident	have dynamic communication/ask questions	get prompt responses from other makers/citizens or the platform admin
URL62	Citizen/resident	get mentoring on how to develop my project/built my product	build my products
URL63	Citizen/resident	be able to upload pictures of material I want to give away	inform people what material is available
URL64	Citizen/resident	have proof on the materials origin and processing	know that materials I purchase are circular
URL65	Citizen/resident	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL66	Citizen/resident	to be informed if certain materials are needed	may have to give away
URL67	NGO	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL68	NGO	get training/education	am better informed on circular economy good practices, legislation

Table 4. User requirements of the city of Leuven (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that I ...
URL69	NGO	be able to contact and interact with makers and circular actors	achieve networking with the sector
URL70	NGO	have dynamic communication/ask questions makers and circular actors	can motivate, educate and actively involve them in circular practices
URL71	NGO	have documented and quantified evidence of the impact of circular and maker initiatives	can support policy improvement arguments
URL72	Makerspace administrator	get educated on good practices and success stories	gain knowledge on how to promote the makerspace
URL73	Makerspace administrator	get training/education	can improve my service and processes
URL74	Makerspace administrator	have access on the regulatory framework	can run my business lawfully
URL75	Makerspace administrator	have access on the regulatory framework	accredit the safety and quality of my products and processes
URL76	Makerspace administrator	know of the processes and volume of materials and makers of the maker ecosystem	offer the tools, methods and space for their operations
URL77	Makerspace administrator	a solid registration and reservation platform	book my workspace
URL78	Makerspace administrator	be able to contact and interact with makers and circular actors	promote my product/service
URL79	Makerspace administrator	know about regulatory framework	find info about subsidies. I can get to start a social business; open a makerspace
URL80	Makerspace administrator	have dynamic communication/ask questions	get prompt responses from other makerspace administrators/makers/citizens or the platform admin
URL81	Makerspace administrator	have a workflow or methodology to define the price of my product	know what price I can sell my product-service
URL82	Makerspace administrator	be able to upload pictures of machinery, materials and the space	inform people what material and methods available at the makerspace
URL83	Makerspace administrator	be able to contact and interact with makers	to sell my products - services
URL84	Makerspace administrator	know if citizens want to give away materials	can collect them if they are of interest to me
URL85	Manager of resources/materials	get educated on good practices and success stories	gain knowledge on how to promote my materials
URL86	Manager of resources/materials	get training/education	can improve my products and processes
URL87	Manager of resources/materials	be able to upload pictures of material I want to give away	inform people what material is available
URL88	Manager of resources/materials	have access on the regulatory framework	can run my business lawfully
URL89	Manager of resources/materials	have access on the regulatory framework	accredit the safety and quality of my products and processes and I can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL90	Manager of resources/materials	know how/where I can give away my waste	inform the correct people

Table 4. User requirements of the city of Leuven (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that I ...
URL91	Manager of resources/materials	get training/education	can procure circular services and products
URL92	Higher education institute	have access on good practices and success stories	gain knowledge
URL93	Higher education institute	be able to contact and interact with actors of the makers ecosystem	can network with them and achieve cooperation to study and research circular product and service development, so that we can exchange information and good practices and get feedback on their needs and requirements
URL94	Higher education institute	be able to contact and interact with actors of the makers ecosystem	can provide scientific knowledge and know how
URL95	Higher education institute	research documentation and quantification of circular activities	can research the impact of circular activities
URL96	Higher education institute	research the impact of circular activities	
URL97	Higher education institute	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL98	Social economy organisation	have access on the regulatory framework	can get actively involved in policy discussions for circular economy
URL99	Social economy organisation	get training/education	am better informed on circular economy good practices, legislation
URL100	Social economy organisation	be able to contact and interact with makers and circular actors	achieve networking with the sector
URL101	Social economy organisation	have dynamic communication/ask questions makers and circular actors	can motivate, educate and actively involve beneficiaries in circular practices
URL102	Social economy organisation	be able to contact and interact with makerspaces	beneficiaries can use them
URL103	Social economy organisation	get training/education	can experiment with new materials
URL104	Social economy organisation	get training/education	can give directions and re-educate beneficiaries
URL105	Social economy organisation	have documented and quantified evidence of the impact of circular and maker initiatives	can support policy improvement arguments
URL106	Social economy organisation	be able to search for raw/secondary materials availability	can decide if I can make a product
URL107	Social economy organisation	be able to contact and interact with citizens/companies/shops/makers	can provide information on the organisation's products
URL108	Social economy organisation	get mentoring on how to develop my project/built my product	build the organisation's products
URL109	Social economy organisation	be able to upload pictures of material I want to give away	inform people what material is available

5. City of Thessaloniki

5.1 Introduction

Thessaloniki is a medium sized city of approximately 325,000 inhabitants in its core urbanised area, reaching about 1 million in its metropolitan region. It has been severely affected by the ongoing economic crisis that started in Greece in 2009/2010, resulting in phenomena such as brain drain, population ageing, unemployment, decaying infrastructures, vacant properties and limited financial and operational capabilities of the public sector.

The city can benefit from Pop-Machina in the following ways:

- achieve a thorough understanding of the structure and spatial distribution of information and material flows in the city and the bottlenecks therein, and such as information and collaboration gaps across systems that hinder the closing of the circular loop;
- identify, mobilise and connect untapped sources of knowledge and competencies that could contribute to the closing of the circular loops;
- bridge the start-up innovation community with society, in order to provide more and more relevant ideas to start-ups and better solutions to the needs of residents;
- support the actual development and commercialisation of circular products and services with a potential to create new jobs and promote urban regeneration in the area;
- promote the development of more sustainable and liveable urban forms by improving the quality, quantity and accessibility of its public and shared spaces, enhancing connectivity amongst key structures and communities, and greening urban functions and land uses;
- experiment and innovate with tokenisation in a local economy context, creating a hybrid (digital and material) ecosystem;
- enhance awareness and capabilities on the potential of circular thinking, tinkering and collaborative production;
- ultimately, foster sustainable, organic, bottom-up urban regeneration.

5.2 Current situation

5.2.1 Overview

Despite the challenges of the recent years, there exist specific technological and innovation areas in which Thessaloniki has managed to stay ahead, and these constitute sources of strength for the city in the context of Pop-Machina. These include (Pop-Machina relevant properties):

- the city is home to vibrant, self-sustained digital start-up community, comprising mainly of young university graduates;
- the city has in place strategies both for waste management and for urban resilience, which are slowly but steadily being implemented with the support of bottom-up resources;
- overall, the city has an open and co-creative culture for social innovation, which is in large spontaneous and self-regulated. Many citizen groups, NGOs and social cooperatives operate here.

The most important **initiatives** relevant to the project in Thessaloniki include:

- [the Local Plan for the Decentralised Waste Management of the Municipality of Thessaloniki](#), which includes measures to increase reusing, repairing and recycling, develop green points, map location of related projects and resources on GIS application, etc.;
- [the Resilient Thessaloniki Strategy](#). Among its foreseen actions are to reframe waste management in the city by improving waste collection, increasing recycling and up cycling streams and promoting green public procurement. These will influence consumption patterns, encourage re-use and repair, establish Green Spots and seminars and activities for up-cycling. The development of urban composting systems will also be explored;
- the activity of **several start-ups in the digitised services and products domain**. Relevant to Pop-Machina, i.e., some start-ups develop products/services for sustainable development and more efficient resource management and ii. some teams build custom made cases and other parts for the products they develop; these are manufactured by means of 3D printing and other maker technologies; occasionally they might need large quantities of those cases, esp. when they are testing them with users or at initial stages of commercialisation;
- the existence of many (circa 10) **social enterprises and cooperatives** that are active in the circular waste management, urban agriculture, food production and distribution, and access to the job market domain. All of them seem to operate with a limited and recurring set of partners. Also, none of them seems to be especially organised platform-wise -many of them do not even have a proper website, they just operate through social media. They would benefit from (i) collaboration/connection to potential partners as well as (ii) better promotion/visibility to be made known;
- the existence of **do-it-yourself urbanism grassroots movements**, driven by community groups commissioned to improve the quality and quantity of public space and social cohesion, and using/reusing cheap first materials. Examples of initiatives include: temporary pedestrianisation of Ag. Sofias street, neighbourhood rooms, pocket parks, etc. Most of them operate spontaneously and on social media. They would benefit from (i) access to new ideas, (ii) access to potential sources of funding, (iii) collaboration/connection to potential partners and community members, (iv) better promotion/visibility to be made known and generally (v) help with formulating a more strategic approach and organising their activities better;
- the recent **'Zero Waste Cities'** corporate social responsibility programme of Coca-Cola that includes three initiatives: (i) 'Print Your City', an initiative that empowers citizens to design useful items (public seats, bicycle stations, etc.) that will be created by plastic waste through 3D printing, and then decide their desired location in public areas of Thessaloniki; (ii) 'Recycle at the Beach', aiming to clean up the coast of Thessaloniki, boost awareness for recycling and educate people on how to recycle'; (iii) An interactive recycling and circular economy centre in the city centre. However, it seems that this initiative ran in late 2018-early 2019 for a predefined period and now is inactive. The only related digital application is the website where one can produce a digital model of a circular item: <https://www.printyourcitycoca-cola.gr>.

5.2.2 Current business process models

Makers and citizens interact with the city authorities through the common communication channels offered by the city (citizen phone line, email, social media). They also use the application 'Improve my City' to report abandoned waste in public spaces and request from the city authorities to collect it (<https://imc.thessaloniki.gr/imc>).

Regarding the processes and responsibilities of the city departments related to Pop-Machina, these are:

- [Directorate of Operational Programming & Information and Communication Technology Systems](#). This directorate develops and monitors the operational planning, related to the strategy

and the implementation of the vision of the municipality administration, making optimal use of the resources available. It also monitors the financing of actions/projects and supports the actions selected through the optimal implementation of specific procedures. In addition, it is responsible for the development, installation, operation and maintenance of ICT systems of the Municipality. It is relevant to the technical and financial management of Pop-Machina;

- **Directorate for Entrepreneurship**. This directorate undertakes infrastructure initiatives and actions that, through the absorption of co-funded programmes, stimulates and encourages entrepreneurship, combats youth unemployment and creates new jobs. It also supports the partnerships between the academic/research bodies, the European organisations and the businesses with main focus on investing in innovation and the transfer of know-how. It enhances the communication and the interaction between the stakeholder entities concerned, as well as the dissemination of the Pop-Machina Project actions/events. It is worth noting, that the innovation ecosystem of Thessaloniki (OK!THESS) is a developmental action of this directorate. It is relevant to the technical and financial management, as well as the ecosystem mapping and circular innovation and entrepreneurship building activities of Pop-Machina;
- **Directorate for Recycling & Urban Waste Management**. It is responsible for ensuring the regular collection and transfer of solid waste in the city, ensuring the cleanliness of public areas, as well as the management of the urban waste by applying new programmes in all the recycling flows. It is ensuring that environmentally friendly waste management is achieved, based on the 'recycling principles' but also on the reuse of materials by applying recycling methods, saving energy and respecting environmental needs. Additionally, it organises awareness and information campaigns (festivals, printed material, workshops, advertising spots, etc.) by reinforcing the need for co-operation by the side of the residents and aiming at stimulating their active participation. It is relevant to the circular production activities of Pop-Machina;
- **Directorate of urban planning and architectural projects**. Ensures the promotion and improvement of the natural and built environment through the formulation and promotion of urban sustainability policies, the protection of architectural heritage, the promotion of modern architectural creation and the improvement of the quality of life in general, through the preparation of studies and ensuring the conditions for the implementation of urban design and urban planning at the level of the Municipality of Thessaloniki from national and European resources. It is relevant to the urban regeneration activities of Pop-Machina;
- **Directorate of Construction & Conservations**. It is responsible for the construction and maintenance of municipal buildings, schools and public spaces and outdoor and electromechanical installations. It is relevant to the urban regeneration activities of Pop-Machina;
- **Directorate of Building and Planning Applications**. Includes the GIS Department which works with public and private data providers, to ensure continued access to data and long-term data storage and archiving. It is relevant to the ecosystem mapping and urban regeneration activities of Pop-Machina.

Makers and citizens interact with each other and other external entities through commonly used communication channels (face to face, email, social media). There are no dedicated software systems that participate in the relevant business processes.

5.2.3 Stakeholders' identification

The user groups that interact for purposes relevant to the project are:

Table 5. Stakeholders identified in the city of Thessaloniki

User group	Role
Local governmental authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the policy challenges and priorities to be addressed by the project - Orchestrate resources and material flows - Foster the development of maker communities - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to making and circular production - Provide and receive know-how, tinkering ideas and practices - Connect with other makers and communities to exchange ideas, collaborate in new product/service development, and acquire materials and parts required for their circular endeavours - Develop circular products and services - Receive proper technical and business training in order to develop more mature circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Start uppers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to making and circular production - Provide and receive know-how, innovative ideas and practices - Connect with other start-up teams, makers and communities to exchange ideas, collaborate in new product/service development, and acquire materials and parts required for their circular endeavours - Develop circular products and services - Receive proper technical and business training in order to develop more mature circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Citizens/residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to new circular products and services - Help identify, mobilise and connect untapped sources of knowledge and competencies that could contribute to the closing of the circular loops - Help identify and select urban areas and spaces that could benefit from DIY urbanism in the context of Pop-Machina - Upvote the most desired products and services developed by the makers and start uppers of Pop-Machina - Validate the quality, usefulness and sustainability of the circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Makerspaces administrators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Obtain construction and operations permits from city - Offer tools, methods and space for the operation of the maker movement - Foster the development of maker communities - Suggest best practices in circular production - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Managers of resources and materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Suggest best practices in circular production - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide scientific knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Social Cooperatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Suggest best practices in circular production - Provide applied knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy

5.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

In the table below we describe the challenges of Thessaloniki in the context of Pop-Machina and the potential of the project to address them.

Challenge	Pop-Machina potential
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	To collect, store and provide the relevant data and analytics based on this data
Lack of previous applied knowledge on how to promote maker initiatives	To educate and train stakeholders (particularly the city, makerspace administrators and makers) on how to develop, manage initiatives related to circular endeavours
Lack of resources (financial, knowledge) for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context	To educate, train and provide the necessary means to stakeholders (particularly the city, makerspace administrators and makers) to finance initiatives, exploit results, obtain certifications and manage IPR related to circular endeavours
Unsupportive/unclear legal and regulatory framework in areas such as collaborative production, social entrepreneurship, etc.	To identify the framework conditions of those operations and make demand driven suggestions for streamlining and improvement; to use data-driven intelligence on how these conditions could be improved; to fuel the policy debate on how these conditions could be improved
Further raising of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.	To increase awareness and promote sustainable cultures and behaviours through a structured approach, driven by results
Identifying and repurposing spaces into makerspaces	To use data and grassroots knowledge to identify the appropriate spaces and repurpose them according to user needs
Supporting the commercialisation of maker products	To develop appropriate business models and business support services for the makers - entrepreneurs of Pop-Machina
Inability to document and quantify the impacts of circular and maker initiatives	To use proper (if possible real-time) monitoring mechanisms and KPIs to document the outcomes and impact of the interventions

5.3 TO-BE scenario

5.3.1 Overview

The vision for Thessaloniki in the context of Pop-Machina is ‘To improve the framework for generating employment opportunities, support tech and science start-ups and experiment with do-it-yourself urbanism in the context of the circular economy.’

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- get inspiration from best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places;
- organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers;
- trading and buying secondary raw materials;
- trading and buying circular products, certified for circularity;
- smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity;
- identifying potential collaborators in circular endeavours;
- community applications/forums;
- organising and offering training for policy makers;
- access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, lawyers, IT policy makers, etc.);
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives.

It would be very helpful if the above information, where relevant, could also be depicted through spatial/mapping applications (GIS) that feature the exact location of the materials, products, makers, etc.

5.3.2 Business requirements

Table 6. Business requirements of the city of Thessaloniki

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trading and buying secondary raw materials - Trading and buying circular products, certified for circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens/residents - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Social Cooperatives
Lack of previous applied knowledge on how to promote maker initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning
Lack of resources (financial, knowledge) for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering training for policy makers - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Social Cooperatives
Unsupportive/unclear legal and regulatory framework in areas such as waste management, collaborative production, social entrepreneurship, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - Local governmental authorities - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives
Lack of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - More interactive, real-time communication with city authorities - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Citizens/residents - Social Cooperatives
Identifying and repurposing spaces into makerspaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Community applications/forums - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Social Cooperatives
Supporting the commercialisation of maker products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Social Cooperatives

Table 6. Business requirements of the city of Thessaloniki (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Inability to document and quantify the impacts of circular and maker initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - More interactive, real-time communication with city authorities - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning

5.4 Use cases

5.4.1 Overview

Thessaloniki is a city heavily affected by several opposing forces. Fostering a vibrant student community amongst its several universities, research entities and polytechnic schools it is easily characterised as a young people’s urban environment. However, the lack of jobs and professional/entrepreneurial options, not only leads to a failure to capitalise on its younger audience, it has also given fuel to the extended brain drain recorded over the last decade. In addition, the city and its surrounding areas, due to their proximity to Greece’s northern borders, have seen a dramatic influx of refugees who subsequently remained trapped in the region and a percentage of them are expected to be assimilated to the local population.

The city’s answer to the above is its investment into initiatives to support the primary and tertiary sectors, amongst which is its resolve to nurture entrepreneurial efforts by students as well as innovative local SMEs, which in turn can constitute the driving force behind local investments. The vehicle towards this goal, among others, is the OK!Thess initiative, a pre-incubation and acceleration programme, which for the past 3 years has supported a significant number of teams mostly active in the ICT field, agritech and tourism. OK!Thess is currently facilitating one of the most active start-up ecosystems in Greece, as it has managed to amass a vibrant and diverse set of local meetups, start-ups, entrepreneurs and investors, as well as create ties with other ecosystems active in the wider Balkan region.

However, OK!Thess has not managed thus far to support local makers to the desirable extend due to lack of the necessary facilities required to provide the motivation and ease of access to prototyping tools and machinery. Participating in the Pop-Machina project, provides this opportunity for the initiative to expand its reach to the maker community and enrich it with its knowledge and expertise leading to new areas of entrepreneurial interest that could facilitate local efforts, lead to re-skilling and up-skilling or even support efforts with a more international scope.

5.4.2 Thessaloniki pilot use cases

The Municipality of Thessaloniki is processing annually over 140 metric tons of recyclable material including metal, plastic, wood, and structural material. Conversely, several makers currently active in the city are already working in the repair and upcycling field, giving discarded old furniture or metallic material new life and targeting the second hand as well as the artisan markets.

Pop-Machina poses an interesting opportunity, whereby the municipality considers that circular economy practises can be leveraged into feeding the makers community with raw material’, training and ideas. When coupling this with the knowledge and expertise of OK!Thess on structuring an entrepreneurial effort one could be facing a winning combination.

5.4.2.1 Use case 1: OK!Thess & Pop-Machina Makerspace Pilot

Building and running a makerspace in conjunction with OK!Thess and within its premises, has been the main reason for participating in the project. This effort poses three major challenges:

1. upskilling the people involved in the initiative to be able to support ‘making’, know the equipment and machinery required, acknowledging timeframes for prototyping and understanding the needs as well as the risks involved;
2. running a makerspace efficiently in terms of procurement processes, scheduling access, maker management;
3. identifying the opportunities for makers and local stakeholders leading to successful collaborations either in terms of knowledge exchange or later in terms of transforming prototyping and experimenting to market potential.

This has thus far led to a hands-on approach by the Pop-Machina project members and members of the OK!Thess initiative in reaching out to makers in the city, discussing with them, understanding their needs, finding common ground into what can be achieved within the frame of the project and prioritising the premises upon which the makerspace will be implemented to foster diverse needs. Thus, the common ground reached revolves around processing wood (e.g. discarded old furniture), soft metals (e.g. aluminium) and plastic recycling. On top of that, mainly engineering students and architects suggested the need of a fully equipped electronics lab that can support experimentation and novel ideas brought forth by the community with clear differentiating factors and value propositions. In addition, hosting the makerspace within the premises of OK!Thess will double up as a fertile ground for training and knowledge exchange, a hotspot of innovation and serendipity among start uppers and makers, which could very well lead to fruitful collaborations in the future.

Building a vibrant maker community is going to be key towards a successful makerspace. Building on the marketing channels of OK!Thess, reaching out to new makers out there and working in conjunction with other local initiatives in the city of Thessaloniki like the ‘Creativity Platform’, ‘Open Schools’ & ‘Circular Neighbourhoods’ as well as nearby cities, Academia & Research Institutes and international initiatives like ‘Precious Plastic’ and ‘YouThinkGreen’, with the aim is to explore collaborations and diffusion of knowledge. In addition, hackathons and local challenges are expected to play a key role to attracting hobbyists and professionals working side by side with more dedicated makers leading to applicable projects for local neighbourhoods and the municipality.

5.4.2.2 Use case 2: Training & Knowledge Exchange Pilot

OK!Thess has thus far successfully implemented 3 cohorts per year onboarding start-ups, providing training masterclasses, individual coaching, access to market mentors and a chance to institutional funding from Venture Capital Firms and Angel Investors. Training for makers will follow a similar structure in terms of entrepreneurial skillset training and individual coaching. However, it has to be extended with maker specific masterclasses and content relevant to upskilling people and helping makers learn new techniques, experiment with new materials. This content is partly expected to be provided from Pop-Machina partners, but will also be enriched by local/international stakeholders from industry and academia. Ideas and best practices from circular economy standpoint will be elaborated too, with the goal to lead to more options for makers as well as new transferable skills.

One important aspect which has been promoted over the last couple of years by OK!Thess is also the exchange of practises and cross-border collaboration between OK!Thess start-ups and other start-ups across the world. It is believed and proven consistently that it helps start-ups be better aware of the wider picture of the market they are addressing, across geographies. What is however lagging is an active and close collaboration among people countries apart mainly because of lack of a formal process that can recognise their effort and/or lead to future fruitful collaborations without the need for direct reciprocity. It is expected that the proposed tokenisation framework will facilitate collaboration in a manner that supports the regulation of this skills exchange by appending future value to

the time dedicated. Appending a value in work-effort, i.e. digitising IOUs, that can be acquired with a use of a ‘tradable’ token could very well (a) showcase effort and experience among members and (b) liberate creative forces across borders.

5.4.2.3 Use case 3: circular economy Policy Building Pilot

Pop-Machina and its circular economy environment’s focus on the effort of makers are believed to be a good starting point for the municipality of Thessaloniki to source, analyse and extrapolate valuable data. This could lead to informed planning and decision making over the coming years, whilst subsequently support policy making and the city’s relationship with recycling space contractors as well as universities and research institutes.

To this end it will be crucial for the project and the technologies to be implemented to support the collection of valuable datasets via the use and evolution of the makerspace and its community of makers. Material flows and impact of circularity in the local economy must become obvious and clear to attain and interpret. This will in turn provide the required buy-in for the municipal authorities to back future projects as well as include circularity in their agendas. Impact scores could be a stepping-stone into attracting other stakeholders as well, collaborating into driving circular economy and a green agenda for the benefit of the city, its neighbourhoods and citizens alike.

5.5 User requirements

Table 7. User requirements of the city of Thessaloniki

Req. ID	As a	I want to ...	So that ...
URT1	Maker	search for secondary raw materials by type	I can decide if I can make a product
URT2	Manager of resources and materials	have an overview of the materials and their quantities	I can take care of procuring them
URT3	Citizen	see what circular products are available	I can buy them
URT4	Citizen	identify if products are part of the circular economy	I can buy them
URT5	Makerspace administrator	be able to upload educational resources	makers can access and be educated about processes and best practices
URT6	Local government authority/ Makerspace administrator	provide online training to makers who will use the equipment	I can be sure they will safely conduct their work
URT7	Professional/Researcher	contribute with educational content	in order to support the circular movement
URT8	Maker	have access to education and training	I can better use the equipment and also be inspired
URT9	Maker	have access to open source/free designs I could use	I can kick-start my prototyping and small business
URT10	Maker	have a trusted authority verify my products as part of the circular movement and provide me a link	I can reliably market them to my buyers, and they can check authenticity
URT11	Maker	be able to print a QR code for every product I produce	my customers can see where the materials come from and where it was made
URT12	Local government authority/ Makerspace administrator	be able to monitor which materials were used for which product	I can provide my 'seal of approval' for each individual product
URT13	Local government authority/ Makerspace administrator	have enough clarity in terms of legal constraints	I know what my limits are
URT14	Makerspace administrator	have a way of disseminating the progress of what our makers do and produce	the public becomes aware of activities taking place and the city's role in this
URT15	Local government authority	be able to inspire citizens into participating in the circular movement	they become more active and see the benefit for the city
URT16	Local government authority	be able to identify topical interest and groups	I can support them in setting up more circular makerspaces to other areas
URT17	Local government authority	be able to identify topical interest and groups	I can organise the distribution of raw materials gather by the recycling services

Table 7. User requirements of the city of Thessaloniki

Req. ID	As a	I want to ...	So that ...
URT18	Local government authority/ Makerspace administrator	provide the opportunity to makers to showcase their products	they stand a better chance to access consumers
URT19	Maker	have a way to inexpensively showcase my products, set a price and get paid	I can focus on making at the beginning rather than finding the funds to setup an online presence
URT20	Makerspace administrator	help makers find each other and 'procure' skillsets	they can conduct their work better and more efficiently
URT21	Maker	have a way of finding collaborators and make sure they can be rewarded	they can more easily decide to help me with my work
URT22	Maker	have a way of finding collaborators with special knowledge even outside my makerspace	I am not limited to what skillsets are available locally
URT23	Local government authority/ Makerspace administrator	be able to document what happens in terms of what raw materials come in, how many are consumed in making, what could be needed in the future	I can better organise the value chains of the city
URT24	Professional/Researcher	be allowed to use data collected	I can base my work on real world evidence

6. City of Piraeus

6.1 Introduction

The focus area of the action plan of the Municipality of Piraeus is the city centre and the Zea Marina, which is located in one of the 3 largest bays of Piraeus,² namely the bay of Zea, known also as Passalimani. This port has hosted the summer Olympics of 1896 and offers a combination of seaport and yacht marina berthing spots. In ancient times, this was known to be the largest Athenian military harbour. Zea Marina is located in Athens, near the main port of Piraeus. It had been initially founded as a war harbour with shipyards and other installations, at the beginning of the 5th century B.C., before it was converted into a commercial port where millions of tourists start their travel to the Aegean coasts, the Saronic Gulf and the Island of Crete every year. Fully organised, offering facilities and services of high standards, the marina was totally renovated for the 2004 Olympic Games. The Marina has a berthing capacity of 670 yachts up to 120 m and 6 m draught. Within the marina shore area of 40,000 m², 4,780 m² of building installations offer modern and high standard services, such as restaurants, refreshment bars, cafés and commercial shops. In the environs of the marina, there are athletic installations and the Greek War Naval Museum.

Figure 2. Four stages of development, waste treatment, recycling and new-material/technologies

Waste recycling and social engagement are the areas, where the Municipality of Piraeus and Zea Marina mainly anticipate to benefit from Pop-Machina. Waste treatment, recycling and new-material and technologies production are expected to lead to investment attraction in current and future smart city projects (Figure 2).

² <https://www.maritime-database.com/port.php?pid=4427>

The aspiration of the Municipality of Piraeus is the development of a new industrial ecosystem for collaborative production based on waste use, which is collected in the Zea marina. The targeted waste is expected to be treated as it is shown by the steps of Figure 2. The focal points for waste disposal collection are shorelines. Minimisation of waste disposal into landfills or into the sea, with major impact on sea-life and marine-life ecosystems, is the main aim of Piraeus to be accomplished through material re-use. To this end, a number of potential stakeholders have been examined and are presented in the next section.

6.2 Current situation

6.2.1 Overview

The Municipality of Piraeus (PIR) has set its goals considering various challenges affecting its economy as well as its socio-political and environmental sustainability. These challenges are relevant to the municipal self-sufficiency, waste and resource managements, social engagement and the vital environmental challenges, such as sea-water and shoreline pollution as well as the urban heat island effect. To tackle these challenges, the municipality of Piraeus has created a catalogue of tangible methods to develop collaborative production of sustainable solutions and technologies (e.g. based on 3D printing infrastructure using disposed plastics). These are based on the development and use of dedicated, user-friendly tools, which can set the pace of sustainable development bottom-up.

In the context of Pop-Machina, PIR will focus on material re-use and more specifically on creating close-loop blue growth economies. The approach will take advantage of the Internet of Things (IoT) technology, since it is the vision of Piraeus to increase citizens' technological. This involves the development of cutting-edge, low-power consumption technological applications that will promote citizens' engagement in recycling, sustainable growth of Piraeus, as well as innovative collaborative production. Related projects with Piraeus participation are the following: Xtended Coverage GSM for the Internet of Things (EC-GSM-IoT), Long-Term Evolution for Machines (LTE-M) and Narrow-Band Internet of Things (NB-IoT).

Figure 3. The envisioned exploitation of IoT technologies in the municipality of Piraeus

Piraeus Municipality contrary to the outbreak of the urban heat island effect (air pollution and overheating conditions in the city) has developed strategies that are reflected in the ‘blue-growth initiative’, which among others targets also the development of the city smartness in the future. Piraeus is the largest Greek port and the 6th largest port city in Europe and thus, the resolution of the problem of the increased pollution, land and marine-related, under the circumstances of the Greek financial crisis is imperative. The economic downturn is calling for novel bottom-up approaches to spin off circular economies in Piraeus. A strand for such action plans is based in its marine and so-called ‘BLUE-economic’ strategy that includes its connection with other municipalities across the nation (Greece), with the aim of promoting innovation, attracting investments and contributing in its local and global socio-economic, as well as environmental sustainability.

Overall, PIR’s mission is to connect Public – Private – People – Partnerships (4P), in its local and global action plans for the creation of ‘smart infrastructure’ and the symbiosis of different inputs in mitigating local pressing needs and socio-economic as well as environmental challenges (e.g. the minimisation of greenhouse gases by 10-15% annually and the minimisation of the use of water reserves by 20-30% annually). As part of the blue growth strategy of the Municipality of Piraeus, its bluelab³ has been established to promote innovation, technological advancement and sustainability. In the scope of the bluelab initiative, appropriate infrastructure has been employed to educate, empower and support local investments as well as know-how for bottom-up innovation (e.g. through engagement in 3D-printing with use of plastics as a main resource). Consequently, the maximisation of recyclable materials’ use is among the aims of the Municipality of Piraeus action plans. This is expected to mitigate increasing pollution levels in shore areas and coincides with the objectives of Pop-Machina. The following materials have been considered to form recyclables that could be re-used in innovative ways: plastics, textiles, paper and wood. Insulation materials will also be examined as possible materials, mainly to be used by artists. Piraeus envisions the use of these materials in innovative ways to increase local knowledge and know-how, to attract investments, and to let circular economies emerge.

6.2.2 Current business process models

PIR plans overall to follow a qualitative business and research model developed by Strauss and Corbin (1996) , for analysing renewable energy projects. This focuses on the analysis of current and future and is summarised in Figure 4.

With the aim to develop PIR’s 4P initiatives, two maker community groups have been established. These effectively form the beginning of two new and distinct FabLabs based in Piraeus, which are namely the following (briefly described):

- **Blue/lab innovation centre** (<https://www.bluelab.gr>): This is an innovation lab, which has been developed recently by the Municipality of Piraeus focusing on blue (marine and ocean related) economic growth and sustainability. Within the ‘blue’ innovation lab of the Municipality of Piraeus, citizens with an interest in blue development projects can be engaged in municipal resources, software and 3D printing systems and services to develop new skills, experiment with new technologies as well as develop business ideas that will translate into sustainable business plans locally in the near future;
- **Blue Cycle | Beyond marine plastics waste** (<https://bluecycle.com/en/>): Since 2007, BlueCycle operates under the auspices of the Aikaterini Laskaridis Foundation (capital stakeholder) with the vision to create a lab that will offer a new ‘life cycle’ for plastic fishing and shipping gear (bottom-up). Its current research relies on, new technologies, innovation and creativity, and sustainable

³ <https://www.bluelab.gr>

solutions to the marine plastic waste challenges are proposed. As such, modern practices are adopted which operate with a view to protecting marine environment.

Effectively, in the aim to connect its key stakeholders (i.e. citizens with makers and authorities) PIR has created or endorsed the abovementioned two labs that offer to the public the opportunity to partner with experts while being directly engaged in the production process, of e.g. plastic waste into new usable objects. In this process, software systems have been engaged in the business process and are presented in the respective websites of blue/lab and blue/cycle. Both focus on marine debris recycling and the blue/lab (recently inaugurated) makes use, for instance, **specialised 3D printing design, 3D scanning and 3D printing technologies** that can be used by citizens and other interested members of the public under the supervision of a technical expert.

Figure 4. Key stakeholder types that are expected to be involved in the PIR project development

6.2.3 Stakeholders' identification

The key stakeholder types and user groups that are expected to interact or already interact for purposes relevant to the project in Piraeus are summarised in Figure 4. Based on a pool of available stakeholders that have been considered for engagement in PIR's potential industrial ecosystem on Pop-Machina, 5 distinct categories have been identified: business, capital, citizen, knowledge and government. Each category involves a few stakeholders that can actively interact in the local collaborative production symbiosis of the Municipality of Piraeus, for this specific project.

Cross-fertilising local collaborative production players, in our belief, can spin-off circular economies. More specifically, some of the potential interacting stakeholders are briefly analysed herewith.

6.2.3.1 Business Stakeholders Pool

- **Blue/lab innovation centre** (<https://www.bluelab.gr>) for blue (marine and ocean related) economic growth and sustainability (described in Section 6.2.2).
- **Blue Cycle | Beyond marine plastics waste** (<https://bluecycle.com/en/>) creating a new 'life cycle' for plastic fishing and shipping gear (described in Section 6.2.2).
- **Shedia/Diogenis NGO**: Diogenis NGO is an Athens-based Urban Non-Profit Company, established in early 2010 to support, through a wide range of activities, the efforts of the homeless and socially excluded people to join or re-integrate into the social web. The main actions of 'Diogenis NGO' are the publication of the street magazine 'Shedia' and the establishment of the national football team of the homeless with its annual participation in the World Cup of the Homeless. The

actions of the ‘raft’ are not limited to the distribution of a magazine, as a wide range of initiatives provides a network of protection for those in need.

6.2.3.2 II. Capital Stakeholders Pool

Bluegrowth Competition (<http://www.bluegrowth.gr/register/>)

The Bluegrowth aims to inspire and support start-ups with innovative ideas relating to the blue economy, including shipping, tourism, fisheries, and the marine ecosystem. The process is carried out through the big competition Bluegrowth, organised for the 4th year in a row, in which take part teams that have submitted their proposals. The selected ones join the ‘incubation’ programme of Bluegrowth, building a strong foundation to entry the ‘business world.’

Rewarding Packaging Recycling (<https://www.antapodotiki.gr/en>)

- Rewarding Recycling, in the context of enhancing the contributions to Society through reciprocal packaging recycling, has concluded a Cooperation Agreement with the ‘Holy Archdiocese of Athens’ and its Mission ‘Urban Non-profit Organisation’ (Charitable Organisation of the Holy Archdiocese of Athens) implementing the Integrated Programme for Actions in Rewarding Recycling and Environmental Protection entitled ‘Man and the Environment’.
- One of the Actions of the Integrated Programme is the ‘Collection of Social Capital from Packaging Recycling for the Financial Support of Actions of the Holy Archdiocese of Athens and of the mission ‘Apostoli’.
- Under this Action, Rewarding Recycling sets up and operates Integrated Rewarding Recycling Centres. Citizens who return empty metal, plastic and glass packaging to the Integrated Rewarding Recycling Centres (by pressing the corresponding button on the recycling machine and the use of the relevant ‘Social Capital Gathering Scheme’) have the option of donating the value of the compensation offered in order to strengthen social goals. Under the framework of this action, the total amount to be donated to the respective Integrated Rewarding Recycling Centres will support the actions of the mission ‘Apostoli’ and the Holy Archdiocese of Athens (such as its soup kitchens, etc).

Piraeus Chamber of Crafts : (<http://www.bep.gr/>)

The Company was founded on 19/06/2017 with a key partner in the Chamber of Crafts of Piraeus, pursuing a financial goal in the broad sense, with emphasis on educational and training purposes, development of activities that serve the national economy, management and implementation of all types of Community programmes and programmes and any other chamber purpose in general. Indicative purposes of the Company are:

- enhancing business;
- the organisation and creation of a Youth Entrepreneurship Club;
- organising and establishing a Women’s Entrepreneurship Development Academy;
- organising and creating an alternative form of modern ‘VIPClubBusinessSuccess’ networking;
- the enhancement of long-term vocational rehabilitation, especially for young people, women and young graduates;
- providing brokerage services and meeting the different needs of businesses by proposing appropriate certification;
- organising and conducting open seminars;
- implementation of training and empowerment/empowerment programmes (indicative courses, seminars, establishment of educational institutes, etc.);
- providing specialised consulting to businesses;

- the effort and support for the creation, participation, participation of one or more clusters, the management of actions to coordinate and support the development of such clusters, as well as the management and development and implementation of policies for their development.

Piraeus Traders Association (<https://espireas.gr/>)

The Piraeus Chamber of Commerce is one of the oldest trade associations in the country, according to its founding charter dated February 14, 1900. Its vision was focused on bringing together all the forces for greater efficiency and contribution to progress and from then until today. It struggles, gathers, organises and motivates people with anxieties and a passion for creation.

Purposes:

- (a) the protection of the professional interests of its members;
- (b) support and development of solidarity between its members and other members of the Greek merchant class;
- (c) the promotion of Piraeus Trade and the Greek trade in general and the trade profession, in combination with the general interests of the social community.

Piraeus Chamber of SM Industries

(<http://www.exporters-coaen.gr/member-chambers/chamber-of-sm-industries-piraeus>)

- The activities of the of the Piraeus Chamber of Small and Medium Sized Industries include: Issuing of certificates for any lawful use (tax office, banks, participation in competitions, etc.).
- Conducting expert appraisals for resolution of disputes.
- Providing opinions on draft laws, Presidential Decrees and decisions by the Central Administration which refer to small and medium sized industries, as well as suggesting and proposing amendments on laws and decisions already on the books.
- Monitoring the movement of the region’s small and medium sized industries with an eye on the viability of the businesses and their export activity.

Through the idea of ‘One Stop Shop’, facilitating, simplifying and speeding up the procedures for setting up and running a business by reducing barriers. Barriers which make entry into the business difficult. This is possible by saving time and money for the new entrepreneur and relieving public administration of significant administrative costs, by creating an online network of cooperation amongst many departments/services.

III. Citizens Pool:

Young members of the **‘Olympiacos’ basketball, volleyball and football girls and boys teams**, who are related closely with the action plans of PIR.

Scouts of Greece (<http://www.sep.org.gr/en/normal/home>)

- The Scout Movement is a voluntary non-political educational movement for young people open to all without distinction of gender, origin, race or creed, in accordance with the purpose, principles and method conceived by the Founder, Baden Powell.
- The Mission of Scouting is to contribute to the education of young people, through a value system based on the Scout Promise and Law, to help build a better world where people are self-fulfilled as individuals and play a constructive role in society. To achieve the Mission, the Scout Movement is counting on the voluntary and responsible contribution of adult trained Leaders.
- Soma Hellinon Proskopon – Scouts of Greece is governed by Legal Act 1066/1917. The Head Office is in Athens and it is an Institution governed by Private Law. It is a non-profit institution and is under the supervision of the Ministry of Education.

- Soma Hellinon Proskopon – Scouts of Greece (SHP) was founded in 1910 and is the only recognised Scout Movement in Greece. SHP is a founding member of the World Organisation of the Scout Movement that was established in 1920.

Association ‘ARGO’ of naval parents of children with special needs

(<https://www.argonauts.gr/en/>)

- The Association of Naval Parents of Children with Special Needs ‘ARGO’ is NPID recognised as specifically charitable and is overseen from the Ministry of Health and Social Solidarity.
- In the articles of the Association they function as the Centre of Daily Staying and care, the Specialised Centre of Professional Training and the Centre of Benefit of Accompanying Supporting Services in AmeA.
- It was founded in 1985 from an initiative of mothers of children with special needs that were spouses of seamen and can hold workshops as well as special sports events. It is managed by a 9 member administrative council, seven elected members (parents of children with special needs) and two named (representative of Pan-Hellenic Naval Federation and a representative of Naval Chamber Greece).
- The main aim of the Institution is the care and the education of children with special needs, primarily the children from families of Greek Seamen. In the Statute of Association provision is made that in case of empty places, children from non-seafaring families can be offered places.

6.2.3.3 Knowledge Stakeholder Pool:

Technical Group

Association of Hellenic Plastic Industries (<http://www.ahpi.gr/>)

Like most plastics industry associations across Europe, the AHPI aims to strengthen a positive image of plastics among the media, academia and politicians. The Greek association says it can ‘provide a fundamental contribution to the adaptation of an efficient circular economy in Greece.’ It will also communicate the benefits of plastics to consumers. The AHPI seeks to unify all Greek companies dealing with plastics, including raw materials producers and traders, converters as well as recyclers to tackle common problems. During his inauguration speech, Syrmos said, ‘In Greece unfortunately there is a poor waste-management system and we are really struggling to promote recycling to municipalities and consumers. We strongly believe that circular economy is a real opportunity for a country devastated by an ongoing financial crisis.’

(see, <https://www.plasteurope.com/news/detail.asp?id=241277>).

Association of the Greek Manufacturers of Packaging & Materials

(<https://www.pac.gr/?lang=en>)

- The Association of the Greek Manufacturers of Packaging & Materials was founded in 1999 by the leading packaging manufacturing enterprises in Greece. Members of the Association are companies producing packaging materials out of paper and carton, aluminium, tin, plastics, glass, wood and natural fibres.
- The 2007 changes in the statute of AGMPM extended its scope and allowed the expansion of its membership. Now, members of the Association can also be packaging machine manufacturers, companies providing services to the packaging industry (e.g. packaging designers, logistics services, packaging engineering and marketing services), and contract packers.
- AGMPM is member of the World Packaging Organisation (WPO).

Thrace Group: A world of materials and solutions (<https://www.thracegroup.com/gr/en/>)

- Creating new business standards through innovation and smart thinking, aiding our customers' leadership in their markets.
- Providing not just products but complete & innovative solutions, tailor-made upon our customers' specific requirements and needs.
- Acting local – being global, serving thousands of companies worldwide through strategic geographic dispersion.
- Pursuing profitability through organic growth and strategic acquisitions.
- Achieving competitive prices through economies of scale, vertical integration and internal synergies.
- Combining diverse high-end technologies with a long know-how and an extensive experience in the markets we operate.
- Respecting the global environment and the societies.
- Adapting to the ever-changing market environment and promptly adjusting our practices to successfully meet the global trends that will shape the future of business, economy and society.

Academic Group

University of West Attica, Department of Industrial Design and Production^{4,5}

It was established in 2018. It is the result of the merge of Piraeus University of Applied Sciences (TEI of Piraeus) and Athens University of Applied Sciences (TEI of Athens). The new University is the third biggest in Greece. The University is based on the long and successful tradition of the constituting institutes provides a high level undergraduate and postgraduate education combined with intensive research activities in specific areas. UNIWA reserves standing partnerships with other domestic and foreign educational and research institutes in order to continuously improve the level of the studies and research. UNIWA participates actively in several national and European Union programmes for international cooperation, research and dissemination of knowledge.

The University of West Attica maintains two campuses. Moreover, it offers 26 undergraduate and 40 postgraduate programmes in various fields of engineering, economy, health, arts and food technology. The graduates of the University following the tradition of the former PUAS and AUAS will serve successfully the industrial and services sectors of the Greek and international economy.

Topics of interest for the engagement in Pop-Machina: [Garment Engineering](#), [Materials Engineering](#), [Textile Engineering](#)

University of Piraeus, Department of Marine Studies⁶

The main educational objectives of the Department are:

- to offer modern theoretical knowledge and practical experience in maritime, transport and logistics;
- to approach and solve basic transport and maritime problems, by developing and extensive research and consultancy programme;
- to develop an international orientation, by establishing cooperation with other academic institutions and by utilising the international contacts which have been established by Greek maritime and transport companies all over the world.

Thanks to the collaboration of several companies, the programme combines theoretical courses with the opportunity for practical experience. Graduates who wish to expand their knowledge can follow one of the options of the post-graduate programme.

⁴ <https://westattica.esngreece.gr/university-west-attica>

⁵ <http://www.autex.org/members/university-west-attica-uniwa-school-engineering-department-industrial-design-and-production>

⁶ <https://www.unipi.gr/unipi/en/department-mar.html>

In addition, the Department of Maritime Studies co-operates on scientific projects with corresponding Departments of Universities in the European Union and in the United States and takes part in a number of research programmes, both at a national as well as at a Community level. Conceived as an utmost modern academic institution, the Department of Maritime Studies applies modern pedagogical methods based on the use of novel technology, and on the evolution of the ancient Greek method of education.

Piraeus Professional Lyceum for Special needs students (<http://tee-eavv-peiraia.att.sch.gr/>)

The Piraeus Professional Lyceum for Special needs students was founded with the Government Gazette 1856/2007. It operated for the first time in the school year 2012-2013 with 25 students and now 95 students. It serves students from the areas of: Salamina, Perama, Keratsini, Nikaia, Drapetsona, Korydallos, Piraeus.

Sectors and specialties:

- Computer-Computer Networks Sector specialising in ‘Computer Systems Support’;
- Department of Environmental Food Agriculture, specialising in ‘Plant Industrial Enterprises-Landscape Architecture’;
- Department of Electrical Engineering with a specialisation in ‘Electrical systems and way of installation in the Buildings’.

Government

Zea Marina S.A.

Zea Marina is located in Athens near the main port of Piraeus where it was firstly found as a war harbour with shipyards and other installations at the beginning of the 5th century B.C. before it was converted into a commercial port where millions of tourists start their travel to the Aegean coasts, the Saronic Gulf and the Island of Crete every year. Fully organised, offering facilities and services of high standards, the marina was totally renovated for the 2004 Olympic Games. The Marina has a berthing capacity of 670 yachts up to 120 m and 6 m draught. Within the marina shore area of 40,000 sq.m., 4,780 sq.m of building installations offer modern and high standard services, such as restaurants, refreshment bars, cafés and commercial shops. In the environs of the marina there are athletic installations and the Greek War Naval Museum.

Piraeus Port Authority S.A

Piraeus Port connects continental Greece with the islands, is an international cruise centre and a commercial hub for the Mediterranean, providing services to ships of any type and size. P.P.A. is developing into a modern and dynamic company that provides high quality services, keeps investors satisfied, ensures long-term employment and serves commercial transactions in Greece in favour of the national economy and the consumers in the most efficient way and within the context of the global port industry. The Piraeus Port Authority SA (PPA SA) provides high quality, efficient and safe port services and contributes to local and national economy by achieving sustainable growth. It provides the link between the Greek islands and the mainland and with its ongoing investment plan aims to be established as the most important HUB, Logistics, Cruise, Container and RoRo centre in the East Mediterranean.

Today P.P.A. S.A. employs more than 1.000 people and annually provides services to more than 24,000 ships. P.P.A. S.A contributes towards the local and national economic growth and is further developed by upgrading both the infrastructure and the services provided.

Attica Region

Attica Region is an administrative region of Greece, that encompasses the entire metropolitan area of Athens, including Piraeus.

KODEP – Piraeus Municipal Social Enterprise⁷

The Public Benefit Municipal Social Enterprise of Piraeus (K.O.D.E.P.) is a Legal Entity under Private Law. KODEP is subsidised for specific actions, which aim at the organisation of functions or activities related to the responsibilities of the Municipality of Piraeus that have been assigned to KODEP based on specific agreement.

The purpose of KODEP is to take care of all the social problems of the Citizens, regardless of age. Among other things, the care for food, nutrition, clothing for the poor and homeless citizens, the care for informing the public on health and prevention issues, as well as the general implementation of policies and actions aimed at caring for and supporting vulnerable social groups.

Its headquarters are in Piraeus, 11 Zosimadon Street, as well as its various facilities where its activities are served.

Piraeus stakeholders are summarised in the following table.

⁷ <http://www.kodep.gr/>

Table 8. Stakeholders identified in the city of Piraeus

Name of stakeholder	Localisation (City)	Stakeholder in circular economy (yes or no)	Stakeholder in Maker Movement
<p>Business: Local NGOs & Makers. Makers & maker communities, FabLabs, individual makers, DIY communities</p> <p>Blue Lab</p> <p>Shedia DIOGENIS NGO</p> <p>Blue Cycle</p>	<p>Piraeus</p> <p>Athens</p> <p>Piraeus</p>	<p></p> <p>X</p> <p></p>	<p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p>
<p>Capital: Local Enterprises. SMES, Start – ups, circular entrepreneurs & investors, raw material suppliers, waste management companies</p> <p>Blue Growth Competition</p> <p>Rewarding Recycling S.A.</p> <p>Piraeus Chamber of Crafts</p> <p>Piraeus Traders Association</p> <p>Piraeus Chamber of SM Industries</p> <p>CEA Computer Express Aid https://www.cca.gr/</p>	<p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p>	<p></p> <p>X</p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p>	<p>X</p> <p></p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p>
<p>Citizen: Customers, end-users, trusted individuals</p> <p>Argo Institute (for disabled kids)</p> <p>Professional High School for disabled students</p> <p>Young Artists</p> <p>Scouts of Greece</p> <p>Look at the stars http://looktothestars.gr</p> <p>Ma...Zei http://www.mazei.gr</p>	<p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p>	<p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p>	<p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p>
<p>Knowledge: Technical & Technological Expertise, Academic research Community</p> <p>University of West Attica</p> <p>University of Piraeus</p> <p>University Academy of Fine Arts</p> <p>Piraeus Professional Lyceum for Special needs students</p> <p>Association of Hellenic Plastic Industries</p> <p>Thrace Group</p> <p>Association of the Greek Manufacturers of Packaging & Materials</p> <p>Plastikourgeio S.A.</p>	<p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Athens</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Athens</p>	<p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p></p>	<p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p>X</p>
<p>Government: Local Authorities. City, regional and national authorities (municipalities)</p> <p>Zea Marina S.A.</p> <p>Piraeus Port Authority S.A.</p> <p>Attica Region</p> <p>KODEP – Piraeus Municipal Social Enterprise</p>	<p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p> <p>Piraeus</p>	<p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p> <p>X</p>	<p></p> <p></p> <p></p> <p>X</p>

6.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

In every bottom-up social innovation initiative, it is expected to face numerous challenging conditions. These mainly arise from the lack of appropriate policy to empower local engagement more actively and from lack of local awareness as well as technical expertise or finances. The Municipality of Piraeus has aimed to face all these challenges by making all its maker community projects available for free to the public. This is based on its 4P mission, and, thus, is also advertised widely as such. Notwithstanding the abovementioned, there are still various challenges to be tackled. Thus, a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) analysis has been performed, the results of which are summarised as follows.

<p>STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong civil society - High level of knowhow in the plastics industry - Two existing maker communities as well as existing business and knowledge know-how - Relatively engaged population/as in need of new job opportunities - Long history of cooperation (between NGOs, SMEs, communities, administration) - The collaboration with the University of Macedonia which made it possible to identify FabLabs in Athens as well as OK!Thess in Thessaloniki who have expressed interest to cooperate - KODEP's experience and contribution in engaging and motivating local focus groups – especially the ones of unprivileged communities and people with special needs - Spinning off circular economies based in the engagement of the appropriate focus groups – maker communities - Developing new environmentally and socio-economically sustainable products that can form the product of training and an overarching Fab Academy activity 	<p>WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Makerspaces and FabLabs are not widely known in Greece and in the area - Community is not aware of the benefits of engaging in new innovative maker movements - There is no space in Piraeus that is ready for use so extra care must be taken on this - There is not enough knowledge on the benefits of engaging the maker movement - There is not enough evidence on the financial benefit of one engaging in the maker community due to the fact that it is effectively a bottom-up type of activity - There are a few success stories that however are not widely known and therefore one should consider that the Piraeus community is unaware of the benefits of their participation solely or in groups in the maker movement
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation options with industry - High potential for waste management in a wider Municipal level where we can offer useful products that can cross-fertilise the need for new jobs and the need for sustainability - Existing maker communities are looking for future perspectives so some of them might be willing to collaborate - Motivate and Engage exciting maker networks and initiatives in a city level, e.g. social groups/enterprises, etc. - Existing FabLabs in Athens that can engage in future activities in Piraeus - To engage a variety of stakeholders in developing a very strong collaborative team producing new materials for community use - Capitalise existing knowledge and experience from local labs and networks 	<p>THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conflicts of interest in the use of recycled materials - Changes in policy (restrictions) - Focus only on the city centre or the sea/shore and not in wider areas of Piraeus - Lack of engagement due to lack of awareness - Lack of necessary technological awareness in using new machinery and technological advancements to produce useful outputs - Lack of one-size-fits all solution to pressing challenges in the societal decision-making

Pop-Machina can increase engagement in the PIR projects and can also increase PIR's connection with other national municipal projects, such as that of the Municipality of Thessaloniki. It can also increase awareness of citizens and local or regional stakeholders in the benefits of blue growth and waste treatment in spinning-off locally circular economies. This can be achieved through engagement with the media, workshops, newspaper and academic articles, posters and more methods that rely on social innovation awareness – engagement – adoption and diffusion techniques⁸ (Figure 5).

⁸ https://www.h-brs.de/files/erklaerung_soziale_innovationen_fuerd_2_0.pdf

Figure 5. Social innovation for Germany

6.3 TO-BE scenario

6.3.1 Overview

Based on a study on social innovation techniques to trigger engagement in renewable energy projects (conducted by INSEAD, France, for the EU ISABEL project),⁹ PIR aims to adopt some simple awareness and acceptance-raising techniques as its new business process in adding stakeholders and interest in its maker movements and its mission to locally spin-off circular economies.

Attracting interest and engagement in PIR's projects require information dissemination. This effectively relates with a series of triggers that will have a socio-economic and environmental impact. These are based on (i) communicating the innovation characteristics, through examples of 'role models', waste management 'champions' and (ii) presenting the innovation benefits (e.g. lasting financial incentives). This can lead to the development of social entrepreneurship illustrating a clear direction towards the project goals. The following diagram illustrates the method in which PIR conceptualises its innovation process in attracting and engaging stakeholders in its projects. This effectively requires the achievement of a social impact. This is based on, (i) offering prompts (e.g. information, triggers, inspiration), (ii) disseminating useful information in order to raise awareness, trust and attract social engagement, and (iii) managing resources, technical infrastructure and capabilities. This can then lead to the adoption and initiation of the first projects tests and trials. Successful tests and trials as well as coordination can attract funds (i.e. capital) to the given social/ sustainability venture.

⁹ <https://isabel-project.eu>

6.3.2 Business requirements

Table 9. Business requirements of the city of Piraeus

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Lack of previous applied knowledge and detailed information on how to support and promote maker initiatives and their ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices analysis - Access to scientific resources - Organising and offering online and offline synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers - Communication of impact of circular and maker initiatives - Engagement of special communities and trusted individuals and or organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Low levels of social engagement, provision of information, awareness and trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices analysis - Access to scientific resources - Communication of impact of circular and maker initiatives - Engagement of special communities and trusted individuals and or organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Lack of evidence of benefits of the Pop-Machina project implementation, presenting successful credible 'role models'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication of benefits of circular and maker initiatives - Connection and information exchange with experts and other successful role models across the world - Learning and cross-fertilising knowledge - Wide dissemination of success stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Lack of maturity in collaborative production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More interactive communication with city authorities - Engagement of special communities and trusted individuals and or organisations - Provision of useful know-how and successful 'role models' (success stories) to be used as guidance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Lack of state of formal relations, social entrepreneurship engaging citizens as well as communities & local government cooperatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation of 'role models' - Overcoming barriers - Creating social responsibility and corporate social responsibility - Increase of dissemination to attract the policy maker - Following Piraeus mission to connect Public – Private - People – Partnerships (4P) for the creation of 'smart infrastructure' and mitigating local pressing needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Lack of managing resources (technological knowledge, prototyping, testing) in the maker context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical support, prototyping and affiliation in the maker community - Educating local communities to innovate (e.g. through engagement in 3D-printing by using plastics as a main resource) - Developing methods to mitigate local increasing pollution levels in shore areas of Piraeus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Makers - Makerspaces administrators - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises

Table 9. Business requirements of the city of Piraeus (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Lack of venture financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attracting investors (e.g. private funds, crowdfunding, etc.) and public funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Lack of support for the commercialisation of maker products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation of ‘role models’ - Overcoming technical barriers - Organising and offering online and offline synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers - Developing smart contracts for trading and circularity - Engaging in existing supply chains - Connecting technological experts with local makers and local enterprises and or investors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises
Decentralised and fragmented maker initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating a network of makers - Increasing social collaboration engagement - Developing industrial ecosystems of makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens and residents - Managers of resources/materials - Social cooperatives - Local enterprises

6.4 Use cases

6.4.1 Overview

The goal of the Municipality of Piraeus through Pop-Machina is to turn into a locally, productive, globally connected city. Piraeus wants to engage 4 Ps: Public – Private – People – Partnerships. A ‘community engagement plan’ is designed for promoting urban sustainable development by empowering the local maker community to participate in the Global Fab initiative and for prototyping and producing urban infrastructures useful for the city and its local circular economy.

Pop-Machina can increase awareness of citizens and local or regional stakeholders in the benefits of blue growth and waste treatment in spinning-off locally circular economies.

This can be achieved through engagement with the media, workshops, newspaper and academic articles, posters and more methods that rely on social innovation awareness – engagement - adoption and diffusion techniques.

So, a holistic plan is designed which includes the makerspace in the framework of Pop-Machina and the conjunction of it with the existing Blue Lab. It will be established a common space for these two labs (makerspace and blue lab), so that makers, citizens, stakeholders will have an active home for the development of the circular economy in the city of Piraeus, in the future.

The plan for the municipality of Piraeus consists of:

- creation of new products useful for our city such as: Waste bins from recycled material, benches, flower pots, flower beds, Equipment for the beach and the port, Furniture from plastic/metal scrap, lightening equipment;
- increasing inclusiveness of people with special needs through recycling and re-use activities;
- engagement of vulnerable people;
- conjunction with existing FabLabs in Athens and Piraeus;

- creation of a network between citizens, industry, social entrepreneurs;
- engagement of schools/institutes in our activities and combine recycling and renewable energy resources with the blue economy;
- total reuse activities and exchange of products, materials, ideas for producing new things;
- making products for urban development and being an example of circular economy for all the citizens.

This is the way of establishing the idea of making and circular economy in the city of Piraeus.

6.4.2 Piraeus pilot use cases

Some real examples of making pushed Piraeus to get seriously involved in the Pop-Machina project. The following pilot use cases emerged as a result of meetings, the first Pop-Machina workshop and extended research among the citizens of Piraeus and the existing FabLabs. These use cases depict the implementation of the plan of creating our makerspace and its function through the framework of producing products from citizens/makers for achieving an urban development and creating infrastructures for Piraeus Municipality.

6.4.2.1 Use case 1: Engagement of vulnerable people – children with special needs

Rodamanthi is a Philologist-Special Educator and **Evita** is a psychologist. They work both in ‘Argo’ which is an association of naval parents of children with special needs. The main aim of the Institution is the care and the education of children with special needs, primarily the children from families of Greek Seamen. In the Statute of Association provision is made that in case of empty places, children from non-seafaring families can be offered places.

‘Argo’ has been active in the field of Special Education and Training for 33 years. It mainly hosts and educates adult students with mental retardation and autism.

Rodamanthi, besides education, deals with wood constructions. Specifically, in the department of the Wooden Certified Laboratory (equipped with appropriate machines) Rodamanthi trains the beneficiaries in cutting and processing wood, while at the same time apply various micro-technical techniques. The raw materials are mostly wood or materials for recycling or reuse.

Thus, Rodamanthi would like to use Piraeus makerspace to benefit the facilities and the available tools and machinery. The first step is to get involved in Pop-Machina project. She has to login in a platform as a maker for wooden constructions. Then, she fixes the timeline and the machinery needed for her constructions. She has no knowledge of 3D printing. So she is interested in learning. She asks help from Piraeus maker champions so as to 3D design her potential construction.

Finally, Rodamanthi uploads her design in Pop-Machina platform, so everybody can see it. This action can be combined with the exchange of tokens. Rodamanthi receives tokens for her design and gives tokens for e-learning of 3D printing.

Evita has been working for ten years as a psychologist at the handicraft centre of Argo. This section engages learners with constructions and handmade creations. Evita and her students collect fabrics, old jeans, old clothes, beads, buttons and ribbons. They took a sewing machine and started processing and sewing. Old jeans, for example, have become aprons for Argo’s cooking department and women’s handbags. They process, reuse, recycle worn-out, useless items as raw material and not as waste, creating ecological awareness in the students through circular management.

Evita wants to use the makerspace of Piraeus for creating new prototype products with modern equipment. She has no knowledge of 3D printing and digital design, but she knows very well the usage of sewing machines.

Evita wants to explore in a more fabric way in the makerspace the reuse of old clothes so as to create things for the citizens of Piraeus.

Evita uploads her designs in Pop-Machina platform, so everybody can see it and receives tokens for her design and gives tokens for e-learning of 3D printing, too.

Evita and Rodamanthi could earn more tokens organising workshops for people with special needs and upload them in the platform.

They could also find their raw materials/recyclable wastes exchanging some of their tokens in Piraeus makerspace.

6.4.2.2 Use case 2: Education/training

Iason and Marilena are architects. They are members in the team of Fab-Lab Athens. They have a wide knowledge for the function of a FabLab and for prototyping. They want to get fully involved with making. But they have the problem of the absence of a fully equipped makerspace in Athens and in Piraeus, where they can realise their ideas.

They get informed about the Pop-Machina project and they make themselves available to organise workshops and projects for Piraeus makerspace.

They receive tokens from Pop-Machina platform to organise online workshops. They could earn more tokens for creating digitally prototype products and upload them to the platform.

Finally, they could exchange some of their tokens, to take from the platform designs, updates of software, webinars, etc.

Marilena, Iason, Rodamanthi and Evita in close cooperation with Municipality of Piraeus should organise educational programmes for everybody dealing with making using the equipment of makerspace.

These four persons should be characterised as Pop-Machina network helpers and awarded with tokens related to their experience, in educating in sewing machines, 3D printers, creations of wood, prototyping.

6.4.2.3 Use case 3: Engagement of Industry/Cooperation between makers and social enterprises

Marilena and Iason have some ideas for prototype products for use in the urban system of Piraeus. Municipality of Piraeus organise an event for promoting products from makers to local industry and SMEs. In this event, makers, industry, chambers participate.

Marilena and Iason present their products. Representatives of a local industry get informed about the product and come to an agreement with them for producing their products.

The company becomes a member of the Pop-Machina platform earning tokens for the production of a product fully designed in Piraeus makerspace and exchanging tokens for the acquisition of the design of the product.

Marilena and Iason also earn tokens for uploading the design for the new product to the platform.

6.4.2.4 Use case 4: Making new business teams

Rodamanthi has an idea for new wooden benches that they could be installed in the beach of Piraeus.

Iason has a wide knowledge of using 3d printers and laser cutter in the makerspace of Piraeus.

After getting to know each other, they create a social enterprise and design the new wooden benches.

Then, in cooperation with recyclers, they take their raw material and produce their product. This social enterprise should be acknowledged as new business and awarded with tokens for its creativity.

6.5 User requirements

Table 10. User requirements of the city of Piraeus

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URP1	Local authority	connect with local recycling industry	acquire knowhow and collaboration
URP2	Local authority and local enterprise	connect with local universities that offer technical knowledge on converting waste into fibres	engage into the production of future products
URP3	Local governmental authorities	create a map of the location of waste resources	target waste management centres
URP4	Local governmental authorities	bring members of the society together	explore the method to engage them in collaborative production
URP5	Local governmental authorities	find a way to combine the work of different stakeholders of Piraeus	produce more powerful and smart materials/products that will increase sustainability and decrease the local governmental cost expenditure
URP6	Local governmental authorities	get involved in the maker movement as part of the maker city action plan	produce useful products for the urban realm of Piraeus
URP7	Local governmental authorities	develop a new local waste management system or empower existing ones	create a closed loop waste management plan locally
URP8	Local governmental authorities	identify interesting propositions for ongoing public needs	find partners for works of the Municipality/region, etc.
URP9	Local governmental authorities	promote makers movement in legislation of recycling waste and of programmes of fining jobs	we can create motives for being a maker
URP10	Local governmental authorities	create a legal framework in a simplified way for the function of makerspaces	new makerspaces may be created
URP11	Local governmental authorities	inspire makers to collaborate	find new projects and address new challenges locally, make circular economy enterprises, have a wider framework of producing products for their region
URP12	Local authorities	connect with experts to offer knowledge and support	local communities and other stakeholders can engage in circular community movement
URP13	Local authorities	combine the separate collection of paper, plastic, glass, wood, etc. with the creation of products in makerspace	circular economy be implemented in action by creating new products of waste material
URP14	Local authorities	push vulnerable and unemployed citizens to work in a makerspace	reduce unemployment and create job for the vulnerable citizens
URP15	Local governmental authorities	I want to save public budget through sustainable use of waste	to promote sustainable development and the use of moneys for urgent needs
URP16	Makers	connect with local authorities to empower higher engagement	address challenges and produce useful products
URP17	Makers	overcome barriers and showcase the public benefit in engaging makerspaces	finding partners for works of the Municipality/region, etc.

Table 10. User requirements of the city of Piraeus (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URP18	Makers	inspire citizens to collaborate in making new products from waste materials	create a hands-on and DIY experience on making
URP19	Makers	find out how the accurate budget to establish a makerspace	create a secondary spin-off technology for the Municipality and its activities
URP20	Makers	find partners who contribute in the educational content	engage with new infrastructures and expertise
URP21	Makers	connect with experts to offer knowledge and support	local communities and other stakeholders can engage in circular community movement
URP22	Makers	learn new technologies	I can enter a new market
URP23	Makers	search for secondary raw materials by type	contribute in a supply chain in a circular method upcycling or reusing materials
URP24	Makers	develop my skills related with new technologies (3D printing, CNC cutting, etc.)	create new more evolving objects by waste materials, useful for the urban realm
URP25	Makers	find other people with common interests	create new more evolving objects by waste materials, useful for the urban realm
URP26	Makers	be educated from experts of recycling	produce products for my region of recycling material
URP27	Citizen	each neighbourhood to be able to face its own challenges locally	increase efficiency, save time and offer new jobs to the ones in need
URP28	Citizen	find out how to make a maker business	enter a new market and learn its specificities
URP29	Citizens and residents	know if the Municipality of Piraeus can endorse my interest	to feel safe in my new maker movement
URP30	Citizens and residents	innovate	create new local businesses on waste management
URP31	Citizens and residents	see what circular products are available	to buy them, develop them and earn how to sell them
URP32	Citizens and residents	participate in a producing new materials using recycled waste	develop knowhow to build pavilions for the city and more
URP33	Citizens and residents	watch training programmes/seminars	in order to collaborate with more people and produce useful waste based products
URP34	Citizens and residents	identify methods to engage with stakeholders in the value chain	create new local markets
URP35	Citizens and residents	identify appropriate spaces where we can be trained to use makerspaces and their devices	be able to produce new materials and products by ourselves
URP36	Citizens and residents	learn how to kick off a makerspace	to become aware of the stages of a makerspace development

7. City of Santander

7.1 Introduction

The city of Santander is the capital of Cantabria region which is located in the north coast of Spain (see Figure 6). It has ca. 172,000 inhabitants and occupies a land area close to 35 km². The weight of the city within the region is very important, considering that the total region population is ca. 580,000 inhabitants; therefore, it concentrates 30% of the population.

Figure 6. Location of the city of Santander

Although Santander, like other comparable cities, regularly carries out innovation activities in different areas, in 2010 there was a significant change when adopting the Smart City paradigm as a focus for the future development of the city.

As a result, the city has thousands of IoT devices deployed throughout the city that have allowed the development of services and applications that have been integrated in the daily life of the citizen. Thanks to this project, Santander has become an urban laboratory where new technologies and solutions can be installed and tested in a real environment and with real users.

This action was part of the plan of Santander described in Santander Strategic Plan 2010-2020 which led to the Innovation Director Plan in which ‘Santander Smart City’ and ‘Santander open innovation’ joined to the more classical ‘Public body modernisation’ were the key points for focusing the activities.

As a result of this strategy, a series of activities have been developed that make up Santander City Council’s innovation cycle (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Santander innovation strategy summary

Santander City Council has participated in different R&D projects with energy efficient and sustainability as a fundamental component of the activities.

The city is currently working on the regeneration of a neighbourhood of the city that includes a living lab. The idea is that by dedicating a part of the spaces planned for this purpose could have a very important synergistic effect for the neighbourhood and for the city. We would therefore have a part dedicated to social space infrastructure (including IT).

7.2 Current situation

7.2.1 Overview

As it has been already introduced, Santander has a long record of innovation activities focused on the Smart City paradigm. In this regard, some of them are connected to the circular economy model as well as to environment sustainability objectives. Apart from the different verticals that have been addressed in different projects (i.e. from smart mobility, to smart waste management or smart energy), there is a common, horizontal, basis for all of them that relates to the management of data coming from the technological infrastructure, based on the IoT concept, that is deployed throughout the city.

On the maker community aspect, there is one active FabLab in Santander with some tens of affiliates. While the FabLab is a completely private association, it has been supported by some public initiatives promoted from the Santander Municipality.

7.2.2 Current business process models

In general, Santander economic activity is mainly linked to the tertiary sector, where tourism and ICT are the main areas of business development. In this sense, more than 70% of the active population works in the tertiary sector, which means that economic dependence, on trade and services, is very high in Santander, especially in seasonal sectors linked to tourism, such as hotels and restaurants.

Pertaining to the Pop-Machina project, building on the previous experiences in the research and innovation projects in which the city has been involved, the innovation department from the municipality will be the catalyser of the activities and issues raised during the project. They are responsible for the bidirectional flow of information. On the one hand, they carry out the tasks of

contacting the relevant agents within the municipality (and sometimes also other local stakeholders) and engaging them in the respective actions carried out by the project. On the other hand, they are also responsible for gathering the specific requirements for each of the vertical actions, in which innovative initiatives are being put forward.

Apart from the innovation initiatives promoted by the innovation department, which follow a top-down approach, this is, they address necessities identified by the respective municipality departments (e.g. mobility responsible, environment manager, etc.), Santander municipality has a tool to get bottom-up initiatives coming directly from citizens.

This tool is called Santander City Brain (<https://www.santandercitybrain.com/>). It is an open, transparent and free online platform of ideas for enhancing Santander. It is open to individuals anyone who, being citizens or not of the city of Santander, want to share their ideas and projects, comment and vote on the ideas and projects shared by others users, in order to collaborate in the development of Santander as a Smart city and in the execution of the city's Strategic Plan. The objective is to get proposals to improve the city of Santander in any aspect: administration, government, economy, mobility, buildings, public spaces and contribute to the execution of the Strategic Plan, involving the inhabitants themselves with this open space to receive their ideas and projects. In addition to a continuously open call for proposals, sporadically special challenges are organised in the Santander City Brain platform. In these challenges, citizens are asked to provide their proposals in a pre-defined topic. The idea is to exploit the 'wisdom of crowds' concept and eventually get game-changing innovations to be developed.

Another interesting innovation initiative, supported by the University of Cantabria, is an annual hackathon (<http://www.hack2progress.com/>) which is organised by the University and a local ICT company. Every year the initiative is themed on a different topic linked with sustainable development. For example, this year's edition was founded on the objectives set by UN in its 2030 Agenda.

Concerning the makers community, there are mainly three initiatives. The first one is the FabLab Santander (<http://www.FabLabsantander.org/>). This is a privately run FabLab who has been running in the city for several years already. They have a well-organised workshop with typical FabLab equipment. They regularly organise workshops and training activities not only with their registered members but also inviting other people for enlarging their already established community. The second and third initiatives are two Meetup events: Makers Santander (<https://www.meetup.com/es-ES/Makers-Santander/>) and Maker InvenLab (<https://www.meetup.com/es-ES/Meetup-Maker-InvenLab/>). These communities organise events related with the maker movement in which they share their latest projects or invite experts to give short presentations and workshops on their area of expertise.

7.2.3 Stakeholders' identification

A preliminary identification of the potential and relevant stakeholders regarding Santander pilot case is included in the table below:

Table 11. Stakeholders identified in the city of Santander

Stakeholders categories	Short description	Identified to be engaged in the Santander pilot
Government	Local/regional authorities responsible for policy making, planning and implementation of plans/regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Santander Municipal Environment Service - MARE (environment, water, waste and energy, Regional Government of Cantabria)
Public-Private initiatives	Partnerships/initiatives of companies, knowledge institutions and government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CISE (Santander International Entrepreneurship Centre) - ADL (Local Development Agency) - Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, and Shipping of Cantabria
Higher education/universities	Academia; Researchers involved in circular economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University of Cantabria Department of Chemistry and Process & Resource Engineering - EcoCampus University of Cantabria - EIT Climate KIC Cantabria
FabLabs & related business		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FabLab Santander - Inven.es
Waste management organisations	Local/regional waste management authorities and/or contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ascan-Geaser: supplier to the City Council in charge of urban waste management
NGOs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AMICA - SEO-BIRds - Language of the Sea initiative - Botin Centre cultural organisation
Entrepreneurs/citizens		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizens - Consumer associations - Neighbourhood associations

7.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

The objectives that are envisaged for the Santander Pilot are:

- promote circular activities that reduce the overall environmental footprint of the city;
- help boosting the incipient maker community in Santander;
- encourage the creation of innovative manufacturing and making activity, specially focusing on those with a circular economy approach;
- develop synergies between maker initiatives and the general Smart Santander strategy;
- promote activities aimed at closing the technological gap on groups of population which might be on risk of exclusion. Special interest would be devoted to elderly people due to the ageing of Santander population;
- align the initiatives to be developed in innovation projects with any of the objectives set into the UN SDG 2030 Agenda.

Based on these objectives, in the table below we describe the challenges of Santander in the context of Pop-Machina and the potential of the project to address them.

Challenge	Pop-Machina potential
Access to information about initiatives related to circular economy in the city	To gather in a single point information about circular initiatives including details such as the location, schedule, target and ways of contributing
Contribute to the raising of awareness/interest in the different aspects of circularity of goods and resources	To leverage circular initiatives and demonstrate how sustainable cultures and behaviours can generate environmental, social and economic benefits
Quantify the impact of the initiatives/campaigns put forward for promoting circular behaviours	To gather the respective KPIs identified for each initiative put forward during the pilot and to set the tools that help the different stakeholders involved in the analysis of them
Access to a system for local trading of secondary raw materials and circular goods	To develop a trading system on which experiment on novel business models
Unclear legal and regulatory framework in the areas of circular economy and collaborative production	To identify the framework conditions of those operations and make demand driven suggestions for streamlining and improvement; to use data-driven intelligence on how these conditions could be improved; to fuel the policy debate on how these conditions could be improved
Create a dedicated space which could be the physical hub for circular activities in the city	To finance the adaptation of an under-utilised municipal building for concentrating circular-oriented initiatives
Lack of resources (in terms of municipal initiatives) for boosting maker activities focused on circular economy	To organise events and initiatives leveraging the existing maker community and engaging them in circular behaviours
Scattered initiatives and individuals with different grades of relation with the circular economy and makers movement that could find synergies among them	To gather various stakeholders under the umbrella of the project and enable the cross-fertilisation among the newly created community
General absence of manufacturing and making commercial activities that could be the basis for the creation of high added value jobs and for strengthening the image of Santander as city of culture, sciences and arts	To be the basis for experimental innovation projects and to help advanced users through training and acceleration of new business models around the circular making concept
Link the multiple innovation actions in Santander with the Smart City Platform that is deployed in the city	To gather new sources of information pertaining to circular economy and maker activities that can fuel the capacity of the city to be aware of what is happening at the city at every moment
Progressively ageing of Santander's population	To organise initiatives where elderly people could be engaged, thus generating non-negligible social benefits such as counteraction of loneliness

7.3 TO-BE scenario

7.3.1 Overview

The Santander Pilot will be initially focused on two circular economy concepts:

- Circular FabLab: the site will be arranged as a FabLab where different stakeholders will be invited. However, the projects and initiatives to be fostered will have a common denominator, the circular economy movement. In this sense, initiatives like Urban Resource Centre (focused on plastics) will be promoted, gathering secondary raw materials and leveraging a circular economy between the stakeholders that join the Circular FabLab (producers and gatherers of the materials, project developers, FabLab experts, community developers, business accelerators, local communities with necessities, etc.). This way, the pilot will be a pole of attraction where demand and offer (at a local and circular level) will join so that circular projects can be triggered;
- Repair Café: getting benefit of the workshop area of the pilot, regular Repair Cafes will be arranged. The idea is to exploit as much as possible the infrastructure and also getting people into the pilot with initiatives which are not so technological. This way, the entry barrier that could exist would be

lowered. This Repair Cafes, organised on different themes (e.g. bicycle repair, clothing, small electric appliances repairing, etc.) would be ideal ‘excuses’ to bring more people into the Circular FabLab loop.

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- supply and demand of products and services connection;
- tracking and trading of materials, resources (e.g. time, designs, usage of equipment, reservations of spaces and/or machines, projects, etc.) based on a system of virtual credits;
- networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services;
- organising and offering technical, business and legal training and support sessions for makers;
- e-library to access relevant documentation on technical, business or legal matters related with circular making;
- inventory of local circular actors (including profile, shared resources, availability, position in the leadership board);
- connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform;
- community applications/forums;
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives;
- announcements – notifications of the material flows (which ones are available and which ones are requested), maintenance of a leadership board to identify top contributors (for gamification purposes), and dissemination of special events (such as Hackathons or recollection campaigns) bound to special projects.

7.3.2 Business requirements

Table 12. Business requirements of the city of Santander

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Access to information about initiatives related to circular economy in the city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Inventory of local circular actors (including profile, shared resources, availability, position in the leadership board) - Connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform - Community applications/forums - Announcements – notifications of the material flows, maintenance of a leadership board to identify top contributors, dissemination of special events bound to special projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Public-Private initiatives - FabLabs - NGOs - Entrepreneurs/citizens
Contribute to the raising of awareness/interest in the different aspects of circularity of goods and resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inventory of local circular actors (including profile, shared resources, availability, position in the leadership board) - Connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives - Announcements – notifications of the material flows, maintenance of a leadership board to identify top contributors, dissemination of special events bound to special projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Public-Private initiatives - FabLabs - Universities - NGOs

Table 12. Business requirements of the city of Santander (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Quantify the impact of the initiatives/campaigns put forward for promoting circular behaviours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives - Announcements – notifications of the material flows, maintenance of a leadership board to identify top contributors, dissemination of special events bound to special projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Public-Private initiatives - FabLabs - Universities
Access to a system for local trading of secondary raw materials and circular goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supply and demand of products and services connection - Tracking and trading of materials, resources (e.g. time, designs, usage of equipment, reservations of spaces and/or machines, projects, etc.) based on a system of virtual credits - Connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - FabLabs - Universities - Waste management organisations - Entrepreneurs/citizens
Unclear legal and regulatory framework in the areas of circular economy and collaborative production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organising and offering technical, business and legal training and support sessions for makers - E-library to access relevant documentation on technical, business or legal matters related with circular making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - FabLabs - Universities
Create a dedicated space which could be the physical hub for circular activities in the city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supply and demand of products and services connection - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Organising and offering technical, business and legal training and support sessions for makers - Community applications/forums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - FabLabs - Entrepreneurs/citizens
Lack of resources (in terms of municipal initiatives) for boosting maker activities focused on circular economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tracking and trading of materials, resources (e.g. time, designs, usage of equipment, reservations of spaces and/or machines, projects, etc.) based on a system of virtual credits - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Organising and offering technical, business and legal training and support sessions for makers - Connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform - Community applications/forums - Announcements – notifications of the material flows, maintenance of a leadership board to identify top contributors, dissemination of special events bound to special projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Public-Private initiatives

Table 12. Business requirements of the city of Santander (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Scattered initiatives and individuals with different grades of relation with the circular economy and makers movement that could find synergies among them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tracking and trading of materials, resources (e.g. time, designs, usage of equipment, reservations of spaces and/or machines, projects, etc.) based on a system of virtual credits - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - E-library to access relevant documentation on technical, business or legal matters related with circular making - Inventory of local circular actors (including profile, shared resources, availability, position in the leadership board) - Community applications/forums - Announcements – notifications of the material flows, maintenance of a leadership board to identify top contributors, dissemination of special events bound to special projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Public-Private initiatives - FabLabs - Universities - Entrepreneurs/citizens
General absence of manufacturing and making commercial activities that could be the basis for the creation of high added value jobs and for strengthening the image of Santander as city of culture, sciences and arts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supply and demand of products and services connection - Tracking and trading of materials, resources (e.g. time, designs, usage of equipment, reservations of spaces and/or machines, projects, etc.) based on a system of virtual credits - Networking and matchmaking of circular entrepreneurs and citizens requiring products or services - Organising and offering technical, business and legal training and support sessions for makers - Connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Public-Private initiatives - Entrepreneurs/citizens
Link the multiple innovation actions in Santander with the Smart City Platform that is deployed in the city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connection of circular flows to the Santander smart city platform - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - Universities
Progressively ageing of Santander's population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organising and offering technical, business and legal training and support sessions for makers - Community applications/forums - Announcements –dissemination of special events (such as Hackathons or recollection campaigns) bound to special projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government - NGOs - Entrepreneurs/citizens

7.4 Use cases

The following use cases have been created to be used as examples of how the aforementioned business process would come to practice in typical situations of the Santander Pop-Machina pilot. Thus, they are generically described in order to be used for the extraction of requirements. Different use cases are proposed for the two aforementioned general initiatives (i.e. Circular FabLab and Repair Café).

7.4.1 The Circular-Economy Makerspace

These use cases intend to promote the circular economy and the maker movement through one open space in the city of Santander called ‘The Circular-Economy Makerspace’ or ‘CEMS’.

The main goals of this use case are described as follows:

- to promote the circular economy by encouraging the citizens to reuse and provide recyclable materials to be used in the CEMS;
- to promote and share the knowledge in different fields within the Maker movement framework among Santander citizens;
- to effectively track and measure the usage of CEMS and reused materials;
- to encourage the collaboration among the citizens of Santander, by supporting each other in a common space.

Following these goals, we aim at providing an open space to facilitate the participation and collaboration of citizens from Santander. This open space will provide the needed tools that are normally out of their possibilities to let them create and share their creations. This space will be also a collaborative area where all the users can share their knowledge. Furthermore, to make this space sustainable and self-managed, it will rely on a platform with a credit-based system which will be used by citizens to be able to use the machines and tools, including booking the machines, tracking the usage of the machines and their status, proposing solutions to open issues, etc.

The CEMS is also a mean to promote the circular economy within Santander, including ecological awareness and material reuse. Therefore, those who contribute more to these circular economy goals will be awarded with exchangeable credits and acknowledgement within the Maker community in the city.

Use case 1: Daily basis

Alice and Bob are two citizens from Santander, who enjoy developing their own ideas. Alice is a ‘maker’ with several years of experience, and she would like to use the available tools at the CEMS. Bob is also interested on it, but he has no experience at all.

Alice is a technology enthusiast which creates their own solutions. She has a new smartphone and needs a new base to place it in her car while she is driving. Thus, Alice would like to use CEMS to take advantage of the facilities and the available tools and machinery. Firstly, she creates an account in the Pop-Machina platform, in charge of the CEMS management, obtaining an initial set of credits. Then, she books the machine she wants to use during an available timeframe. As she already has some knowledge using 3D printers, she creates the design and print the smartphone holder at the CEMS facilities, which will cost her most of the credits available in her account. In addition, to earn some more credits for future use, she decides to upload her design into the platform, making it available to other users of the CEMS.

Bob has heard about the CEMS, but he does not have any knowledge about the usage of the available tools and machinery, neither about creating any design for them. Fortunately, thanks to the existing programme to foster the circular economy in Santander, there are alternatives to learn about these tools. Thus, Bob goes to the CEMS, creates an account and exchanges 1 kilogram of plastics for a certain amount of credits. Using these credits, Bob can now use the machines and, instead of creating his own design, uses the one uploaded by Alice following the available instructions and being helped with some users at the CEMS. This exchange will give part of the credits to Alice, while allowing Bob to directly create the smartphone holder without any issues. Furthermore, in addition to the credits for the platform, Alice contributions in the Maker community in Santander are instantly recognised within the platform after this transaction is performed. She will be appearing as one of the top contributors in the Maker leadership board.

Use case 2: Hackathon

Alice, Bob and Carol received a notification about a new event that will be held next month in the CEMS in Santander. This event is a ‘hackathon’ in which they will have to solve a challenge proposed by Dave, another participant from the Maker community that has a problem who was not able to solve by himself.

Alice, Bob and Carol decide to participate at the event. Thus, they register into the Pop-Machina platform and get a ticket and the preliminary instructions about the challenge. This challenge consists of designing and building a set of garden stakes for plants using recyclable materials. It can be done either with plastic or wood, for example. In addition, these stakes will be used in the existing urban sharing gardens that are in the city of Santander.

The day of the event the contestants proposed several solutions, but Carol finally manage to come up with a solution that is the most sustainable for the purpose, according to the jury, which is composed by members of the Maker community. Thanks to this, Carol is awarded with credits and acknowledgement in the social networks and website from the platform.

Use case 3: Training

Alice, who is subscribed to the mailing list of the platform, receives an email with an invitation for a training opportunity. This email was not only showing the next training activities to be held in the CEMS, but also the possibilities of becoming a trainer for the Maker community. As she already has some knowledge on 3D design for 3D printers, she decides to apply and prepare a talk for the event. The platform registers her request and reserves an available spot in the formation event.

On the other hand, Bob wants to improve his knowledge 3D designs to be able to create his own designs in the future. Thus, once he receives the notification about the next training event, he registers as an attendant. As part of this event and the activities related to them, it is required to bring some materials (such as plastic, wood, etc.) to the event to be reused.

Once the event finalised, the trainers received credits for the community support, and they are acknowledged as ‘trainer expert’ in the social networks and website from the Pop-Machina platform.

Use case 4: Project and team building

Alice has a strong entrepreneurial spirit and has a new idea in which she will provide a service to companies with an environmental awareness that want to improve the sustainability of their services. However, she does not have neither the adequate tools or facilities, nor the knowledge in all the areas required for such goal. As part of the Maker Community, she notices that the CEMS proposes the opportunity to registered members to establish contact among them depending on their needs. Taking advantage of such service, she posts her needs into the Pop-Machina platform looking for experts in computer science that could help her to boost her business idea.

Carol, a computer science expert, set a meeting at the CEMS after reading the post set by Alice. Once they meet at CEMS and agree on certain conditions, Carol helps Alice to start her novel idea on circular economy business. Thanks to this collaboration, a newly created company by Carol and Alice is setup in Santander. In exchange, this new company keeps using the CEMS as an operational centre for certain tasks and support the CEMS sustainability through a sponsorship.

Use case 5: Company events

As part of a plan to raise awareness on the workers, the company ‘Green Energy Savings’ would like to use the CEMS area to organise several ‘Green Days’ in the circular economy topic. In this regard, the company creates an account in the platform and reserve the room for two days. Additionally, the company requests help and support from the Maker community to carry out this event. In exchange, the company will sponsor the CEMS with some funds and will provide the plastic waste for free to be used in the CEMS.

Alice and Dave, which have seen the initiative created by the company, will support the event. In exchange, they will receive an additional set of credits, and they will have the opportunity to make themselves known to the company and show their skills.

7.4.2 Repair Café

This use case has as an objective to engage the participation of citizens from Santander in the circular economy and the Maker Movement through periodic meetings where experienced and non-experienced citizens can meet and share their problems and solutions.

The main goals for this use case are described as follows:

- to foster a thriving community in Santander where citizens can help each other in the circular economy framework;
- to link citizens among them and to support each other in their respective areas of knowledge.

Having in mind these goals, the 'Repair Café' use case will be a series of events in which citizens from Santander will be invited in a common space to share their knowledge and help each other.

Carol and Dave are two citizens from Santander which are experts in different areas with a strong environmental awareness. However, several of the products they have are broken, and they do not have the knowledge, neither the tools to repair them. As they do not want to replace the products and give them a second opportunity, they would like to join the next Repair Café in Santander.

Use case 6: Repair café

Carol access to the platform and register herself as a Maker with knowledge in computer science and wood craft. Then, she checks when the next repair café will be held and register her interest in attending the event. While registering, she uploads the description of her needs, which consists of repairing several missing buttons from her favourite shirt. On the other hand, Dave has registered to the event looking that could help him to install a new antivirus on his computer, which was infected and does not work smoothly. Luckily for him, while he was registering into the platform for the event, he saw someone with computer knowledge attending the event and who could help him. In return, as he is a sewing expert, he could help other people with any issue with their clothes. Thus, he brings with him some of the sewing tools he already has.

The day of the 'Repair Café' event, registered people meet in the CEMS (Circular-Economy Makerspace). At the event, Carol and Dave meet and help each other with their broken shirt and faulty smartphone, respectively. In addition, they also help other attendants with their knowledge and take advantage of the tools and machinery available at the CEMS.

Once the event is about to finish, they register into the platform what they helped to repair, being confirmed by other attendants. In exchange, the platform awards with several credits to Carol and Dave, which they could use in the future at the CSEM. Furthermore, they are acknowledged and recognised in the platform as community helper and awarded with badges related to their experience, such as 'Techie' and 'Sewing Master'.

7.5 User requirements

Table 13. User requirements of the city of Santander

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URS1	Local authority	have access to indicators of impact and success of the circular activities	I can promote it internally and leverage further resources.
URS2	Local authority	know about best practices in circular making	I can apply them into our pilot.
URS3	Local authority	have a better mapping of potential flows of materials (from waste of one business to input of another - industrial symbiosis)	I can promote and support these flows if they are not already established
URS4	Local authority	know about policies on circular economy, and in particular circular making	I can promote them into my own city.
URS5	Local authority and/or circular FabLab manager	have the means (mailing lists, news webpage, forums, social networks, etc) to publicly promote the initiatives organised at the Santander CEMS as well as propose others which might be related	the local community gets engaged with the initiatives and special events.
URS6	FabLab manager	keep record of historical and real-time knowledge about Santander CEMS usage (number of people, usage of equipment, projects developed, etc)	I can assess the utilisation of the space and how to best use the resources
URS7	Maker	know about the availability of resources at the Santander CEMS and be able to make reservations at the Santander CEMS	I can organise my project and making /manufacturing work plan.
URS8	Maker/local business	share information about waste of my primary business that could be used as secondary raw material	I can feed (and get some revenue from) a local circular reutilisation of materials
URS9	Maker/expert	share my expertise (upload materials and organise trainings for the community (e.g. uploading video tutorials), or answer questions from other users and support them (e.g. FAQs, Q&A Forum, etc.)) with other members of the Santander community	I can contribute to the community and I can earn credits to use the resources at the CEMS for my own projects.
URS10	Maker/expert	be recognised as a valuable (based on user rankings and/or different badges that can be earned by active users (accounting number of projects and/or initiatives where the user is leader or participant, questions answered in the forum, usefulness of the answers, etc.) member of the local/national/international circular ecosystem.	I can enhance my visibility as a trustworthy collaborator for future circular economy projects
URS11	Maker/citizen	share my 'circular' ideas and expertise with other members of the community	multi-disciplinary teams can be built to bring 'circular' ideas to reality
URS12	Citizen/citizen	access and use the facilities	I can make my own 3D prints, Wood crafts, etc.
URS13	Maker /Citizen	search and exchange raw materials	I can make my own products

Table 13. User requirements of the city of Santander (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URS14	Maker	certify the origin of the materials used in my projects	I can add a label of 'circularity' to the objects I am creating
URS15	Local authority	keep track of the flow of materials within the makerspace	I can enforce existing policies.
URS16	Citizen	reuse existing maker designs or provide my own	I can use existing designs or contribute with my own designs to the Maker Community
URS17	Citizen	be able to request help from expert users to use the CEMS facilities	I can make my own ideas with limited knowledge and learn on how to use the facilities
URS18	Citizen	be able to know the upcoming events programmed by the CEMS or the Maker Movement	I can participate in the events
URS19	NGO/Social aware association	be able to promote events or actions related with circular economy	I can engage the community around the makerspace
URS20	Entrepreneur/Professional	share my expertise or request support from other members of the Santander community	I can start professional relationships with other members from the community
URS21	Entrepreneur/Professional	be able to reserve exclusively the CEMS facilities	I can make an event for my employees/business partners

8. City of Venlo

8.1 Introduction

Venlo is a municipality (www.venlo.nl) and a city in the southeast of the Netherlands, next to the German border. Venlo has a population of about 100,000. Venlo is a frontrunner in recycling of raw materials, so that products are 100% recyclable and waste serves as raw material. Venlo embraces the principles of cradle-to-cradle. Cradle-to-Cradle (C2C) is a sustainability concept, in the products of which various companies in the region have invested. In addition, the C2C ExpoLAB and the C2C Product Innovation Institute are based in Venlo. Venlo council has taken the initiative to let the region embrace C2C and circular economy. Venlo and the region are the second largest logistics centre in the Netherlands.

Venlo is a main rail hub from the Rotterdam harbour to the large German industrial areas, with some 15 million consumers. The region of Venlo employs 64,000 people in logistics. About 22,000 lorries and trucks pass through Venlo, on a daily basis. Venlo and its region constitute also one of the largest agricultural areas in the Netherlands and an important manufacturing area, especially for high-tech industries. Many people in Venlo are employed in high-tech industries. On the other hand, Venlo is also a city with many residents who do not have higher education levels. In this setting, a project like KanDoen, which constitutes a maker initiative extensively described in the next section, is of great importance for a city like Venlo.

The city can benefit from Pop-Machina in the following ways:

- find strategic and tactical solutions for the lack of highly educated people and the barriers this creates in the development of maker's spaces;
- further raising of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.;
- achieve applied knowledge on how to promote circular initiatives;
- achieve detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem;
- achieve information for supporting the commercialisation of KanDoen or other circular activities;
- enable the growth of the amount of KanDoen activities and to increase the quality of KanDoen activities;
- find strategic and tactical solutions for the sustainable integration of more vulnerable groups into society using their skills.

8.2 Current situation

8.2.1 Overview

In 2009, the discussion of a strong national and European position for Venlo was challenged by the issues that the region had to deal with. Ageing and a reduction in the attractiveness of business activity were issues that could have an important influence on the vitality of the city and the maintenance of facilities. That is why Venlo embraced the C2C principles in 2009: waste is food, use the sun, and enjoy diversity. In essence, this was and is an innovative economic design principle with the highest

form of sustainability as the result to be pursued. On this basis, the so-called ‘Venlo Principles’ were formulated:

- continue to innovate;
- connect place and context;
- managing and valuing food;
- enjoy mobility;
- use the sun;
- create clean air, water and soil;
- resign for the pleasure of future generations.

The principles have provided us with an important source of inspiration in our efforts to organise society in a healthy, safe and sustainable manner, creating added value for both the earth (planet) and its inhabitants (people) in an affordable manner (profit). This is based on clean energy, safe and healthy materials and diversity. The Strategic Vision Venlo 2030, which was drawn up in 2010, states that C2C has the potential to bind innovation, business activity, young people and higher educated people to the region.

8.2.1.1 Plans and initiatives relevant to Pop-Machina

Waste policy plan of the Municipality of Venlo: Material Policy Plan for 2015-2020

This plan contains a legal and policy framework and an implementation programme. This programme is based on the programme of the national Ministry of Infrastructure and Environment. This ministry adopted the National Waste to Raw Materials programme, the main objective of which is to stimulate the transition to a circular economy, i.e. a closed materials cycle. This plan has been implemented by the municipalities from 2015. This programme has led to 75% waste separation by 2020 (equivalent to 100 kilograms of residual waste per inhabitant per year), and the goal is for that to reach in time 100%.

The municipal waste regulation,¹⁰ which is publicly available, contains regulations of the municipality, the province and the water board.

Council programme ‘Circular and sustainable capital’

The policy theme ‘circular & sustainable’, in December 2018, was promoted to a separate programmatic environment, named ‘Circular and sustainable capital’. The main strategic objective of this programme is to achieve awareness and support collaboration within the society towards the creation of a sustainable environment. The goal is the accomplishment of the national and (supra)-local climate ambitions. This Council programme has a direct relationship with all other Council programmes. After all, sustainability and increasing sustainability form the main theme throughout all of these programs.

Coalition agreement and ambitions of this College of mayor and aldermen (2018-2022)

The city of Venlo has identified sustainability as a spearhead in the coalition agreement ‘Samen Venlo Veranderen’ (Changing Venlo Together). For this college, ‘sustainability’ is, just like the term ‘liveability’, a collective name for many topics, all of which contribute to a better and cleaner world. After years of planning, the college now considers it time to realise it. Sustainability projects can only succeed if there is support for them among the population. This requires from the government a lot of investments in the neighbourhoods. This College wants to work actively together on this support base and pursues the implementation of concrete activities.

¹⁰ <http://zoekdienst.overheid.nl/CVDR/CVDRResultaat.aspx?postcode=5944&datumgeldendop=15-08-2019&searchtype=Simple&sortBy=alternativetitel%2fascending&onderwerp=Milieu&gemeente=venlo>

Themes identified in the coalition agreement:

- joint local power generation;
- optimisation of waste separation;
- recognisable point of advice for residents and businesses;
- sustainable (housing) construction and renovation projects;
- sustainable distribution in neighbourhoods and city centres;
- sustainable economy;
- sustainable food production;
- sustainable mobility.

These themes are included in the implementation plan, which also contains themes such as ‘be in progress’, ‘be prepared’ or ‘be part of a larger project or activity’. The College wants to make as many connections as possible between these themes. The College also wants to link these themes to existing dossiers such as the society agenda, making social property more sustainable, revitalisation industrial sites, management and maintenance of educational housing and large-scale renovation of home ownership (by corporations). The aim of the joint venture with the partners is a broad information and advice point. This point can have various purposes, such as a large-scale circular purchasing in combination with broader and, above all, integrated effort of professional partners to raise awareness and to improve the quality and relieve citizens and businesses of their worries. The College explicitly wants to work together to realise ambitions. This creates a positive environment for collaboration of partners and society. It also applies to the connection with the economy and the social policy, so that eventually everyone can share the positive effects of investments in sustainability and circularity.

City deal circular city

In the City Deal Circular City, the parties are working together to stimulate access to the new market for circular economy for both demanders and suppliers by making knowledge and good examples accessible via shared (digital) platforms, and by putting frontrunners in the shop window. Cities have come together to take joint steps to accelerate the transition to a circular economy. The strength of this City Deal Circular City is that each city shapes this transition in its own way, but learns from experiences in other cities. Cities are working with the central government and partners to accelerate the transition to a circular economy. The regional level of the city, in combination with a national approach, is therefore an essential part of achieving the national transition to a circular economy.

The City Deal Circular City’s ambition is to achieve fully circular cities by 2050 at the latest, similar to the ambition expressed in the government-wide circular economy programme.

The following parties are partners in this City Deal:

- municipalities: Amsterdam, Almere, Apeldoorn, Dordrecht, Haarlemmermeer, Rotterdam, Utrecht and Venlo;
- state: The Minister of Infrastructure and the Environment, the Minister of Economic Affairs and the Minister of Housing and the Government Service;
- other parties: TNO, Circle Economy and Royal HaskoningDHV.

De Stadstuinderij (The city gardening)

The aim of Stadstuinderij is everyone to be able to grow their own vegetables and make the world a little more beautiful. All the vegetables at the Stadstuinderij will be grown without the use of artificial fertilisers or pesticides. From the vegetable garden on the Barracks grounds, knowledge is transferred to support initiatives in neighbourhoods and schools. The ambition is to enable the construction of vegetable gardens in every place, where people wish to share a vegetable garden in their own area.

Akarton

Cardboard is 100% recyclable and it is one of the few products that is recycled worldwide. Akarton is committed to reduce CO2 emissions and an environmentally conscious purchasing process. In this initiative, raw materials are produced in a responsible manner. Furthermore, the engines of the machines utilised are as sustainable as possible. LED lighting is used in the hall, reacting to the amount of sunlight, so that no energy is wasted. As far as the production process is concerned, residual cardboard that is left over is also reused. In addition, part of the work is out by employees who live at distance from the labour market. They are offered the opportunity to gain experience in an industrial working environment. This shows that Akarton is an innovative company that continues to work on the application of the Cradle-to-Cradle principles.

StoneCycling

StoneCycling from Venlo turns the rubble from demolished buildings into brand new bricks and tiles. After much experimentation in a garage, 2 entrepreneurs managed to find the right formula. In the spring of 2015, the first batch of cradle-to-cradle tiles and bricks was made. In the meantime, their company has experienced good growth. This innovative company talks about the way in which they create new bricks from demolition waste.

These ideas were very well received by architects and builders. The company StoneCycling was founded and proved to be a true game changer in a construction world that yearns for innovative, sustainable materials. The stone is suitable for various applications. Think of office buildings, homes, but also restaurants and various interior applications. The commercial roll-out takes place from the office in Amsterdam.

The WasteBasedBrick can be baked up to 300 degrees less hot than a conventional stone. As a result, energy and production costs are significantly reduced and CO2 emissions are reduced by 25 to 35%. So in addition to re-use, producing our brick is more environmentally friendly than with the old products. In addition, smarter demolition will be encouraged, looking for high-quality applications for the waste that would otherwise be dumped.

Building material ECOR

Eric Logtens, who was born and raised in Venlo, earns his living entirely from Cradle to Cradle. Logtens, a graduate ergonomist, is director of ECOR Noble Environmental Benelux, manufacturer of building materials ECOR. ECOR is made from fully recycled and recyclable biomaterial. This can range from residual products from the agricultural and food sector to old (office) paper; and from discarded jeans to sawdust.

Energy counter Venlo

The independent Energy Desk in Venlo helps with questions and initiatives about making homes more sustainable. An energy coach helps with questions and comes to peoples' homes in person for an energy scan.

Rendiz

Rendiz, a care provider and social entrepreneur, builds sustainable homes and works with people living at distance from the labour market.

Zomerparkfeesten

Zomerparkfeesten is a festival that was first organised in 1977 as a street party. From 1979 the event was moved to the nearby park. The name was then changed into Zomerparkfeesten. Zomerparkfeesten is a free event with music and theatre. The last ten years is Zomerparkfeesten with more than 90,000 visits over four days one of the largest events in the province Limburg. The festival has seven

stages and also organises activities on the site itself. The number of performances is more than 120. On Friday there is traditionally a senior afternoon and on Sunday there are activities for children.

The programme of the Zomerparkfeesten is a mix of established names and innovation. The Zomerparkfeesten has been and continues to be free of charge since its inception. The festival is organised entirely by volunteers. The festival has about 400 volunteers of its own. In addition, Zomerparkfeest makes use of associations for extra tasks during the festival itself. An additional 600 volunteers will be deployed. In exchange, they will receive a contribution to the association's coffers.

The festival is made possible by sponsors. More than 150 companies sponsor in money or services. In addition, the festival has 1,600 'Friends' who pay an annual amount of 35 euros in exchange for a T-shirt and an extra festival evening prior to the actual festival.

Zomerparkfeesten is committed to sustainable energy, healthy use of materials, sustainable interaction with people, reducing waste and so on. KanDoen uses the banners and flags for their production of bags, wallets, aprons, etc.

Advice for entrepreneurs and organisations through the C2C ExpoLAB

The C2C ExpoLAB is based in Venlo and has a wealth of experience in applying the circular principles in practice. Some examples are the cradle to cradle municipal office, sports complex Egerbos and gym and primary school the Zuidstroom. In addition, various tenders have been completed, both for the selection of design and construction teams as well as products and services.

The C2C ExpoLAB advises both clients and contractors in the practical application of the circular principles within the construction and government sectors. Clients are e.g. municipalities, governments, school boards, project developers or other public organisations. The clients are architects, contractors and architectural advisors.

Het Goed: recycle department store

Het Goed is a chain of recycle department stores spread throughout the Netherlands. One of them is located in Venlo.

The mission: respect for people and the environment. In practice this means to deliver work through reuse and give people and stuff a second chance. In addition to reusing used items, Het Goed makes work a reality. Het Goed offers suitable work to people who are at a distance from the labour market. In the recycle department stores, they can gain experience in an easily accessible way and this is put into practice with workshops. With appropriate support, employees repair bicycles, make products from collected textiles and redecorate furniture by giving them a modern twist. This gives them a greater chance of finding a job at a regular company.

All the incoming stuff that arrives daily at the recycling stores is sorted with care. It concerns products such as clothing, blankets, shoes, household goods, furniture, bicycles, toys, books and electronics. In Venlo it is possible to collect clothing by textile containers which are spread throughout the city. Products are sold for a small price or it will be ensured that they are reused in a different way.

Het Goed cannot achieve this mission alone. That's why they work together with partners.

In the Netherlands, Het Goed collects 20 million kilos of textiles and household goods every year. More than 80% of this is reused. The majority is going to be sold in one of the 26 locations, including one in Venlo. Het Goed has received a certification for social entrepreneurship.

Parties which are involved: Municipality of Venlo, KanDoen, De Stadstuinderij, Environmental station (owned by the municipality of Venlo and carried out by a private company) and Het Goed.

The goals are that volunteers/stakeholders from the neighbourhood start working in their neighbourhood with reusable materials (originating from an environmental station/recycle department store) in order to realise time spending, products and services, primarily, with a collective interest. In

addition to the goals mentioned above, it is important that participants and stakeholders (neighbourhood residents) use raw materials in the neighbourhood and become aware of the existence of an environmental station and recycle department store.

Target groups are the residents in the neighbourhood, youth and seniors, technically trained people, unemployed people and associations.

The results: Participants become aware of the fact that the reuse of raw materials is important and useful and everyone's contribution of separating 'waste' is indispensable and necessary. The social cohesion in the neighbourhood, as well as the quality of life in the public space, is noticeably improved.

Residents in the neighbourhoods will make (more) use of the environmental station and recycle department store.

Activities: making, repairing and upgrading (consumer) objects and facilities; supervising transport to the environmental station and to the recycle department store.

Repair cafés

Repair cafes are free accessible meeting places where things are repaired together. At the location of the repair café, tools and materials are available to perform all possible repairs. On clothing, furniture, electrical appliances, bicycles, toys, etc. Expert volunteers are also present, with repair knowledge and skills in all kinds of areas.

Visitors bring broken items from home. In the Repair Café they work together with the experts. So there is always something to learn. If there is nothing to repair, a repair café is also a meeting point where residents of the neighbourhood meet each other, or a place where it is possible to help with someone else's repair.

In Venlo are located 4 repair cafés spread throughout Venlo.

The Employers' Service Hub Northern region of the Province Limburg

This is cooperation between entrepreneurs and public parties. The municipality of Venlo is one of the public parties. The Employer Service Hub invests in the relationship between entrepreneurs and government. This partnership between entrepreneurs and public parties leads to structurally more work for people in North Limburg.

8.2.2 Current business process models

8.2.2.1 Programme Management

At the end of 2017, the municipality of Venlo decided to work programmatically. A new way of working for the organisation was implemented in six different programmes.

8.2.2.2 Programmatic working

For themes that require management attention, integrity and external attention, the municipality works with programmes. A programme is defined as 'a coherent whole of activities'. A programme is defined as 'a coherent set of activities'. The programmes therefore correspond to the municipal policy fields and ensure connection and focus within the organisation. The sum of the six programmes 'covers' the content of the municipal budget.

The programme manager ensures that the official organisation and the town council are prepared for new developments. They bring in information from outside and vice versa. They make connections and provide focus. Within our municipal organisation, they act as the client for a wide variety of projects and are also the first point of contact and sparring partner for the administrative portfolio holder in terms of content.

Each programme manager has his or her own programme(s), but together they are responsible for the whole. The objectives of the programmes are closely linked to the main tasks of the strategic vision of Venlo 2030 (<https://www.venlo.nl/file/226/download>).

The municipality of Venlo works with the following six programmes:

1. Healthy and active Venlo
Venlo is becoming a community in which everyone is challenged and given the opportunity to get the best out of themselves. A vital community, with appropriate support, is important to us.
2. Liveable Venlo
It is important that Venlo is transformed to an attractive place to live, stay and work. A municipality that is subservient, clean, whole and safe with liveable neighbourhoods.
3. Boundless Venlo
Venlo is aware of its special location on a major transport axis to Eastern Europe and on the German border. We want to make Venlo a welcoming, internationally oriented community that welcomes newcomers.
4. Prosperous Venlo
Economic development is at the forefront of the Welfare Venlo programme. The aim is to ensure sufficient employment in the labour market and local and regional purchasing power.
5. City centre of Venlo
Venlo is a vibrant city. The ambition is to make Venlo the administrative, cultural and economic beating heart of the Euro region.
6. Circular and sustainable capital
The city of Venlo has a leading position in the field of C2C. We want to maintain and strengthen this position in the future. We want to give more substance to the transition to sustainable energy and climate neutrality.

Citizens and companies interact with the city authorities through the common communication channels offered by the city (citizen phone line, email, social media). They also use the application Invest in Venlo, Visit Venlo, to report abandoned waste in public spaces and request from the city authorities to collect it.¹¹

Regarding the processes and responsibilities of the city, several internal teams are related to Pop-Machina:

- administration team;
- team Building and environment;
- communication team;
- team Financial affairs;
- team Participation and development;
- team Personnel and organisation;
- social Neighbourhood Teams;
- team Surveillance and Enforcement;
- team Employment;
- teamwork and Accessibility;
- team Realisation and Management of Public Space;
- team Corporate staff;
- team Property and land management.

¹¹ <https://www.venlo.nl/meteen-melden-0>

8.2.3 Stakeholders' identification

The user groups that interact for purposes relevant to the project are:

Table 14. Stakeholders identified in the city of Venlo

User group	Role
Local government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defines the policy challenges and priorities to be addressed by the project - Conducts resources and material flows - Stimulates the development of maker communities - Participates in the policy debate for circular economy
Entrepreneurs, repair cafés, KanDoen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to circular production - Provide and receive know-how and practical skills - Connect with communities to exchange ideas, collaborate in new product/service development, and acquire materials and parts required for their circular endeavours - Develop circular products and services - Experiment with circular products and services - Suggest best practices in circular production - Receive proper technical and business knowledge in order to develop more circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Citizens/residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to new circular products and services - Help identify, mobilise and connect untapped sources of knowledge and competencies that could contribute to the closing of the circular loops - Help identify and select urban areas and spaces that could benefit to DIY circular activities in the context of Pop-Machina - Promote products and services developed by KanDoen and other circular relatives of Pop-Machina - Appreciate the quality, usefulness and sustainability of the circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Researchers for sustainable production, development and planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide scientific knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy

8.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

In the table below we describe the challenges of Venlo in the context of Pop-Machina and the potential of the project to address them.

Challenge	Pop-Machina possibilities
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	To collect, store and provide the relevant data and analytics based on this data
Lack of applied knowledge on how to promote circular initiatives	To educate and train stakeholders on how to develop, manage initiatives related to circular endeavours
The lack of better-educated inhabitants is hampering the development of maker's spaces	Pop-Machina develops facilities that enables the less educated to participate in a maker's space
Further raising of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.	To increase awareness and promote sustainable activities and behaviours through a structured approach, driven by results
Supporting the commercialisation of KanDoen or other circular activities	To develop appropriate business support services for KanDoen/entrepreneurs of Pop-Machina
Expand the amount and the quality of KanDoen activities	To develop new sustainable products that meet the needs and interests of citizens
Sustainable integration of the KanDoen population in the society	Pop-Machina gathers knowledge about how to connect sustainable and circular activities with socially weaker groups of people

8.3 TO-BE scenario

8.3.1 Overview

KanDoen is the starting point for the pilots. From the KanDoen point of view, we are going to expand ongoing activities by using more intensive the common entrepreneurial networks which are already involved in manufacturing products like the bee hotels. The purpose is to make the production more sustainable and add new products to the current collection. In the meantime the current entrepreneurs can act as an incentive towards new entrepreneurs.

We want to increase the awareness of residents on the subject of sustainability and circularity by:

- drawing residents (vulnerable and not or less vulnerable) into circular and sustainable activities;
- promoting new circular KanDoen-products, like bird houses which can be used for exterminating the processionary caterpillars. Another idea is the stolen bicycle project;
- people with a distance to the labour market have a permanent position and role in stimulating circularity and sustainability;
- finding new partners, commercial and not commercial (in Dutch 'non-profit').

In Venlo, there are three KanDoen-locations each with their own character and each of them is specialised in different activities. KanDoen is a working location for people who need a lot of structure during their activities. That is why the opening hours for the public are restricted. It is possible for local residents to join KanDoen during the week, provided that agreements have been made in advance. At Friday afternoon KanDoen is publicly accessible.

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places;
- organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers;
- trading and buying products which are certified for circularity;
- smart contracts for trading goods under certifying circularity;
- community applications for civil forums;
- organising and offering training for policy makers;

- access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, lawyers, IT policy makers, etc.);
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives.

8.3.2 Business requirements

Table 15. Business requirements of the city of Venlo

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping relevant information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - KanDoen - Repair cafés - Citizens/residents - Entrepreneurs - Managers of resources and materials
Lack of applied knowledge on how to promote circular initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Organising and offering online and offline training and business support sessions for makers - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning
The lack of better-educated inhabitants is hampering the development of maker's spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Organising training for groups of interested citizens - Organising and offering training for policy makers - Social collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - Knowledge partners - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Local education
Further raising of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) - Analysing the current awareness/interest - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community forums - Local government - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives
Supporting the commercialisation of KanDoen or other circular activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketing programmes - Market research - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering online and offline training and business support sessions for makers - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - Citizens/residents - Knowledge partners - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators

Table 15. Business requirements of the city of Venlo (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Expand the amount and the quality of KanDoen activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Market research - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government (environmental policy makers, urban planners, etc.) - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Social Cooperatives
Sustainable integration of the KanDoen population in the society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - KanDoen - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production and professionals and researchers for social matters

8.4 Use cases

8.4.1 Overview

KanDoen is a present facility from the municipality of Venlo that focuses on assisting participants who, due to whatever circumstances, are at a disadvantage on the labour market. KanDoen organises workplaces, activities and projects to support vulnerable residents of Venlo in their social participation, active commitment and increasing self-reliance. On average, 350 participants are active within KanDoen. KanDoen has three physical locations where the makerspaces of Pop-Machina will be realised.

Through Pop-Machina, KanDoen will have the opportunity to set up various pilots during the duration of the project, which focus on reuse of materials, sustainability, upcycling and co-creation. During the Pop-Machina project, KanDoen will further develop the pilots ‘bicycle workshop’, ‘wood workshop’, ‘Upcycling and re-use of plastic’.

The most important objectives we want to achieve with the pilots and during Pop-Machina are:

- making products at KanDoen more sustainable;
- transition from downcycling to upcycling;
- creating social added value;
- using the pilots to create more workplaces and activities for participants within KanDoen;
- raise awareness on the reuse of materials;
- increasing support from the Venlo community for the circular and sustainable KanDoen activities.

8.4.2 Venlo pilot use cases

8.4.2.1 Use case 1: Bicycle workshop

People at KanDoen have worked hard and successfully in recent years to develop the bicycle workshop. The bicycle workshop is organised by a group of people within KanDoen with a distance to the labour market. This is not the most vulnerable group. They refurbish second-hand bicycles for sale and repair bicycles. If possible, a bicycle is given a second life, but if there is no other way, they remove the usable parts and reuse them.

At various KanDoen locations there are bicycle workshops that serve as work experience places or as labour activation.

People with a minimum wage can turn to KanDoen for repairs to their bicycle. A small financial compensation must be paid for the time and materials which has been used. They do not compete with the local regular bicycle shops. If the client has a normal wage, he or she cannot turn to KanDoen. KanDoen works together with the social service for pupil transport, with a subsidy foundation for poor families and with the supporting team for unemployment from the municipality of Venlo to provide second-hand bicycles at an affordable price to people with a small wallet. For example, KanDoen is working on a project to stimulate parents with disabled children and motivate them to travel to school by bicycle. Usually, they go to school by special taxi transport, but cycling is much healthier and more environmentally friendly. As a result, parents are better able to take on the role of guiding their children. At the same time, the municipal costs for taxi transport for this group of pupils will be reduced. The bicycle project contributes significantly to this movement.

In the first quarter of 2020, KanDoen started collecting orphan bicycles in the municipality of Venlo. Previously, this was done by a local bicycle mechanic, but for him the storage of the bicycles was a problem. For orphan bicycles, we have to take into account a legal deadline for the storage period. Bicycles are first labelled, and if it turns out that bicycles are actually orphaned, they are collected by KanDoen. KanDoen arranges the storage. After the legal storage period has expired the bicycle workshop starts sorting and, where possible, refurbishing the bicycles. KanDoen is also responsible for disposing of the residual material. Throughout the process there is close cooperation with the municipality of Venlo.

With the help of Pop-Machina we can further optimise the projects within the bicycle workshop and upcycle parts that can no longer be used for a 'new bicycle'. Thought is given to manufacturing jewellery, furniture and other home accessories.

8.4.2.2 Use case 2: Woodworking shop

There is a woodworking shop at every KanDoen location. Participants work on various wood projects such as making birdhouses and bee hotels.

On behalf of the Green Facility Department of the municipality of Venlo, KanDoen makes birdhouses for birds to combat the oak processionary caterpillar. The oak processionary caterpillar causes a lot of nuisance during spring and summer time. The caterpillar lives in summer oaks, which are common in built-up areas in the Netherlands. The oak processionary caterpillar causes many physical complaints. Various bird species eat the oak processionary caterpillar. By placing birdhouses, these birds are lured and thus the oak processionary caterpillar is fought in a natural way.

The birdhouses are made of wood which comes from the environmental station in Venlo and the wood may not have been treated. In addition, we work together with a local timber trade. They supply residual wood (Sapeli) from sustainably managed forests.

On behalf of the companies Bijenhotelkopen.nl and Impact-Spots, KanDoen makes bee houses. Bijenhotelkopen.nl is a social enterprise. They do business in a social and sustainable way, with a social mission.

A bee hotel supports the nesting and living quarters of the wild bee. This is desperately needed, since the Dutch wild bees are not doing well. Half of all 538 species are threatened, while they are very important for our food supply. 80% of our edible crops depend on pollination by wild bees and other pollinating insects. The biggest threat faced by wild bees is lack of food and nesting space. With the large, professional bee hotels, we can easily and quickly offer new nesting opportunities.

For the production of the bee hotels, they work with certified wood from Dutch or Belgian nature reserves. Wood with this certification has been produced according to strict rules about legality, protection of nature and about the rights and welfare of the local population and workers. The system is aimed at ensuring that nature is preserved in the future and that the population, businesses and consumers can benefit from what the forest has to offer them.

With the help of Pop-Machina we can produce more birdhouses and we can make the knowledge available to the inhabitants of Venlo, so that they themselves are also able to make birdhouses on

their own or with the help of KanDoen. Furthermore, we can increase the production of the bee houses, which increases the nesting capacity for wild bees.

8.4.2.3 Use case 3: Reuse of plastic/upcycling

Within KanDoen we intend to set up a pilot for the reuse of plastic materials with the help of Pop-Machina. The intention is that we will purchase equipment to be able to process plastic. This requires the purchase of a shredder, an extrusion machine, an injection machine and a compression machine, to start with. The idea is to collect plastic within our own population and perhaps in the neighbourhoods where the KanDoen locations are located and use this to make new products.

We intend to collaborate with an industrial designer from Venlo on this. His work is mostly about reuse, sustainability and the potential of materials. This will enable us to reach out to other audiences from KanDoen. We will also participate in 'Precious Plastics'.

In the creative workshop at KanDoen we are already working on the banner project. Products like bags for laptops are being made in KanDoen from old banner material. These banners are donated by events, associations and companies. Bags and other (business) gifts are made on request.

8.5 User requirements

Table 16. User requirements of the city of Venlo

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URV1	Local government, Entrepreneurs, repair cafés, KanDoen, researchers	have an overview of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	I can make decisions about extension of makerspaces So that I can make decisions about involving new partners in KanDoen
URV2	Entrepreneurs, repair cafés, KanDoen	have knowledge of tools to promote circular initiatives	I can expand circular initiatives
URV3	Local government, Citizens/residents	know how, despite a lack of highly educated people in our municipality, I can still work on the further development of maker's spaces	a larger proportion of the inhabitants of Venlo are involved in the circular and sustainable economy
URV4	Local government, Citizens/residents	raise citizens' awareness and interest in recycling, re-use and re-use	more residents are able to: reduce their waste flows; make economic gains from reusing things; repair broken products instead of replacing them
URV5	Entrepreneurs, repair cafés, KanDoen	support the commercialisation of KanDoen or other circular activities	KanDoen products and circular activities also become economically attractive
URV6	Entrepreneurs, repair cafés, KanDoen	expand the amount and the quality of KanDoen activities	KanDoen products and circular activities become more attractive to a larger audience and that more residents become interested in these products through variation in the range
URV7	Entrepreneurs, repair cafés, KanDoen Citizens/residents	achieve a sustainable integration of the KanDoen population in the society	vulnerable people can take their place in society and participate in society as full citizens

9. City of Istanbul

9.1 Introduction

Istanbul is a transcontinental city straddling two continents by its inland sea Marmara. One of the world's busiest waterways, the Bosphorus, is situated in north western Turkey between the Black Sea and the Sea of Marmara. Connecting the two seas, Bosphorus also separates Istanbul to two sides, known as European side and Asian side. Istanbul is the largest populated city of Turkey with a population of more than 15,000,000 inhabitants. As one of the largest urban agglomerations in Europe, Istanbul has 39 districts administered by the Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM) and locally by District Municipalities. The city boundaries cover a surface area of 1,830 km² and Istanbul Province covers 6,220 km².

9.2 Current situation

9.2.1 Overview

Istanbul is the economic capital of Turkey because of its strategic location, trade capacity and population. The city generates almost 40% of Turkey's GDP and its annual contribution to the state budget is about 40%, too. As the country's largest industrial centre, approximately 20% of the country's industrial labour force is employed in Istanbul. Some of the city's main industrial products are food processing, textile production, oil products and construction. Istanbul is also the most important export gate of Turkey, concentrating 36% of Turkey's total exportation activity. Moreover, despite the challenges related with rapid population growth, Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM) governs the city with a vision of local governance of a brand city that generates global value with regard to urban planning and civilisation and facilitates life with sustainable, innovative solutions.

The most important initiatives relevant to the project in İstanbul include:

- **İstanbul Urban Transformation Master Plan (IUTMP)** <http://ikdmp.istanbul/>: It is a study in which the macro and micro dimensions of Istanbul are handled and a concrete comparison of long-term forecasting and planning process is made. İUTMP works for developing a spatial and strategic planning approach for urban transformation across the Historical Peninsula with 1/5000 scale, developing 1/1000 scale spatial planning approach in 5 areas to be chosen with different urban characteristics and preparing the Urban Transformation Design Criteria and Transformation Guide started this year and are still ongoing;
- **Istanbul Climate Change Action Plan (ICCAP)**: Within the scope of Istanbul Climate Change Action Plan (ICCAP) works that were conducted and completed for the purpose of identifying local climate change reduction and conformity policies and identifying and prioritising the necessary measures for Istanbul, our Municipality prepared the Roadmap Report which details the outputs targeted by the Action plan, the responsibilities and timeline and the final action plan report which identifies climate change compliance and greenhouse gas reduction actions on a sectoral basis, aiming to reduce urban greenhouse gas emissions. In this regard, workshops and panel discussions were made for various stakeholder groups, including district municipalities. All current details regarding Istanbul Climate Change Action Plan (ICCAP) are published on www.iklim.istanbul and

www.climate.istanbul. Awareness raising activities for promoting the action plan continued. Moreover, Istanbul Climate Change Symposium was organised under scope of the Climate Change Awareness and Works Development Project this year.

The main findings and strategic priorities are explained in the ICCAP:

1. with ICCAP, the carbon footprint of the city is calculated, future climate scenarios are established, sectoral vulnerabilities are determined, and mitigation and adaptation measures are defined;
 2. Istanbul will reduce its emissions by 33% by 2030 compared to its business as usual (BAU) scenario;
 3. Istanbul will manage its disaster risks and reduce its recovery period to better adapt to a changing climate;
 4. IMM will further develop its institutional capacity for climate change;
- **Organisational Zero Waste Management:** Zero Waste Project implementation works within the organisation of Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality have been commenced in the main service buildings of our Municipality. In this framework, current status assessment was made with regard to management of hazardous/harmless organisational wastes across the organisation of IMM, the types of wastes forming, their disposal methods, responsible units and compliance to legislation were evaluated and Organisational Waste Management Procedure was prepared. All types of wastes forming or might form in IMM units were identified, Waste Control Plan was prepared and waste collection, storage and disposal methods and responsible units were identified;
 - **Smart City Project:** the purpose of Istanbul Smart City Project is to demonstrate the theoretical infrastructure for Istanbul to become a ‘smart city’, design the smart city applications suitable for Istanbul, establish the road map for implementing the applications and develop the capacity of our Municipality in this regard under the master plan approach. Within the scope of this project, Literature Scanning, Current Status Analysis, Architectural Design and Roadmap Creation phases were completed and the ‘Smart Cities Master Plan’ was created. Short, middle and long-term realisation plans were created for the projects prioritised in this regard;
 - **ZEMİN İstanbul:** it is the first **entrepreneurship centre** opened for urban development/city science. It was established in order to increase the international competitiveness of Istanbul in the area of innovation, accelerate transformation to an information society and to develop information-based economy and qualified employment. It aims for effective use of information and communication technologies, development and popularisation of technology and creation of collaboration networks. It is intended to make Istanbul the innovation centre of Turkey and to let ‘Made in Istanbul’ brand expand to the global market. 678 project applications were made on the initial call this year, whereupon the project selection board chose the best 20 projects and the activities were commenced in the incubation centre. Furthermore, ZEMİN İstanbul collaboration protocol was signed between our Municipality, Boğaziçi University, Yıldız Technical University, İstanbul Technical University and Istanbul Provincial Directorate of National Education.

ZEMİN İstanbul’s roles in the Pop-Machina are:

1. promoting Zemin Istanbul to all partners within the scope of the project and increasing its awareness in Europe;
2. meeting the concrete outputs of the project with the citizen in Zemin Istanbul, experiencing them and getting feedback from them;
3. organising various workshops in Zemin Istanbul within the scope of the Project, engaging in activities to enhance governance.

9.2.2 Current business process models

Regarding the processes and responsibilities of the city departments related to Pop-Machina, these are:

- **Department of Information Technologies:** Within the scope of the project, to promote Zemin Istanbul to all partners and to increase its awareness in Europe, to present the concrete outputs of the project with the citizen in Zemin Istanbul, to organise various Hekaton, workshops in Zemin Istanbul and conducting activities to increase governance are the key roles of the department in Pop-Machina;
- **Department of Environmental Protection and Control:** This department has three subunits Environmental Protection, Marine Services and Waste Management. Waste Management Directorate is responsible for ensuring the collection and transfer of solid waste to sanitary landfill and ensuring the cleanliness of public areas. Also, this department holds projects about training and environmental awareness like Zero Waste project. Pop-Machina project is carrying out through this department;
- **Department of Institutional Development and Management Systems.** Directorate of European Union Relations is one of the subunits of this department. EU Relations as a partner in the project is managing official correspondences with the EU Commission and Turkey;
- **İSTAÇ A.Ş.:** İSTAC is an environmental company of IMM. The main service of the İSTAC is waste management. The roles of İSTAC are; analysis of city ecosystem, analysis of market research, analysis of general framework, analysis of user requirements, analysis of impact assessment. İSTAC is also responsible for conducting pilot studies and for participating to integrative innovation portfolio.

9.2.3 Stakeholders' identification

The user groups that interact for purposes relevant to the project are:

Table 17. Stakeholders identified in the city of Istanbul

User group	Role
Local governmental authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foster the development of maker communities - To define the legal framework and create a legal roadmap for stakeholders - To provide pure waste and to bring it to the pilot area for using as raw material by the makers - Establishing the link between Manufacturers, NGOs, Professionals - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
District municipalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To define the legal framework and create a legal roadmap for stakeholders - To provide pure waste and to bring it to the pilot area for using as raw material by the makers - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to making and circular production - Provide and receive know-how, tinkering ideas and practices - Connect with other makers and communities to exchange ideas, collaborate in new product/service development, and acquire materials and parts required for their circular endeavours - Develop circular products and services - Receive proper technical and business training in order to develop more mature circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Living Lab (Zemin İstanbul)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To host project workshops - Exhibition of products that have been produced by makers - Public awareness for project progresses and outputs

Table 17. Stakeholders identified in the city of Istanbul (continued)

User group	Role
İSMEK (Metropolitan organisation for Art and Vocational Training)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To find the disadvantaged groups for their contribution to the circular economy - Used as training centre
Citizens/residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to new circular products and services - Help identify, mobilise and connect untapped sources of knowledge and competencies that could contribute to the closing of the circular loops - Help identify and select urban areas and spaces that could benefit from DIY urbanism in the context of Pop-Machina - Up vote the most desired products and services developed by the makers and start uppers of Pop-Machina - Validate the quality, usefulness and sustainability of the circular endeavours - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Makerspaces administrators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Obtain construction and operations permits from city - Offer tools, methods and space for the operation of the maker movement - Foster the development of maker communities - Suggest best practices in circular production - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Managers of resources and materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Suggest best practices in circular production - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide scientific knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Suggest best practices in circular production - Provide applied knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy

9.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

In the table below it is described the challenges of Istanbul in the context of Pop-Machina and the potential of the project to address them.

Challenge	Pop-Machina potential
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	To collect, store and provide the relevant data and analytics based on this data
Lack of previous theoretical and applied knowledge on how to promote circular maker initiatives	To educate and train stakeholders (particularly the city, makerspace administrators and makers) on how to develop, manage initiatives related to circular endeavours
Lack of resources (financial, knowledge) for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context	To educate, train and provide the necessary means to stakeholders (particularly the city, makerspace administrators and makers) to finance initiatives, exploit results, obtain certifications and manage IPR related to circular endeavours
Unsupportive/unclear legal and regulatory framework in areas such as collaborative production, social entrepreneurship, etc.	To identify the framework conditions of those operations and make demand driven suggestions for streamlining and improvement; to use data-driven intelligence on how these conditions could be improved; to fuel the policy debate on how these conditions could be improved
Further raising of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.	To increase awareness and promote sustainable cultures and behaviours through a structured approach, driven by results
Identifying and repurposing spaces into makerspaces	To use data and grassroots knowledge to identify the appropriate spaces and repurpose them according to user needs
Supporting the commercialisation of maker products	To develop appropriate business models and business support services for the makers - entrepreneurs of Pop-Machina
Inability to document and quantify the impacts of circular and maker initiatives	To use proper (if possible real-time) monitoring mechanisms and KPIs to document the outcomes and impact of the interventions
Increase in amount of produced waste due to the growing population	In the context of circular economy, using 'waste' as raw material causes the amount of waste to decrease
Over population of immigrants/disadvantaged who are unemployed	Using this disadvantaged group as maker is a potential situation for the project

9.3 TO-BE scenario

9.3.1 Overview

The vision for İstanbul in the context of Pop-Machina is 'Use a circular neighbourhood-based approach around organic materials, nudging migrants, local citizens and SME owners in becoming circular innovators themselves.'

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in cities;
- organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers;
- trading and buying secondary raw materials;
- trading and buying circular products, certified for circularity;
- smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity;
- identifying potential collaborators in circular endeavours;
- community applications/forums;
- organising and offering training for policy makers;
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives;
- public awareness for maker movement, maker initiatives and secondary raw materials definition;
- encouragement of the secondary products usage;
- increasing the collaboration of public-makers (individual entrepreneurs).

9.3.2 Business requirements

Table 18. Business requirements of the city of Istanbul

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trading and buying secondary raw materials - Trading and buying circular products, certified for circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Makers - Citizens/residents - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - NGO's
Lack of previous applied knowledge on how to promote maker initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - İSMEK - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning
Lack of resources (financial, knowledge) for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering training for policy makers - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - İSMEK - Makers - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - NGO's
Unsupportive/unclear legal and regulatory framework in areas such as waste management, collaborative production, social entrepreneurship, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Community applications/forums - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning
Lack of awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - More interactive, real-time communication with city authorities - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Citizens/residents - NGO's
Identifying and repurposing spaces into makerspaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other cities - Community applications/forums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Makers - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - NGO's

Table 18. Business requirements of the city of Istanbul (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
Supporting the commercialisation of maker products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Makers - Living Lab (Zemin İstanbul) - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - NGO's
Inability to document and quantify the impacts of circular and maker initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - More interactive, real-time communication with city authorities - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Makers - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning
Increase in amount of produced waste due to the growing population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public awareness for maker movement, maker initiatives and secondary raw materials definition. - Encouragement of the secondary products usage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Makers - NGO's
Over population of immigrants who are unemployed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing the collaboration of public-makers (individual entrepreneurs) - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - District Municipalities - Makers - NGO's

9.4 Use cases

9.4.1 Overview

On-site Recycling Centre (Tentative-Final name and logo will be decided by Maker Team after online training which is conducted by IAAC): Recycling Workshop which currently operated by İSTAÇ, will be our İstanbul Makerspace for Pop-Machina. İSTAÇ is able to access to all types of waste (Raw material for makers) due to the fact that İSTAÇ is an environmental company which belongs to IMM. Some employees working at İSTAÇ Edirnekapı location have started recycling activities in the last one year and turned these efforts into material value. Some pictures of the current version of İSTAÇ Edirnekapı Recycling Workshop are below.

New business processes that would be desirable to be included are:

- establishing a central workshop where different stakeholders can easily participate;
- communication between experienced makers and the public within the scope of circular economy;
- providing the training and support to the maker groups;
- providing circular flow in the on-site recycling centre (Waste-Raw Material-Product-Waste);
- encouraging the maker movement in the city of Istanbul under the circular economy;
- supply of materials to the local community (plastic and wood) and incentives for reuse;
- sharing information and experience with different stakeholders;
- monitoring and statistical reporting of all data related to the studies which will be done in the on-site recycling centre;
- enabling local people to collaborate with other stakeholders.

9.4.2 Istanbul pilot use cases

Four use cases have been considered for the planned activities in Istanbul.

9.4.2.1 Use case 1: Production

The aims of this case are to bring the maker communities in Istanbul to this area, to produce circular products in this area, and to evaluate the products in the current workshop. For example, maker team teaches the specific methods to a group of 10 housewives. Those housewives who complete their education evaluate the vinyl posters coming to the workshop. Industrial bags are made with these posters and these bags can be sold. Another example is; a group of students is brought to the makerspace. After completing their education, they design and produce a modular shelf system from wood waste.

This system is used to enlarge the makerspace. Thus, activities that overlap with the definition of ‘On-Site Recycling’ are conducted.

9.4.2.2 Use case 2: Development

In this case, theoretical knowledge of İSTAC employees, who are producing there in the current situation, is planned to be developed. It is also planned that circular product networks will be increased.

Ten people working in the İSTAC recycling workshop, started these works one year ago with limited equipment and as a hobby. In the one-year period, the skills of using equipment increased, and their recognition within the company increased. Thus, they are now able to perform the restoration works in İSTAC’s different locations. This situation provided a financial gain to the company. What is planned in this scenario is to get the necessary training for the staff, to provide equipment support and to increase their personal development. Thus, these staff members will transfer their local knowledge to the project and will benefit from the global targets of the project (Win-Win).

9.4.2.3 Use case 3: Distribution

Total daily domestic waste amount of Istanbul is about 18000 tons. Unfortunately, recycling and upcycling levels are low. However, from a perspective that can turn the crisis into an opportunity, it can be said that the amount of raw material (waste) is various, excessive, and continuous. In order to contribute to the circular economy, it is planned to sell the wastes that will come to the On-site Recycling Centre to use in smaller makerspaces in different districts of the city. Thus, the intended circularity can be achieved not only at one point but in the whole city. For example, there is a makerspace in Kadıköy district that is part of the maker movement. This place wants to use waste as raw material, but it cannot access this waste in accordance with certain regulations. With this method, the desired type and amount of waste will be distributed to these spaces.

9.4.2.4 Use case 4: Experience

In this case, it is aimed to experience activities which are compatible with the purpose of the maker movement for the citizens in their daily life. It is aimed that citizens will learn concepts such as ‘maker movement’ and ‘circular economy’ at a basic level thanks to their visitation to the Makerspace Experience-Exhibition area. For example, a primary school student will be asked to bring the pet bottle of the soft drink which they consume during the day and they will be provided with a simple product from this waste. Thus, early awareness will be provided.

9.5 User requirements

Table 19. User requirements of the city of Istanbul

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URI1	Maker/Start upper	find secondary raw materials by type	I can decide if I can make a product
URI2	Maker/Start upper	find stakeholders by type	I can decide if I can find the right collaborator
URI3	Makerspace administrator	find secondary raw materials by type	I can keep my material stocks updated
URI4	District municipality	have an overview of the overall material flow	I can track the record of primary and secondary materials in the eco-system
URI5	Manager of resources and materials	have an overview of the missing materials	I can take care of procuring them
URI6	Citizen	see what circular products are available	I can buy them
URI7	NGO	find stakeholder by type	I can decide if I can find the right collaborator
URI8	Social Cooperative	find stakeholder by type	I can decide if I can find the right collaborator
URI9	Local governmental authority	find existing makerspaces according to their performance in making	I can select best practices
URI10	District municipality	find existing makerspaces according to their performance in making	I can select best practices
URI11	Local training centre (ISMEK)	find existing makerspaces according to their expertise type	I can allocate my resources according to the expertise type required by 'to be makerspaces'
URI12	Makerspace administrator	find existing business and training programmes	I can direct my employees to these programmes
URI13	Practitioner and researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find makerspaces that need training and business support in the circular economy	I can find stakeholders to which I can give training on circular economy
URI14	Local governmental authority	find stakeholders having expertise in smart contracting	I can build new smart contract templates for makers and other initiatives
URI15	District municipality	find stakeholders having expertise in smart contracting	I can build new smart contract templates for makers and other initiatives
URI16	Local training centre (ISMEK)	find makerspaces that need training and business support in material procurement	I can match them with stakeholders that can provide that training
URI17	Maker	exchange services with stakeholders providing raw materials	I can build a product
URI18	Makerspace administrator	exchange services with stakeholders providing raw materials	I can keep my materials stock updated
URI19	Manager of resources and materials	know about the overall material flow in the eco-system	I can provide the stakeholders with raw materials if needed

Table 19. User requirements of the city of Istanbul (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URI20	Practitioner and researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find makerspaces that need training and business support in material procurement	I can match them with stakeholders that can provide that training
URI21	Social Cooperative	exchange services with stakeholders providing raw materials	I can trade my products
URI22	Local governmental authority	find clear and valid legal and regulatory framework in waste management, collaborative production, social entrepreneurship	I can tailor these frameworks to the needs of the local maker ecosystem
URI23	District municipality	quantify the environmental and economic gains achieved by circular makers in the city scale	I can better tailor exemplar frameworks to the local context
URI24	Practitioner and researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find governmental stakeholders that still does not have a clear legal and regulatory framework	I can collaborate with them to create new frameworks
URI25	Local governmental authority	find places where recycling efforts by citizens are low	I can create new communication campaigns to raise awareness
URI26	District municipality	find NGOs, circular makerspaces and professionals having expertise in circular economy	I can collaboratively create training programmes
URI27	Citizen/resident	find circular maker initiatives	I can learn about and practice reuse, repair, recycle and repurpose
URI28	NGO	find successful communication campaigns for raising awareness in recycling, reusing and repurposing	I can create new communication campaigns to raise awareness
URI29	Local governmental authority	find idle spaces in the city	I can turn them into makerspaces
URI30	District municipality	find stakeholders having expertise in building and managing a makerspace	I can build new makerspaces
URI31	District municipality	find practices that shows a successful account of a spaces' transition into makerspace	I can learn more about making such a transition at the local context
URI32	Maker	find newly established makers spaces	I can provide them with training on making
URI33	Makerspace administrator	find newly established makers spaces	I can provide them with training on managing a makerspace
URI34	Practitioner and researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find newly established makerspaces	I can provide them with training on circular economy and sustainability
URI35	NGO	find citizens/residents who might be interested in building a makerspace	I can direct their interest towards collaboratively creating a makerspace
URI36	Maker/Start upper	find venues that I can exhibit my product	I can sell my product to a wider audience
URI37	Makerspace administrator	find stakeholders that offer training services for developing smart contracts for trading circular products	I can train my employees

Table 19. User requirements of the city of Istanbul (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URI38	Manager of resources and materials	find stakeholders that can upcycle/downcycle waste resources	I can provide them with the material collected
URI39	NGO	find stakeholders having expertise in developing smart contracts for circular products, and the ones have already commercialised several circular products	I can develop a training programme on smart contracts for commercialisation
URI40	Local governmental authority	find circular maker communities who produced/or are going to produce circular products	I can ask for data in relation to impact on city's economy, social structure and environment
URI41	District Municipality	find circular maker communities who produced/or are going to produce circular products	I can ask for data in relation to impact on district's economy, social structure and environment
URI42	Maker/Start upper	find stakeholders who are in charge of quantifying the impact of circular-maker initiative and products	I can provide my own data to the system
URI43	Professional and researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find circular maker communities who produced circular products	I can assess and quantify their impact
URI44	Local governmental authority	find places (districts) produced high amount of waste	I can better manage the circulation of wasted resources (as an alternative to raw materials) at the city scale
URI45	District Municipality	find places (districts) produced high amount of waste	I can better manage the circulation of wasted resources (as an alternative to raw materials) at the district scale
URI46	Maker	find places in which I can obtain waste	I can use this waste as a secondary material to build a new product
URI47	NGO	create communication campaigns to raise awareness, and tailor these campaigns to the needs of residents	I can promote good practices and raise awareness on waste, reuse, repair and refurbish
URI48	Local governmental authority	find makerspaces that has previously worked on projects in relation to social inclusion, empowerment	I can support these makers spaces in their future projects focusing on migration, empowerment and social inclusion
URI49	District Municipalities	find makerspaces having close proximity to places where migrant population is high	I can facilitate the participation of immigrants into the maker movement at regional scale
URI50	Maker	identify migrant (or disadvantaged) groups having skills related to circular economy and makers	I can collaborate with them in one my ongoing projects (e.g. designing a tent for refugee camps)
URI51	NGO	identify places in which migrant population is high	I can design communication campaigns to raise their awareness on making

10. City of Kaunas

10.1 Introduction

Kaunas is the second largest city in Lithuania with 286,763 (2019) inhabitants and is located in the centre of Lithuania at the crossroads of major international road and rail links. Kaunas is a large centre of business and industry with convenient location and strong logistics capacity. For business and investors, the city offers friendly, open, and creative space for partnerships and cooperation.

Kaunas city is an active partner in the Urban Agenda for the EU circular economy Partnership. Cities play an essential role in the development of a circular economy; they act as enablers of potential measures by which they can influence both consumers and businesses. In order to develop the concept of a circular economy within cities, there are other themes that cannot be overlooked, such as overall governance, enabling businesses, public procurement, consumption and resource management. The Partnership on circular economy has investigated the whole circle, beginning with the extraction of raw materials to design, production, transportation, consumption and, finally, the recycling of waste with residues for final disposal. By choosing the themes mentioned above, the Partnership on circular economy covers most of the relevant circular economy aspects from a city perspective. The Partnership on circular economy has not elaborated an overall plan for introducing the circular economy at a city-level but has rather focused on specific actions and recommendations that would fit into already existing plans for most cities.

The city's developed vision for Kaunas for the year 2022 defined in the Kaunas city 2016-2022 strategic development plan, states: 'Kaunas - sustainable and civic city, leader in advanced business and innovations, centre of modern and engaging culture, home for continuously learning and happy people'. Kaunas City municipality has developed a strong project management team responsible for implementing new approaches in sustainable development projects and transiting towards a Circular city. Local level institutions have large scope of responsibilities therefore the municipality has experience in various sustainable development projects as well as projects related to social inclusion, infrastructure, cultural heritage, tourism, sustainable traffic, etc. In the framework of Pop-Machina, we seek to increase the awareness and importance of circular economy and circular consumption, to promote circular maker communities, to raise residents' interest in recycling and reusing, to get applied knowledge on how to promote circular initiatives and support its commercialisation.

10.2 Current situation

10.2.1 Overview

Kaunas City intention is to work towards increasing citizens' participation in circular economy by creating a makerspace and empowering them to commercialise their ideas. Either one of the municipality's buildings or other premises will be converted into a makerspace for:

- experiments and small-scale production;
- co-working;
- common projects and activities, public events, trainings.

The selected premises will be adapted to the needs of the community that will be working there, to purchase necessary equipment based on the needs of people working in the makerspace. Kaunas city in the framework of Pop-Machina expects to:

- experiment with innovative solutions;
- share best practices with other cities and organisations;
- find actions and tools that could be implemented in Kaunas city.

Ongoing initiatives:

- initiation of cooperation between local manufacturers and retailers or citizen-led initiatives as a good way to promote more durable, repairable and recyclable products. (Ongoing programme: <http://Iniciatyvos.kaunas.lt>);
- green Public Procurement and Public Procurement of Innovation with criteria developed by public authorities can ensure the sustainability, durability and reparability when setting out or revising criteria. (Green public procurement requirements for city administration);
- integrated waste management. Problematic flows: packaging waste, food waste, promoting of tools for waste prevention (minimisation) and growing rate of reuse/recycling. (Responsible: www.kaunoratc.lt);
- promotion of a collaborative economy which shares products or infrastructure would see citizens and businesses consuming services rather than products. (Car or bike sharing projects CityBee, Project 'Like Bike', etc.);

10.2.2 Current business process models

Kaunas City Municipality Strategic Development Plan until 2022 identifies three priority areas: Economic development promotion, Education of smart and civil society, Sustainable territorial and infrastructure development.

In order to evaluate efficiency of the current circular economy measures applied in Kaunas, a system of indicators for the circular economy and a model for measuring the efficiency of cities was developed and implemented. Kaunas City Inventory analysis of municipal data and indicators was performed on three programmes covering all areas of the city:

Economic Development Programme: 4 of 69 indicators from this programme are related to the circular economy.

According to the circular economy indicator system, it belongs to the category of renovation of public spaces and the annual renovation of public spaces and buildings.

Smart and civil society education programme: 9 out of 398 indicators related to the circular economy.

The circular economy Indicator System is a public space renovation category, the indicator is public space and buildings renovated annually and the local government support category, the indicator is population promotion and participation in circular economy activities.

Sustainable Spatial and Infrastructure Development Programme: 13 of the 118 indicators are related to the circular economy.

The circular economy Indicator System comprises various indicators of different categories such as (i) indicators of the proportion of the waste generation, covered by the waste sorting system, compared to the total amount of waste collected (waste generation category), (ii) indicators of reconstructed and newly constructed water supply and wastewater collection networks (water-use category), (iii) indicators of air quality (category of emissions into air), (iv) indicators of collected and recycled waste (waste-recycling category), (v) an indicator of the annual efficiency of the recycling of

solid urban waste and (vi) an indicator of the annual number of parks renewed (public space renovation category).

10.2.3 Stakeholders' identification

There is a lack of knowledge by public authorities about potential initiatives and instruments that can support better consumption and waste prevention. This might also be related to a lack of engagement of decision makers and therefore there is a need to raise awareness of elected representatives at Kaunas city level about the benefits of waste prevention and sustainable production and consumption models, in terms of environmental, social and economic impact.

There is a lack (or perceived lack) of circular alternatives on the market in Kaunas. This again generates a lack of demand of the already existing products and services. In addition to this the information and knowledge related to repair and reuse services in the city might be limited. For people to use circular services and products, they need to be convenient and accessible.

Furthermore, the city government might lack knowledge and overview over existing initiatives and services related to waste prevention activities. There is a need for a mapping of the circular initiatives and stakeholders in Kaunas city and exchange of best practices and lessons learned by all levels of government and stakeholders. Kaunas city municipality might play an important role as facilitator for this process. Kaunas could contribute to a general perception change for second-hand goods and to demonstrating tangible benefits of circular characteristics. Also, Kaunas could contribute to networking and matching supply and demand, for example, digital platforms for repairing services or sharing goods providing authentication and certification.

On the supply side, a lack of knowledge can equally be observed. Manufacturers in Kaunas as well as intermediaries, especially small medium enterprises (SMEs), should be founded and be provided with access to new technologies of production and to research and innovation.

The user groups that interact for purposes relevant to the project:

Table 20. Stakeholders identified in the city of Kaunas

User group	Role
Local governmental authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen the development of maker communities - Define legal framework and roadmap for stakeholders - Establish the link between manufacturers, NGOs, Maker movement communities - Participate in the circular economy policy debate
Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect to making and circular production - Connect with other makers and communities to exchange ideas, collaborate in new product/service development - Develop circular products and services - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy
Makerspaces administrators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Obtain operations permits from city - Offer tools, methods and space for the operation of the maker movement - Foster the development of maker communities
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide scientific knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning - Participate in the policy debate for circular economy, engage in joint projects
NGO's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express their needs and requirements with respect the operation of their business - Provide and trade primary and secondary material resources that will be used for circular production - Experiment with circular products and services - Share applied knowledge and know-how with respect to sustainable production, development and planning
Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Express the needs with respect to new circular products and services - Involve into circular activities - Create circular economy-based start-ups

10.2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

Kaunas is characterised by many stakeholders engaged in a multitude of activities and exhibiting a different degree of circular potential.

A city is led and managed by many public entities that apply different strategies, plans and resources to govern and develop the activities under their responsibility. This may lead to so-called silo thinking, where different departments and entities have their own priorities which hamper the need for circular integration required to succeed. The transition to a circular economy could benefit from introducing more circular thinking into such activities, and tools and platforms that facilitate such thinking and exchange of views between different stakeholders.

However, a successful transition of Kaunas to a circular economy requires not only a top-down approach instigated by public authorities, but also the identification and application of new ways of voluntary (formal and informal) cooperation between public authorities and other local circular stakeholders such as citizens, businesses (commerce and industry), media, academia, educational institutions and organisations of civil society (NGOs). The large number of different stakeholders, and the individual interests and interactions among them makes circular governance in the city quite complex.

Urban resource management starts with understanding a city's metabolism. This means (1) identifying and understanding material stocks and flows within the city. Furthermore, cities need to know (2) the turnover speed of the resource flows. These may differ, depending on the type of resource. For example, materials used for building or infrastructure have a slower turnover speed than consumer goods or food. Also the stakeholders involved can be different. If the stakeholders per stream are identified, the relevant and applicable policies and legislation can be addressed.

Increasing our knowledge of material flows within cities and promoting the use of secondary resources in the process of value creation are not enough. There are several bottlenecks to be dealt with to further enhance the business case of urban resource management.

Regulations	Knowledge	Funding
Markets for secondary raw materials do not function sufficiently in order to substitute primary raw materials. Financial and regulatory incentives (for example linked to EPR-schemes and tax shifts) are needed to correct this and accelerate the transition towards a circular economy.	Resource mapping generally has a strong focus on the supply side. For urban resource management to be successful more insight into the demand for secondary raw materials is essential.	As a general rule waste management is cost-oriented while resource management is benefit-oriented. In the present situation this can lead to secondary raw materials not being used, because costs of preparation for re-use and recycling are too high and it is cheaper to use virgin raw materials.
As soon as a product or material is defined as waste, a set of regulations apply that aim at protecting public health and the environment. These regulations make it difficult (if not impossible) to redirect waste back into the economy as secondary raw materials. This calls for adaptations of (the applicability of) waste legislation to better fit the circular economy.	The lower we descend the value hill in the post-use phase, the more complex the 'mining' of secondary raw materials becomes. This is especially true for non-separated household waste. As a consequence, a lot of resources are used and recycled at low levels of circularity. More focus on 'mining' at source higher up the value chain could help tackle this, provided that the right incentives are in place.	Funding for planning and development of urban circular business parks.
	Availability and reliability of mapping data is a problem. Redirection, exchange and processing of material flows between stakeholders will not be adequate without detailed data from businesses and other stakeholders.	
	Most stakeholders are poorly adapted to principles of resource management (as opposed to waste management) at the end of production- and value chains.	
	The actual redirection and exchange of material flows between stakeholders is case and time sensitive and can be facilitated through (intermediate) treatment and storage facilities.	

Challenges:

- lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem;
- lack of applied knowledge on how to promote circular initiatives;
- further raising awareness/interest by citizens in recycling, reusing, repurposing, etc.;
- supporting the commercialisation of maker's activities;
- expand the amount and the quality of makers' activities;
- sustainable integration of Maker's movement in the society.

Pop-Machina possibilities:

- to collect, store and provide the relevant data and analytics based on this data;
- to educate and train stakeholders on how to develop, manage initiatives and commercialise the ideas;
- to increase awareness and promote sustainable activities and behaviours through a structured approach, driven by results;
- to develop appropriate business support services;
- to provide makers with required equipment;
- to develop new sustainable products that meet the needs and interests of citizens;
- Pop-Machina gathers knowledge about how to connect sustainable and circular activities.

10.3 TO-BE scenario

10.3.1 Overview

Resource efficiency is an important aspect of circular economy. One way of addressing this issue is through re-use and recycling of waste materials. Given the substantial flows of waste materials that cities produce, developing concepts of urban resource management can greatly contribute to the circular economy. There are already several interesting practices available from which several issues on knowledge, regulation and funding arise that need to be addressed. The most important are:

- knowledge about a city's metabolism;
- knowledge (and interest) of local stakeholders (mainly SME's);
- functioning of markets for secondary raw materials in terms of supply and demand (knowing what is available, how, where and when);
- financial support mechanisms like circular tax shift;
- regulations not fit for purpose (especially waste regulations).

Central to the theme circular economy is consumption. Development of more sustainable consumption patterns among citizens of Kaunas is a huge opportunity to move the economy in a circular direction. City is able to help, motivate, nudge or push their citizens in this direction. City may also identify measures and regulations that are hindering a smoother transition into a greener consumption and a circular economy.

The choices made by citizens could either support or hamper cities transition to a more circular economy. Consumer of Kaunas choices are shaped by the access to information, physical space, the range and prices of existing products, the regulatory framework and how consumption is organised. Kaunas should aim to facilitate for their citizens, so that they more easily make choices that fuel the demand for better/smarter/circular goods and services to reduce waste and promote more sustainable consumption patterns.

An important part of waste prevention and circular consumption is encouraging and promoting Eco-Design. Eco-Design can contribute to the decoupling of economic growth from resource consumption through a decreased use of materials and energy, higher recycling rates and reduced waste generation. An important aspect of the circular economy is the increased consumption of goods produced with more secondary resources. Meaning energy- and resource efficient goods and goods made from recycled materials that have a long durability and can easily be fixed and goods designed for disassembly for remanufacturing, which are safe and can be taken apart and recycled easily.

From an economic point of view, eco-design can reduce production costs leading to increased purchasing power for consumers, job creation and increased welfare by using secondary resources as input to the production.

Kaunas City vision in the context of Pop-Machina is to increase citizens' participation in circular economy by creating a makerspace and empowering maker communities to commercialise their ideas of Eco-design products:

- achieving detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem;
- achieving information for supporting the commercialisation of circular activities;
- achieving applied knowledge on how to promote circular initiatives;
- finding strategic and tactical solutions for encouraging young people to create circular economy-based start-ups;
- identifying best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places;
- accessing the practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development (environmental scientists, urban planners, lawyers, IT policy makers, etc.);

- organising and offering training and business support sessions for community makers;
- identifying potential collaborators in circular makers;
- organising and offering training for policy makers;
- documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives;
- public awareness for community maker movement and maker initiatives.

10.3.2 Business requirements

Table 21. Business requirements of the city of Kaunas

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of information about available circular services and products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping relevant information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Citizens/residents - Entrepreneurs - Managers of resources and materials
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insufficient funding in infrastructure that enables the waste management industry to sort and store products for reuse or repair - Markets for secondary raw materials do not function sufficiently in order to substitute primary raw materials - Financial and regulatory incentives (for example linked to EPR-schemes and tax shifts) are needed to correct this and accelerate the transition towards a circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trading and buying secondary raw materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens/residents - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Social Cooperatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most stakeholders are poorly adapted to principles of resource management (as opposed to waste management) at the end of production- and value chains. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning open knowledge module - Sustainable
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As soon as a product or material is defined as waste, a set of regulations apply that aim at protecting public health and the environment. These regulations make it difficult (if not impossible) to redirect waste back into the economy as secondary raw materials. This calls for adaptations of (the applicability of) waste legislation to better fit the circular economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Access to scientific resources, best practices and practical guides for professionals in the sustainable development domain (environmental scientists, urban planners, IT policy makers, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - Local governmental authorities - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives

Table 21. Business requirements of the city of Kaunas (continued)

Problem/challenge/vision	Business process	Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of knowledge among consumers on the treatment and usage of re-useable electronic devises - Lack of knowledge among consumers about consumer guarantees and consumer rights - Lack of knowledge about labelling among consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - More interactive, real-time communication with city authorities - Documentation and quantification of impact of circular and maker initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Citizens/residents - Social Cooperatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Insufficient funding in infrastructure that enables the waste management industry to sort and store products for reuse or repair - Funding to support new business initiatives emphasising new consumption models - Funding for competence building on repair of electronic devices (ref. Restarters, repair movement) - Funding for footprint analysis and how to distribute information about these – e.g. by using digital methods as consumer Apps to get information about a product 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Social Cooperatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of knowledge within local authorities on how to address waste prevention - Lack of resources (financial, knowledge) for procuring services and raw materials in the maker economy context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contracts for trading and certifying circularity - Organising and offering training for policy makers - Organising and offering online and offline, synchronous and asynchronous training and business support sessions for makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production, development and planning - Social Cooperatives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable integration of Maker Movers' population in the society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community applications/forums - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - Professionals and researchers for sustainable production and professionals and researchers for social matters
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The lack of better-educated inhabitants is hampering the development of maker's spaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filtering to best practices and successful ideas implemented in other places - Organising training for groups of interested 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local government - Knowledge partners - Start uppers - Makerspaces administrators - Professionals

10.4 Use cases

10.4.1 Overview

Kaunas Circular makerspace will be focusing on the circular economy concepts and working on improving them and bringing knowledge about it to the community, creating environment for local community to use equipment to innovate and fulfil their ideas. Big part of the activities will focus on

working with initiatives like 'Precious plastics', on educating and learning about sustainable living and eco-design of the products, on returning materials back to the supply chain, and on creating new things from leftover or used materials. The makerspace will have variety of fabrication tools and machines to bring ideas into life.

Another part of the circular makerspace is going to be dedicated for gatherings and small workshops, for university classes, or independent stakeholders to hold training sessions, hackathons and similar activities. The makerspace will be equipped with multimedia and transformable furniture to work in one big group or separate into smaller groups.

It is situated in the campus of the university of technology of Kaunas, not far from the mechanical engineering and design faculty as well as the living dorms of the students. Focus will be on building a makers' community, on collaborating with other makers and creators-oriented organisations, and on building new connections with companies around the city.

10.4.2 Kaunas pilot use cases

10.4.2.1 Use case 1: Daily basis

The circular makerspace will be open to the citizens especially to the students due to the location of the space. Students and citizens who want to spend their time prototyping and making things themselves will be able to use the premises and thus, they will be introduced to the Pop-Machina community. It will be possible to check online the availability of particular equipment or a relevant makerspace.

If someone wants to work on a specific field or type of technology and there is no specialist on the premises, help will be provided for reaching experts on the field. Considering the experience of the maker and the complexity of the equipment, they will be instructed on how to use the equipment or how to use a 'buddy system' to get help from persons working in the makerspace.

10.4.2.2 Use case 2: Events, hackathons, workshops

The circular makerspace dedicated for gatherings will be used for hackathons, small workshops, or lessons that will focus on teamwork, brainstorming and socialising. An appropriate space with transformable furniture will allow working in large or small groups, while enabling the exploitation of the necessary. In the makerspace a multimedia system will be used for presentations and other relevant activities.

10.4.2.3 Use case 3: Training

People, who are interested in technologies and want to learn how to use 3D printers, laser cutters or plastic injection machines, etc., will be invited to trainings/lectures to understand how technology works, what are the main strengths, weaknesses and usages of various technologies, and what the future brings in that field.

While focusing on the specific makers' projects, talks and presentations will show what has to be taken into account, when designing and prototyping an idea in computer programmes, so that makers can be prepared for the manufacturing phase. Questions will be answered and solutions to problems will be suggested, allowing makers to troubleshoot obstacles or problematic circumstances while using specific equipment.

10.5 User requirements

Table 22. User requirements of the city of Venlo

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URK1	Local governmental authority	provide citizens and makers a functionality to communicate, discuss, change information with each other via platform	by exchanging their experience, knowledge and ideas they become more professional and encouraged to become makers or develop their activities
URK2	Local governmental authority	to collect contacts of makers or citizens who potentially could become makers, and have a possibility to contact them; to collect information about their interests and needs	by having relevant information about their interests and needs and contacting them, to implement targeted communication, so that more citizens would be encouraged to participate and involved in the maker movement
URK3	Local governmental authority	have a bank of ideas, knowledge and best practices	more citizens and makers would be encouraged to create various circular products or to develop their current activities
URK4	Local governmental authority	have an overview of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	can make decisions about extension of makerspaces, make decisions about involving new partners
URK5	Local governmental authority	place information about regulatory conditions and to provide possibility for makers and citizens report about regulatory shortcomings onto a platform, make suggestions on how to improve	regulation would be closer to practical makers' needs and encouraging maker movements
URK6	Local governmental authority	create a possibility for makers to find like-minded makers and partners for collaboration	scope and impact of maker movement could grow
URK7	Maker	provide citizens and makers a functionality to communicate, discuss, change information with each other via platform	by exchanging their experience, knowledge and ideas they become more professional and encouraged to become makers or develop their activities.
URK8	Maker	have knowledge of tools to promote circular initiatives and commercialise them	I can expand circular initiatives
URK10	Maker	search for secondary raw materials by type	decide if I can make a product
URK11	Maker	get training/education	I can better use the equipment, improve my products and processes, I gain knowledge on how to promote my materials and commercialise my ideas
URK12	Maker	be able to contact and interact with actors of the makers' ecosystem	I can network with them and achieve cooperation to study and research circular product and service development, resource management
URK13	Makerspace administrator	be able to upload educational resources	makers can access and be educated about processes and best practices

Table 22. User requirements of the city of Venlo (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URK14	Makerspace administrator	provide information about possibilities to get funding, how to attract investors, where to get consultations, seminars (how to create sustainable business, how to manage small enterprise, how to promote created products, etc.)	makers' small enterprises could gain relevant information for sustainable growth
URK15	Makerspace administrator	provide the opportunity to makers to showcase their products	they stand a better chance to access consumers
URK16	Researcher	have an overview of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	I know what additional work is needed to create a network of maker's interfaces that covers the entire network
URK17	Researcher	contribute with educational content	in order to support the circular movement
URK18	Start upper	provide a list with makers and information about their circular products	investors could easily find interesting projects for them and other citizens or makers could easily find desired partners or employers
URK19	Citizen	see what circular products are available, participate in a production process	to buy them, develop them and earn how to sell them, be part of a wider environmental friendly movement

11. Academic user requirements

This section presents the work of academic and technical partners of Pop-Machina to record additional user requirements to those of the pilot cities. These requirements reflect the research perspective of Pop-Machina, and at the same time they lay the ground for defining Pop-Machina KPIs and the method of their computation.

Table 23. User requirements defined by academic partners

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URAtud1	Urban planner	view geographical locations of makerspaces and their support network (funding partners and material provision partners) on a map	I can gain understanding on whether location of makerspaces are affected by proximity to other partners, centrality, accessibility ..., etc.
URAtud2	Urban planner	export geographical locations of makerspaces and their support network in shapefile format or other formats compatible with GIS (Geographical information systems)	I can gain understanding on whether location of makerspaces are affected by proximity to others partners, centrality, accessibility ..., etc.
URAtud3	Industrial ecologist	know what type of materials/products are being sourced at each makerspace? (e.g. Plastic, textile, bikes, bricks)	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud4	Industrial ecologist	know where do these materials come from?	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud5	Industrial ecologist	know how much do these materials weigh?	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud6	Industrial ecologist	know what type of production equipment was used	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud7	Industrial ecologist	know what type of production processes were used	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud8	Industrial ecologist	know the name of person/organisation that bought finished product from makers and their composition materials	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud9	Industrial ecologist	know what is the \$\$ value of the finished product?	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud10	Industrial ecologist	know what were the waste materials in the production process?	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAtud11	Industrial ecologist	know where did these waste materials go? (land fill? Reused? Sold to other makerspaces?)	I can perform spatial material flow analysis of network of makerspaces
URAkul1	Academic researcher	search for materials stocks and flows by type	I can document on the material stocks and flows
URAkul2	Academic researcher	have information on materials by types, quantities (weight, surface, volume), price	I can analysis material flow
URAkul3	Academic researcher	see what circular initiatives and maker initiatives are available (coding workshops, drop off point for raw material, open source library, etc.)	I can map the initiatives
URAkul4	Academic researcher	identify the location of the different stakeholder	I can map the initiatives
URAkul5	Academic researcher	have an overview of the different stakeholder in the maker movement and the circular economy (who is who)	I can map good practices in Circular maker movement
URAkul6	Academic researcher	identify exchange among stakeholders (who exchanged what with who)	I can map the ecosystem of the circular maker movement
URAkul7	Academic researcher	track materials from their entrance in the supply chain until their 'end-of-life management'	I can conduct Life Cycle analysis (LCA) of products to see whether circular makers extend product life

Table 23. User requirements defined by academic partners (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URAkul8	Academic researcher	see the traffic by material/structure	I can identify what are the main interests (focus) of the circular maker movement
URAkul9	Academic researcher	find partners (academic and other) to set up new research projects with (related to the MM)	I can efficiently write new proposals
URAkul10	Academic researcher	find MM initiatives (incl. Contact details) for case studies or interviews.	I can study the MM more efficiently
URAkul11	Academic/researcher	download the full database on the MM in a convenient, editable file format (e.g. Csv file) + parts of it using filters	I can analyse (part of) the maker movement as part of my academic research
URAkul12	Academic/researcher	know the amount of the yearly/monthly/daily secondary material consumption, waste production (different flow of waste), energy (electricity consumption), gas consumption, water consumption, during the last 3(?) Years in each pilot city for each individuals/households	I can evaluate the consumption of resource, the improvement in between groups of users, and for each city gather data at individual nut also at city level to compute KPIs 1, 2 and 3
URAkul13	Individuals/households	enter and follow my (daily/monthly/yearly) secondary material consumption, waste production (different flow of waste), energy (electricity consumption), gas consumption, water consumption	I can check my consumption and see any evolution
URAkul14	Academic/researcher	see how many users use the platform by day/month year and track their location and their profile (individuals, makers, policy maker, academics, etc.)	I can know where the network of interest come from and how people form the Pop-Machina network of interest (KPIs 13)
URAkul15	Academic/researcher	see how many users entered sensor data in the platform	I can identify the Number of community members engaged as sensors in pilots (KPI6)
URAkul16	Academic/researcher	see how many users participate in the co-creation development of ICT tools for or in the platform	I can identify the number of Makers involved in the co-creation of ICT tools (KPI 23)
URAIM1	Researcher	to have a possibility to change descriptions and photos of circular products which are sold on online-shop of Pop-Machina platform, and track sales statistics	by collecting data and measuring how consumer behaviour changes we could create the most effective selling practice of circular products
URAIM2	Researcher	to have a possibility on the online shop (next to the product) to add and change various descriptions about makers and makerspaces, where the product was produced	by collecting data and measuring how consumer behaviour changes we could create the most effective selling practice of circular products
URAIM3	Researcher	platform to have 'like' and comment functions next to each product sold	there would be a possibility to collect data about circular product 'likes' and preferences
URAIM4	Researcher	to collect data about platform visitors (potential customers) activities ('liking', viewing, commenting, buying)	we could analyse their preferences

Table 23. User requirements defined by academic partners (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URAIsm5	Researcher	to have a possibility to give for online-shop's visitors (who viewed, liked, commented or bought circular products), questionnaires to answer	we could measure some of their personality traits by using scales and to analyse information about targeted customers.
URAIsm6	Researcher	to create a possibility for makers/makerspaces to declare what disposed waste/used products as materials do they need for remodelling and/or repurposing	citizens could purposefully give away waste or used goods for exact maker/makerspace instead of throwing them away.
URAIsm7	Researcher	to get data about the amount of citizens' given away waste/used products for makers and makerspaces and the purpose of it (did they give away without any expectations, because of their sustainability beliefs; did they give products, so that exact maker would sell them back remodelled or repurposed; etc.)	makers could get additional source to get materials and by analysing this statistical data, find ways to encourage citizens to give away instead of throwing away.
URAIaw1	Researcher	use data on secondary material consumption and circular services in each pilot city	I can conclude if the applicable regulation can impact the advancement of Makers movement
URAIaw2	Researcher	know the type of waste to be used as secondary material in each makerspace	to understand the safety hazards that users may encounter
URAIaw3	Researcher	be able to see a graph comparing secondary material consumption in the past/at the start /in progress of Pop-Machina pilot run (baseline May 2020?)	I can address KPI-12 on the municipal governance of circularity
URAIaw4	Researcher	use data collected on users' digital skills and knowledge as well as on the blockchain infrastructure of pilot cities (baseline July 2020?)	I can address KPI-12 and the capacity of the pilot cities on digital collaboration and social innovation (DSI)
URAIaw5	Researcher	use data collected on business expectations of makers (baseline July 2020?)	I can address KPI-12 on legal drivers and barriers
URAIaw6	Researcher	have data declared on the municipal infrastructure of makerspaces, specifications of users' knowledge, skills, equipment, materials and potential products (baseline July 2020?)	I can address KPI-12 on users OHS skillsets and safety operational licenses for makerspaces
URAIaw7	Researcher	use data on the participation of women or people with disabilities, as makers in pilot cities (baseline July 2020?)	I can compute KPI-10 on socioeconomic progress factors (diversity and inclusion)
URAIaw8	Researcher	share the D2.4 Report on European and national regulatory framework conditions	users can be advised on (governance, legal and tax) enablers and barriers of making
URAIaw9	Researcher	Know the actual makerspace storage capacity under the auspices of the pilot cities	To understand the volume of exchanged flows among users
URAIaw10	Researcher	know the Pop-Machina currency or utility value of tokens and the volume of transactions	to advise if an E/U digital sales tax applies or if is tax free

Table 23. User requirements defined by academic partners (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URAlaw11	Researcher	know what is the monetary value of the raw material and of the finished product	to monitor possible income and tax implications for the users of the makerspace or of the social collaboration platform
URAlaw12	Researcher	know the number of attendants at the 'warm up' events	I have feedback on engagement methodologies
URAlaw13	Researcher	know the number of makers engaged in the co-creation of monitoring plans per pilot city (from May 2020-Dec. 2020)	I can compute the baseline value of KPI15 on the number of engaged maker (KPI15)
URAlaw14	Researcher	know the number of community sensors involved in the co-creation of monitoring plans per pilot city (from May 2020-Dec. 2020)	I can compute the baseline number of the sensors' ecosystem (KPI16)
URAlaw15	Researcher	see how cities promote events or actions related with circular economy	I can measure the engagement of the community around the makers movement
URAlaw16	Researcher	advise on the legal requirements of company, tax law and of digital social innovation skills	users elect to engage in creativity or business entrepreneurship schemes
URAkoc1	Academic researcher	view stakeholder locations at the European level	make comparisons between cities in terms of geographical distribution
URAkoc2	Academic researcher	view stakeholder locations at a city level	make comparisons between different regions of the city in terms of stakeholder distribution
URAkoc3	Academic researcher	view stakeholder locations at a district level.	reach out local stakeholders for further inquiries (e.g. setting up meetings, conducting interviews,)
URAkoc4	Academic researcher	find initiatives according to Pop-Machina project categorisations of stakeholder type, visions, and skills	sort and compare them in relation to their skills and capabilities (e.g. available services, spaces, tools)
URAkoc5	Academic researcher	view stakeholders on a grid like diagram view	sort and compare them in relation to their skills and capabilities (e.g. available services, spaces, tools)
URAkoc6	Academic researcher	view list of activities designed and implemented by the City Pilots	explore and implement relevant activities
URAkoc7	Academic researcher	view ongoing Pop-Machina activities and events in the city on a map	explore and participate in relevant activities
URAkoc8	Academic researcher	explore and download Open Knowledge related to city-level circular economy and distributed production	to have access to metrics relevant to me and to develop educational content
URAkoc9	Researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find makerspaces that need training and business support in the circular economy	I can find stakeholders to which I can give training on circular economy and sustainability
URAkoc10	Researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find circular maker communities who produced circular products	I can collaborate with them to write new research proposals

Table 23. User requirements defined by academic partners (continued)

Req. ID	As a ...	I want to ...	So that ...
URAkoc1 1	Researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find governmental stakeholders that still does not have a clear legal and regulatory framework on circular making	I can collaborate with them to create new frameworks
URAkoc1 2	Researcher for sustainable production, development and planning	find circular maker communities who produced circular products	I can assess and quantify their impact
URAiacc1	Academy trainer	see learning analytics of each participant (student) of the Academy. It means number of interventions, time spent in the Academy (training content, materials...), self-assessment results and open knowledge contribution.	I can conclude and get evidences of the skills and competences developed by the student. It also can compute to KPI-22
URAiacc2	Academic researcher	know the most consulted education material on the platform	I can conclude which has more impact in a circular maker community. It also can compute to KP-19
URAiacc3	Maker	be able to re-mix (adapt, modify) and existing education material on the platform	I can contribute to the open knowledge platform.
URAiacc4	Maker	be able to update a new educational material validated by the community	I can contribute with knowledge to the community
URAiacc5	Maker	be able to have a public space in the platform	I can use it to document and share my projects/products
URAiacc6	Maker	get recognition for my contribution to the platform	I can have benefits in PM makerspaces
URAiacc7	Academic researcher	be able to download the interactions of all participants (data) in the open education module platform	I can measure the impact of the educational material

12. System requirements

12.1 Social collaboration platform

The social collaboration module (SCP) will be the core of the system. It will support all making processes realised by Pop-Machina actors, constituting the main monitoring mechanism of materials used and products made. Since SCP is going to be the basis of all Pop-Machina transactions, it will encompass the blockchain and tokenisation mechanisms for certification and attribution of products' and processes' value. SCP will also enable Pop-Machina actors to find stakeholders, makerspaces and communities relevant with their projects and interests. Data from all actions supported by the SCP will also be exposed to the data collection and analytics tool for further analysis and sophisticated presentation to the end users.

12.1.1 SCP functional requirements

The following table lists the functional requirements of the social collaboration platform. They reflect all the functionalities that must be supported by SCP, so that the relevant user requirements are satisfied. They are grouped in categories and they are assigned a unique identifier for reference. The corresponding user requirements of the pilot cities or the academic partners are also listed in the last column of the table.

Table 24. Functional requirements of the social collaboration platform

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
User management	SR_SCP1	SCP must give the ability to add/edit/view a stakeholder	URL5, URL6
	SR_SCP2	SCP must give the ability to the administrator to give different permissions to different stakeholders	URL5, URL6
	SR_SCP3	SCP must give the ability to the user to add/edit/view the category of the user in the user profile	URL5, URL6, URAkul4, URAkoc2, URAkoc3
	SR_SCP4	SCP must give the ability to the user to add/edit/view the makerspaces/city the user is associated with in the user profile	URI24, URI42, URI50, URI51
	SR_SCP5	SCP must give the ability to the users to register to the platform and fill in their profiles	URL28, URI17, URI18, URI21, URAlaw6
	SR_SCP6	SCP must give the ability to users to add/edit/view the services they offer	URAaw6
	SR_SCP7	SCP must give the ability to users to add/edit/view their skills, expertise and interests	
Content management	SR_SCP8	SCP must give the ability to a user of the community to rank other users and makerspaces	URS10
	SR_SCP9	SCP must give the ability to add/edit/view equipment located at a workstation	URAaw6
	SR_SCP10	SCP must give the ability to add/edit/view exhibition venues	URL36
	SR_SCP11	SCP must give the ability to add/edit/view makerspaces	URL5, URL6, URAkoc1
	SR_SCP12	SCP must give the ability to define the city with which a makerspace is associated	URL5, URL6, URAkoc1
	SR_SCP13	SCP must give the ability to define the foundation date of a makerspace	URL32, URL33, URI34
	SR_SCP14	SCP must give the ability to define the storage capacity of a makerspace	URAaw9
	SR_SCP15	SCP must give the ability to the users to add/edit/view material types	URL16, URL17, URL106, URT1, URS13, URI1, URI3, URK13, URK19, URP23
	SR_SCP16	SCP must give the ability to the users to add/edit/view materials with their available quantities	URL16, URL17, URL20, URL84, URL106, URT1, URS8, URS13, URI1, URI3, URK13, URK19, URP23
	SR_SCP17	SCP must give the ability to the users to add/edit/view the materials	URL15
	SR_SCP18	SCP must give the ability to the users to specify the origin of materials	URL15
	SR_SCP19	SCP must give the ability to the users to add/edit/view the making process of a product	URL15

Table 24. Functional requirements of the social collaboration platform (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
	SR_SCP20	SCP must give the ability to specific users to add/edit/view the type of a product	URI29, URT3, URT18, URI6, URAtud9, URP31
	SR_SCP21	SCP must give the ability to users to add/edit/view a description of a product with text and multimedia files	URL29, URT18, URK15, URAiaac5
	SR_SCP22	SCP must give the ability to the users to add/edit/view a product	URL29, URT18, URK15, URAiaac5
	SR_SCP23	SCP must give the ability to each user to publish ideas for projects or ongoing projects	URS11, URK3, URK18
	SR_SCP24	SCP must give the ability to specific users to add/edit/view a waste repository	URL90, URL56
	SR_SCP25	SCP must give the ability to specific users to add/edit/view the location of waste repository	URL90, URL56
	SR_SCP26	SCP must give the ability to add/edit/view workstations of a makerspace	URL5, URL6
	SR_SCP27	SCP must give the ability to associate tasks with a workstation	URL5, URL6
Search and navigation	SR_SCP28	SCP must display a list with all the exhibition venues	URI36, URK15
	SR_SCP29	SCP must give the ability to the user to check if an exhibition venue is available at a specific date and time	URI36, URK15
	SR_SCP30	SCP must give the ability to the user to search for exhibition venues	URI36, URK15
	SR_SCP31	SCP must be able to present a list with the available makerspaces/stakeholders with all of their attributes	URI32, URI33, URI34
	SR_SCP32	SCP must give the ability to search materials by name or type	URL16, URL17, URL106, URT1, URS13, URT1, URI3, URK13, URK19, URP23
	SR_SCP33	SCP must show a list of the available waste materials	URS8
	SR_SCP34	SCP must give the ability to the users to search for products by type/value	URI29, URT3, URT18, URI6, URAtud9, URP31
	SR_SCP35	SCP must give the ability to each user to search for ideas for projects or ongoing projects	URS11, URK18
	SR_SCP36	SCP must be able to display a list with all the available waste repositories	URL6, URL5, URS8, URI46
	SR_SCP37	SCP must give the ability to the users to search for waste repositories	URL6, URL5, URS8, URI46
	SR_SCP38	SCP must give the ability to users to view stakeholders' profiles	URAkul9, URAkocl0, URPI

Table 24. Functional requirements of the social collaboration platform (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
	SR_SCP39	SCP must give the ability to users to search for users based on their category, skills, expertise or interest	URL26, URL27, URL28, URL31, URL39, URL40, URL41, URL48, URL49, URL69, URL78, URL83, URI12, URT21, URT22, URI2, URI7, URI8, URI12, URI14, URI15, URI26, URI30, URI58, URI59, URK6, URK19, URP25, URAkul10, URAkoc10, URAiaac6, URP1, URP8, URP16, URP25
	SR_SCP40	SCP must give the ability to users to search for users based on their skills, expertise or interest	URL26, URL27, URL28, URL48, URT21, URT22, URI12, URI14, URI15, URI38, URK6, URAkoc10, URAiaac6, URP25
Blockchain	SR_SCP41	Users must be able to export certificates for the products they make	URL14, URL89, URL25, URS14
	SR_SCP42	SCP must certify materials in terms of their origin and quality	URL14, URL89, URL25, URS14
	SR_SCP43	SCP must certify products in terms of their origin, quality, safety and circularity	URL14, URL89, URL25, URS14
	SR_SCP44	SCP must give the ability of validating the certification of materials	URL14, URL64, URL25, URT4, URS14
	SR_SCP45	SCP must provide a QR code per certified product	URT10, URT11
	SR_SCP46	SCP must give the ability of validating the certification of products	URL14, URL64, URL25, URT4, URT10, URT11, URS14
Tokenisation	SR_SCP47	SCP must give the ability to the users to buy materials/products/services via the marketplace	URL30, URT3, URT18, URT21, URS13, URS16, URI6, URK19, URAAtud9, URP31
	SR_SCP48	SCP must give the ability to the users to sell materials/products/services via the marketplace	URL30, URT18, URT19, URT21, URS13, URS16, URI17, URI18, URI21, URK15, URK19, URAiaac5
	SR_SCP49	SCP must give the ability to add/edit the value of a material in tokens	URL30, URL83, URS13, URI17, URI18, URI21
	SR_SCP50	SCP must give the ability to marketplace administrators to define mappings of tokens to real money	URAlaw11, URP31
	SR_SCP51	SCP must give the ability to add/edit the value of a making process in tokens	URL28, URI17, URI18, URI21
	SR_SCP52	SCP must give the ability to add/edit the value of a product in tokens	URT19, URS13, URI17, URI18, URI21, URK19
	SR_SCP53	SCP must give the ability to add/edit the value of a user provided service in tokens	URL28, URI17, URI18, URI21
Booking	SR_SCP54	The user must have the ability to book an available exhibition venue at a specific date and time	URI36, URK15
	SR_SCP55	SCP must display a list with all the available workstations in a makerspace	URL18, URS7, URS12
	SR_SCP56	SCP must give the ability to the user to check if a workstation/makerspace is available at a specific date and time	URL19, URL77, URS7, URS12, URS21, URK19
	SR_SCP57	SCP must give the ability to the user to search for available workstations in a makerspace	URL18, URS7, URS12

Table 24. Functional requirements of the social collaboration platform (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
	SR_SCP58	The user must have the ability to book an available workstation/makerspace at a specific date and time	URL19, URL77, URS7, URS12, URS21, URK19
Collaboration	SR_SCP59	SCP must give the ability to the users to send a message to another user	URL26, URL27, URL28, URL31, URL39, URL40, URL41, URL49, URL61, URL69, URL70, URL72, URL78, URL83, URL80, URL94, URL100, URL101, URL102, URL107, URT18, URT20, URS17, URS20, URI34, URK12, URK19, URAkul9, URAkul10, URAiaac6, URP1, URP16, URP17, URK1, URK7, URK2
	SR_SCP60	SCP must provide recommendations for collaboration of the users according to other users' category, skills, expertise and interests	URL26, URL27, URL28, URL31, URL39, URL40, URL41, URL48, URL49, URL69, URL78, URL83, URI12, URT21, URT22, URT2, UR7, UR8, URI12, URI14, URI15, URI26, URI30, URI38, URI39, URK6, URK19, URP25, URAkul10, URAkoc10, URAiaac6, URP1, URP8, URP16, URP25
	SR_SCP61	SCP must provide recommendations for collaboration of the users according to other users' skills, expertise and interests	URL26, URL27, URL28, URL48, URT21, URT22, URI12, URI14, URI15, URI38, URK6, URAkoc10, URAiaac6, URP25

12.1.2 SCP non-functional requirements

The following table lists the non-functional requirements of the social collaboration platform, which ensure the quality of the data produced and stored by the SCP, as well as its successful integration with the DCAT and OKT modules. They are grouped in three categories, and they are associated with the user requirements of the pilot cities or the academic partners that they serve.

Table 25. Non-functional requirements of the social collaboration platform

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Blockchain	SR_SCP62	SCP must certify materials in terms of their origin and quality	URL14, URL89, URL25, URS14
	SR_SCP63	SCP must certify products in terms of their origin, quality, safety and circularity	URL14, URL89, URL25, URS14
Integrity	SR_SCP64	At least one workstation must be associated with a piece of equipment	URAlaw6
	SR_SCP65	The association of a user with a makerspace/city is mandatory	URL5, URL6, URAlaw4, URAlaw2, URAlaw3
	SR_SCP66	The association of a makerspace with a city is mandatory	URL5, URL6, URAlaw1
	SR_SCP67	The definition of the foundation date of a makerspace is mandatory	URI32, URI33, URI34
	SR_SCP68	The definition of the storage capacity of a makerspace is mandatory	URAlaw9
	SR_SCP69	The location of a waste repository is mandatory	URL90, URL56
	SR_SCP70	At least one workstation must be associated with a makerspace	URL5, URL6
	SR_SCP71	At least one task must be associated with a workstation	URL5, URL6
	SR_SCP72	Each makerspace must be considered available at a specific date and time, if all its workstations are available at that time	URL19, URL77, URS7, URS12, URS21, URK19
	Consistency	SR_SCP73	SCP must synchronise changes in makerspaces with DCAT
SR_SCP74		SCP must synchronise materials and their quantities with DCAT	URS8
SR_SCP75		SCP must synchronise executed making processes with DCAT	URL15
SR_SCP76		SCP must synchronise the value of all transactions to DCAT	URAlaw10
SR_SCP77		SCP must synchronise changes in stakeholders with DCAT	URI32, URI33, URI34

12.2 Data collection and analytics tool

The data collection and analytics tool (DCAT) will host and continuously monitor the user activity in the Pop-Machina platform. This way, it will enable the presentation and export of data through appropriate visualisations and sophisticated reports. These functionalities will support insights extraction and the computation of the project's KPIs. As the main resource of information, it will provide the mechanisms and the appropriate services for storage and exchange of information among SCP, DCAT and OKT.

12.2.1 DCAT functional requirements

The following table lists the functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool. They reflect all the functionalities that must be supported by DCAT, so that the relevant user requirements are satisfied. They are grouped in categories and they are assigned a unique identifier for reference. The corresponding user requirements of the pilot cities or the academic partners are also listed in the last column of the table.

Table 26. Functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Data monitoring	SR_DCAT1	DCAT must monitor and store logs of workspaces/machinery usage per makerspace/city	URS6
	SR_DCAT2	DCAT must monitor interest in materials/products/equipment/workspace per user and user category	URL3, URT16, URT17, URT24, URS1, URAkul8
	SR_DCAT3	DCAT must monitor makerspaces' performance (number of products, amount of materials, number of users/makers) and provide relevant visualisations	URI9, URI10, URI23, URAkoc12
	SR_DCAT4	DCAT must monitor name and location (home/business) of persons buying finished products	URAtud8
	SR_DCAT5	DCAT must monitor origin, transformation and terminal (buyer of finished product) state/location per material/product	URL15, URI51, URS3, URS15, URAtud4, URAtud8
	SR_DCAT6	DCAT must monitor personal (daily/monthly/yearly) secondary material consumption, waste production (different flow of waste), energy (electricity consumption), gas consumption, water consumption	URAkul12
	SR_DCAT7	DCAT must monitor process flows of materials/products during circular economy processes	URL4, URL85, URS3, URS15, URI4, URI5, URI18, URI19, URK4, URAtud7, URAkul7, URAlaw1, URAlaw3
	SR_DCAT8	DCAT must monitor products' making and sale in time per maker/makerspace/city	URL76, URI95, URT12, URT23, URS3, URS15, URI18, URK16, URAtud6, URAkul2, URAlaw1, URAlaw3
	SR_DCAT9	DCAT must monitor quantities/types/value of materials used per maker process/workspace/piece of equipment	URAlaw12, URAlaw15
	SR_DCAT10	DCAT must monitor usage statistics of OKT events and trainings per city	URAlaw4
	SR_DCAT11	DCAT must monitor user skills composition per makerspace/city	URI44, URI45, 25, URAlaw2
	SR_DCAT12	DCAT must monitor waste/recycling effort quantities per city/districts	URI49, URI50, URI51, URAlaw7
	SR_DCAT13	DCAT must record population demographics per city (gender, immigrants, people with disabilities)	
	SR_DCAT14	DCAT must store certifications on circularity, safety and quality of products must be stored	URT4

Table 26. Functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Data input	SR_DCAT15	Users must be able to declare idle spaces in a city with their characteristics (address, size, etc.)	URI29
	SR_DCAT16	Users must be able to define the methodology of computing a product's price based on product's making process	URL34
	SR_DCAT17	Users must be able to insert, categorise and specify location of materials (raw, secondary)	URL4, URL16, URSS8, URK11, URAtud4
	SR_DCAT18	Users must be able to report data on personal (daily/monthly/yearly) secondary material consumption, waste production (different flow of waste), energy (electricity consumption), gas consumption, water consumption	URAkul13
	SR_DCAT19	Users must be able to report legislative gaps on subject/product/process	URK5
	SR_DCAT20	Users must be able to upload specs (pictures, technical, safety, quality, cost) for materials/machinery/space	URL35, URL54, URL63, URL82, URL87, URL108, URPI9
	SR_DCAT21	Users must be able to browse/search idle spaces available for establishing makerspaces	URI29
	SR_DCAT22	Users must be able to check origin and transformation per material/product	URL15, URL51, URL64, URT24, URS3, URS15, URV1, URAtud4
	SR_DCAT23	Users must be able to search cities/makerspaces based on population/users demographics	URI49, URI51
	SR_DCAT24	Users must be able to view makerspaces ordered per foundation date	URI32, URI33, URI34
Search/Browsing	SR_DCAT25	Users must be able to view products with their characteristics (materials used, value, etc.) grouped per makerspaces per maker/makerspace/city	URI40, URI41, URI43, URAkoc12
	SR_DCAT26	Users must be able to view sortable table visualisation of stakeholders aggregated on makerspace/district/city level on their attributes (skills, capabilities, etc.)	URAkoc4
	SR_DCAT27	Users must be able to view a sortable table of stakeholders on their attributes (skills, capabilities, etc.)	URAkoc5
	SR_DCAT28	DCAT must present visualisations on makerspace infrastructures' utilisation	URS6, URV1
	SR_DCAT29	DCAT must present visualisations on materials' use and availability per location/type in time	URT2, URT24, URS1, URS3, URS15, URV1, URI18, URK16, URAkul1, URAtud3, URAlaw1, URAlaw3
	SR_DCAT30	Users must be able to have an overview of raw/secondary/waste materials' volumes used per making process/makerspace/city and per final destination (i.e., buyer of finished products, waste repository, etc.) as well as their value	URAtud8, URAtud9, URAtud11, URAlaw1
	Visualisations' presentation		

Table 26. Functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
	SR_DCAT31	Users must be able to have an overview of the amount/profiles of users/user groups engaged per city	URT16, URT17, URT24, URV1, URAkul14
	SR_DCAT32	Users must be able to have an overview of the demand on materials now/in future per makerspace/city	URL66, URT23, URT24, URT13, URT16, URT20, URT5, URT18, URK16
	SR_DCAT33	Users must be able to view a map of best practices based on practice-makerspace association	URAkul5
	SR_DCAT34	Users must be able to view a map with makerspaces and their corresponding supporting partners (funding, material procurement)	URAtud1
	SR_DCAT35	Users must be able to view a map with stakeholders' interactions	URAkul6
	SR_DCAT36	Users must be able to view makerspaces/initiatives on map with colour codes indicating skills/performance	URAtud1, URAkul3, URAlaw4, URAkoc1, URAkoc12
	SR_DCAT37	Users must be able to view map of waste resources	URP3
	SR_DCAT38	Users must be able to view map visualisation of ongoing activities retrieved from OKT	URAkoc7
	SR_DCAT39	Users must be able to view stakeholders related to makerspaces on map	URAtud2, URAkul4
	SR_DCAT40	Users must be able to view statistics on educational material interest in OKT	URAiiaac2
	SR_DCAT41	Users must be able to view statistics on user activity/performance in OKT	URAiiaac1
	SR_DCAT42	Users must be provided with an overview of materials' categories, quantities and value per process/maker/makerspace/city	URL76, URL95, URT12, URT23, URT24, URV1, URT4, URT5, URT19, URK4, URK16, URAtud3, URAkul1, URAkul2, URAkul7, URAlaw1, URAlaw3
Report generation	SR_DCAT43	Users must be able to export maker movements in csv by specifying relevant filters	URAkul11
	SR_DCAT44	Users must be able to export makerspace locations in GIS compatible spatial format	URAtud1
	SR_DCAT45	Users must be able to export predefined analytics to document reports of circular activities	URL13, URT23, URT24
	SR_DCAT46	Users must be able to export statistics on user activity/performance in OKT	URAiiaac7
	SR_DCAT47	Users must be able to extract makerspaces'/stakeholders distribution statistics in geographical regions Europe/city/district	URAkoc1, URAkoc2, URAkoc3

Table 26. Functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Data processing	SR_DCAT48	DCAT must compute aggregated values on transactions committed per actor/makerspace	URAlaw10
	SR_DCAT49	DCAT must compute estimation of price of a product based on defined methodologies and historical data	URL34, URL81
	SR_DCAT50	DCAT must compute rankings of actors and makerspaces based on direct user rankings and their activity	URS10
	SR_DCAT51	DCAT must extract (spatial) correlations among makerspaces and their corresponding supporting partners (funding, material procurement)	URAtud1
	SR_DCAT52	DCAT must predict demand on materials per makerspace/city based on past data	URT23, URI5, URAlaw5
	SR_DCAT53	DCAT must track and estimate availability of materials in time	URL4, URL5, URL85, URI5

12.2.2 DCAT non-functional requirements

The following table lists the non-functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool, which ensure the quality of the data produced and stored by the DCAT, as well as its successful integration with the SCP and OKT modules. They are grouped in seven categories, and they are associated with the user requirements of the pilot cities or the academic partners that they serve.

Table 27. Non-functional requirements of the data collection and analytics tool

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Data exchange	SR_DCAT54	DCAT must be able to share selected analytics (making statistics and progress per city) with the open knowledge module	URL13, URKT14, URS1
	SR_DCAT55	DCAT must monitor user activity in OKT	
	SR_DCAT56	DCAT must monitor user activity in SCP	
	SR_DCAT57	DCAT must provide an automatic mechanism of updating stakeholders, stakeholders' categories, stakeholders' roles, makerspaces, waste repositories, materials, products, etc. from SCP	
	SR_DCAT58	DCAT must share materials with SCP	
Data model	SR_DCAT59	DCAT must share specifications (pictures, technical, safety, quality, cost) on material/machinery/space with OKT	URL16
	SR_DCAT60	Locations of stakeholders/makerspaces/initiatives must be defined with address and geographical coordinates	URAKul4
Data availability	SR_DCAT61	Stakeholders must be associated with their city	
	SR_DCAT62	Availability of all data sources involved in making procedures must be guaranteed	
	SR_DCAT63	The data required as input to the system procedures must be provided by the respective data sources	
	SR_DCAT64	The data required to measure the proposed KPIs must be provided by the respective data sources	
Data accessibility	SR_DCAT65	All data required by system procedures must be accessible by all components of the system	
	SR_DCAT66	Data preserved must be consistent with the state of the system at each point in time and across all storage locations	
Data quality	SR_DCAT67	Completeness and accuracy of Pop-Machina objects representations must be guaranteed throughout time	
	SR_DCAT68	Unique identification of each object must be provided homogeneously across all storage points of the system	
Data coherence	SR_DCAT69	Data shared among components of the system must conform to the Pop-Machina data model	
	SR_DCAT70	Data from external sources must be assured to conform to the Pop-Machina data model	
Data durability	SR_DCAT71	Actions committed by Pop-Machina entities is guaranteed to be preserved in case of failures	

Table 28. Functional requirements of the open knowledge tool

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
General	SR_OKT1	OKT system must support different languages	URAKoc8, URL8, URI92, URP4, URS20, URS9, URV2
	SR_OKT2	OKT must be compatible with at least English, French, Dutch, Lithuanian, Spanish, Greek and Turkish	URAKoc8, URL8, URI92, URP4, URS20, URS9, URV2
	SR_OKT3	OKT must be provided in a form of a webpage for users	URAlaw16, URI11, URI12, URI21, URI28, URI47, URL1, URL100, URL101, URL103, URL104, URL107, URL108, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL26, URL32, URL36, URL42, URL45, URL47, URI48, URL52, URL53, URL57, URL58, URL60, URL61, URL62, URL68, URL70, URL72, URL73, URL79, URL80, URL86, URL91, URL93, URL94, URI99, URP1, URP2, URP22, URP24, URP26, URS11, URS18, URS19, URS20, URS9, URT8, URV4
	SR_OKT4	OKT must provide a settings webpage so the user can modify his/her preferences at any time	URAlaw16, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL7, URL9, URP10, URP12, URP21, URP9, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS9, URT5, URT7
	SR_OKT5	OKT must rely on a database backend to ensure data persistence	
User Management	SR_OKT6	OKT must provide a user management system based on categories and/or roles that supports user profiles	URAKul5, URI48
	SR_OKT7	OKT must be integrated in a SSO system along with the rest of the Pop-Machina components (SCP, DCAT)	
	SR_OKT8	User profiles and roles must be shared among the different Pop-Machina components	
	SR_OKT9	OKT must support creation of new users within the SSO system	
	SR_OKT10	Non-logged users must be prompted to create an account and define basic profile elements (language, makerspace, etc.)	
	SR_OKT11	Within the settings page, the user must be able to change his/her language preferences	URAKoc8, URL8, URI92, URV2
Multi-tenancy	SR_OKT12	OKT must support different sections to host independent city/country materials, including the capacity to generate multiple silos for different makerspaces and maker movements	URAKoc8, URI11, URL57, URL58, URL8, URI92, URP20, URP4, URS20, URS9, URV2
	SR_OKT13	OKT must allow the generation of training subjects to be used to organise training material by topic	URI13, URI16, URI20
	SR_OKT14	OKT must expose an interface for administrators of makerspaces/maker movements/initiatives to create them into the platform	URI11, URL57, URL58, URP20

Table 28. Functional requirements of the open knowledge tool (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Search and navigation	SR_OKT15	OKT system must let the user browse/search for specific content, training programmes, learning materials and maker movements/ makerspaces using different filters and criteria	URAKoc8, URI11, URI12, URI21, URI22, URI31, URK14, URK3, URL1, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL11, URL12, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL24, URL25, URL36, URL38, URL44, URL45, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL57, URL58, URL59, URL60, URL62, URL68, URL7, URL73, URL74, URL75, URL79, URL8, URL86, URL88, URL89, URL9, URL91, URL92, URL97, URL98, URL99, URP1, URP2, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP28, URP36, URP5, URS16, URS2, URT13, URT8, URT9, URV2
	SR_OKT16	OKT must provide users a way to follow existing courses and/or declare interest on specific learning opportunities	URAKoc9, URI12, URI13, URI16, URI20, URK11, URK8, URL1, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL62, URL68, URL73, URL86, URL91, URL99, URP1, URP2, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP33, URP35, URT8
	SR_OKT17	OKT must show and/or suggest relevant information to users based on their interests, user profile, location, experience, etc.	URAKoc8, URI11, URI12, URI21, URI22, URI31, URK14, URK3, URL1, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL11, URL12, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL24, URL25, URL36, URL38, URL44, URL45, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL57, URL58, URL59, URL60, URL62, URL68, URL7, URL73, URL74, URL75, URL79, URL8, URL86, URL88, URL89, URL9, URL91, URL92, URL97, URL98, URL99, URP1, URP2, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP28, URP36, URP5, URS16, URS2, URT13, URT8, URT9, URV2
	SR_OKT18	OKT must implement a filter to show/hide specific content based on the user profile and associated makerspace once it enters into the platform	URAKoc8, URI11, URI12, URI21, URI22, URI31, URK14, URK3, URL1, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL11, URL12, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL24, URL25, URL36, URL38, URL44, URL45, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL57, URL58, URL59, URL60, URL62, URL68, URL7, URL73, URL74, URL75, URL79, URL8, URL86, URL88, URL89, URL9, URL91, URL92, URL97, URL98, URL99, URP1, URP2, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP28, URP36, URP5, URS16, URS2, URT13, URT8, URT9, URV2
	SR_OKT19	Public content as well as information of existing makerspaces, maker movement, initiatives, ... must be available for any user (even if he/ she is not logged into the platform)	URAKoc8, URI11, URI12, URI21, URI22, URI31, URK14, URK3, URL1, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL11, URL12, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL24, URL25, URL36, URL38, URL44, URL45, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL57, URL58, URL59, URL60, URL62, URL68, URL7, URL73, URL74, URL75, URL79, URL8, URL86, URL88, URL89, URL9, URL91, URL92, URL97, URL98, URL99, URP1, URP2, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP28, URP36, URP5, URS16, URS2, URT13, URT8, URT9, URV2

Table 28. Functional requirements of the open knowledge tool (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
	SR_OKT20	OKT must support a multiple tag system to organise materials based on the topic covered	URAKoe8, URI11, URI12, URI21, URI22, URI31, URK14, URK3, URL1, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL11, URL12, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL24, URL25, URL36, URL38, URL44, URL45, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL57, URL58, URL59, URL60, URL62, URL68, URL7, URL73, URL74, URL75, URL79, URL8, URL86, URL88, URL89, URL9, URL91, URL92, URL97, URL98, URL99, URPI1, URPI2, URPI22, URPI24, URPI26, URPI28, URPI36, URPI5, URS16, URS2, URT13, URT8, URT9, URV2
Content Generation	SR_OKT21	OKT must let users to upload files of different topics (legal, best practices, etc.)	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL7, URL8, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS5, URS9, URT5, URT7
	SR_OKT22	OKT must allow users to upload different media elements as well as other content (text, documents, etc.)	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL7, URL8, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS5, URS9, URT5, URT7
	SR_OKT23	OKT must allow users to group/reference/associate heterogeneous content under the scope of specific makerspaces/maker movements	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAkul5, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URI11, URI48, URK13, URL14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL57, URL58, URL7, URL8, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS5, URS9, URT5, URT7
	SR_OKT24	OKT must be flexible enough to accommodate/visualise different types of content, providing the means to create attractive views	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL13, URL2, URL42, URL7, URL8, URL82, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS1, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS5, URS9, URT14, URT15, URT7
	SR_OKT25	OKT must allow users to declare expertise/availability on specific training topics, so other users can get in contact with them to generate new learning opportunities	URAKoe9, URI13, URI16, URI20, URPI20
	SR_OKT26	OKT must provide users the possibility of creating their own courses and upload learning materials, providing the means to interconnect with streaming platform	URAKoe9, URI26, URI39, URI51, URK1, URK7, URL10, URI9, URPI2, URPI9, URPI21, URPI4, URS11, URS9, URT6, URV4
	SR_OKT27	OKT must let specific users to curate the content created by other users	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URI11, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL57, URL58, URL7, URL8, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI20, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS9, URT5, URT7
	SR_OKT28	OKT must allow users to modify and update their own content	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL7, URL8, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS1, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS5, URS9, URT5, URT7
	SR_OKT29	OKT must expose a set of tools for administrators to edit or remove the content uploaded to the platform	URAIaac3, URAIaac4, URAlaw16, URAlaw8, URK13, URK14, URK17, URK3, URL10, URL2, URL42, URL7, URL8, URL9, URL92, URPI0, URPI2, URPI21, URPI4, URPI9, URS11, URS16, URS20, URS5, URS9, URT5, URT7

Table 28. Functional requirements of the open knowledge tool (continued)

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements
Collaborative tools	SR_OKT30	OKT must be integrated with a third party service to stream video in real time	URAKoe9, URI12, URI26, URI39, URI51, URK1, URK11, URK7, URK8, URL1, URL10, URL103, URL104, URL108, URL21, URL22, URL23, URL47, URL52, URL53, URL62, URL68, URL73, URL86, URL9, URL91, URL99, URP1, URP12, URP19, URP2, URP21, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP33, URP35, URP4, URS11, URS9, URT6, URT8, URV4
	SR_OKT31	OKT must provide a subscription system for new events and content. Events must also be presented in a calendar for easier tracking	URL36, URL45, URL60, URL79, URP4, URS17, URS19, URV4
	SR_OKT32	OKT must provide a forum where users can interact among themselves	URAKoe9, URAlaw16, URI25, URI28, URI47, URK1, URK12, URK7, URL100, URL101, URL107, URL26, URL32, URL42, URL48, URL61, URL70, URL72, URL80, URL93, URL94, URP1, URP12, URP2, URP21, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP4, URS11, URS18, URS19, URS20, URS5, URS9, URV4
	SR_OKT33	OKT must notify users by email at least once per day if there is new information, learning material, etc.	URI25, URI47, URK1, URK7, URL100, URL101, URL107, URL26, URL32, URL42, URL48, URL61, URL70, URL72, URL80, URL93, URL94, URP1, URP2, URP21, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP4, URS11, URS18, URS19, URS20, URS5, URS9, URV4
	SR_OKT34	OKT must provide a forum where logged users can comment and create new topics to be answered	URAKoe9, URAlaw16, URI25, URI28, URI47, URK1, URK12, URK7, URL100, URL101, URL107, URL26, URL32, URL42, URL48, URL61, URL70, URL72, URL80, URL93, URL94, URP1, URP2, URP21, URP22, URP24, URP26, URP4, URS11, URS18, URS19, URS20, URS5, URS9, URV4
Pop-Machina integration	SR_OKT35	OKT must be integrated with DCAT to retrieve statistics, images, materials, product, etc.	URL82, URT14
	SR_OKT36	OKT backend must query or subscribe to the API provided by the rest of the Pop-Machina components to keep the platform synchronised	URAKaul5, URI48

12.3 Open knowledge tool

The open knowledge tool (OKT) will enable users to be continuously educated and informed about best practices and legislation frameworks regarding making processes. This goal will be achieved through educational content that will be organised in categories and will come in textual or multimedia forms. OKT will give the opportunity for organising seminars and surveys or questionnaires through the Pop-Machina platform. It will also provide the means for communication among Pop-Machina members and for disseminating interesting material (news, events, accomplishments, campaigns, etc.) throughout the community.

12.3.1 OKT functional requirements

The following table lists the functional requirements of the open knowledge tool. They reflect all the functionalities that must be supported by OKT, so that the relevant user requirements are satisfied. They are grouped in categories and they are assigned a unique identifier for reference. The corresponding user requirements of the pilot cities or the academic partners are also listed in the last column of the table.

Table 29. Non-functional requirements of the open knowledge tool

Category	Req. ID	Requirement	Related user requirements	
General	SR_OKT137	OKT platform must use English as a common reference language		
	SR_OKT138	OKT platform must support internationalisation, either with a i18n module or using automatic translation based on an available engine		
	SR_OKT139	OKT platform must support multiple charsets for different languages		
	SR_OKT140	OKT platform must be easily accessible by any user		
	SR_OKT141	OKT must be compatible with most of the web browsers existing today		
	SR_OKT142	OKT content accessibility must consider any type of user. i.e. High contrast rate, colours, etc.		
	SR_OKT143	OKT must consider privacy and be compliant with the GDPR (e.g. right to remove personal information, cookie consent, etc.)		
	SR_OKT144	OKT platform uptime must be at least of 99,8%		
	User Management	SR_OKT145	OKT must consider preferences and make sure new users accept the privacy conditions before storing any type of information from them in the database	
		SR_OKT146	Profile updates must be shared/replicated among the other components through an API	
Search and navigation	SR_OKT147	The language used in the OKT and the learning materials must depend on the user language settings and profile		
	SR_OKT148	The OKT system must have enough storage capacity to host users content		
Content Generation	SR_OKT149	OKT must provide an user-friendly interface to edit content online		
	SR_OKT150	OKT must be compatible with most used calendar formats (such as the .ics format)		
Collaborative tools	SR_OKT151	OKT must be compatible with existing mail servers to notify users about new content		
	SR_OKT152	Updates on any of the Pop-Machina components affecting OKT must be immediately synchronised		

12.3.2 OKT non-functional requirements

The following table lists the non-functional requirements of the open knowledge tool, which ensure the quality of the data produced and stored by the OKT, as well as its successful integration with the DCAT and SCP modules. They are grouped in six categories, and they are associated with the user requirements of the pilot cities or the academic partners that they serve.

13. Data model

The data model of Pop-Machina defines the structure of the data that is necessary for the Pop-Machina platform to be functional. It includes the data that is inserted by users to the system and data that is presented to the end users of the platform. At the same time, the data model is the basis for data exchange protocol that is going to be implemented by the different platform components.

The data model presented in this chapter is the base data model of Pop-Machina. Mainly, it is going to be implemented by the database of the data collection and analytics tool (DCAT) of the platform. DCAT is responsible for storing and processing data coming from all platform components, that is, the social collaboration platform (SCP) and the open knowledge tool (OKT). SCP and OKT deployments rely on open source software, which comes with already in place database schemas.

13.1 Conceptual model

The data model of Pop-Machina consists of a set of concepts and their relationships. Through the following analysis, all actors involved in Pop-Machina procedures will be described, as well as the way they are related and act in the Pop-Machina context.

13.1.1 Concepts

13.1.1.1 User

A user of Pop-Machina is any person that is an actor of the circular economy community of the project. The different roles of people becoming members of the community have been identified in the stakeholders' identification sections of the city user requirements chapters (Chapters 4-10), as well as in the user stories provided by the cities in the 'As a ...' part of each story. They may be makers, authorities' representatives, entrepreneurs, researchers, makerspace administrators, etc.

Users are registered to the system and create their profile. It includes their skills, expertise, interests, offered services and tokens. Each user is granted a set of permissions in the Pop-Machina platform. Each set of permissions defines a system role in the platform that determines whether the user has a right to upload and update data in the platform, whether the user has the right to consume specific services provided by the platform, and which portions of data the user has the permission to view and process. System roles may be different in the three basic components of the platform. Depending on their roles, users may be able to make products and exhibit them for purchase, share educational content and expertise, communicate with other Pop-Machina actors, monitor and export reports of Pop-Machina indicators, etc.

13.1.1.2 User group

A user group is any community formed by Pop-Machina users. Makerspace communities, social initiatives, NGOs and academic research teams are examples of such communities. User groups can assume specific roles in the Pop-Machina platform similar to the roles assigned to individual users. Pop-Machina can take advantage of expertise demonstrated by user groups which can be shared through training programmes. They may organise promotion campaigns of ongoing projects or invite

people to seminars. Special Pop-Machina roles of administering and manipulating Pop-Machina content and actors can also be assigned to particular user groups that may or may not correspond to communities of the real world. An example of such a group is a governance body that will determine the direction of the Pop-Machina ecosystem by proposing and voting for modifications of Pop-Machina processes.

13.1.1.3 Material

Materials are the basis of all making processes in the Pop-Machina makerspaces. They are categorised (e.g., raw, secondary, etc.) and they can be provided by cities (e.g., the waste management stakeholders of the city), or by individuals and local businesses at their will. The types of materials, their quantities and their transformation to products, which re-enter the circular economy environment, form the evaluation basis of the efficiency of Pop-Machina makerspaces. Materials are associated with products that are based on them, with equipment that can process them and with guidelines for using them. For all materials, a value in tokens is defined per quantity unit (volume, weight or surface).

13.1.1.4 Product

A product is any object that is produced through a making process in a Pop-Machina makerspace. Products may be final or intermediate ones. Final products can be exposed in the Pop-Machina marketplace and become available for purchase by interested stakeholders. Intermediate products are products that are produced through a making process and can be useful as parts of a different making process. Products are also assigned with a value, based on which they can be exchanged or purchased. A product is related with the materials and equipment necessary to build it, as well as a specific making process and relevant guidelines. The making of a product is accompanied with certifications on the materials used to build it and on the processes applied for creating it.

13.1.1.5 Equipment

Pop-Machina equipment is every piece of machinery available in a makerspace of the project that can be exploited by a user for making circular products. Examples constitute 3D printers, laser cutters, millers, etc.. Equipment is associated with the makerspace where it is located and is characterised by a set of specifications. Based on its specifications, a piece of equipment may be used for processing specific materials and can be used to realise a certain making process. Guidelines, safety precautions, restrictions and best practices are associated with every piece of equipment. The use of equipment at a certain time by a specific user is ensured through the booking system of Pop-Machina.

13.1.1.6 Making process

A making process is defined as a process that builds a product starting from one or more materials. It consists of a sequence of transformation tasks. Each transformation task constructs an intermediate or final product from a material or another intermediate product. Appropriate equipment may be involved in a transformation task of a making process. In this case, the specific equipment and the corresponding workstation of the makerspace, where the product is built, must be booked.

13.1.1.7 Certificate

Certificates are issued for materials that are used in a makerspace to ensure the origin and quality of the material. The platform also certifies all transformation tasks executed in makerspaces, ensuring that all intermediate products of a making process comply with circularity standards. As a result certificates are issued for products either intermediate or final ones. The certification process is one of the main goals of the blockchain component of Pop-Machina, which will record and verify all processes and transactions implemented by Pop-Machina users by acting as a single point of truth.

13.1.1.8 Makerspace

The bases for all Pop-Machina pilot cities' use cases are the makerspaces that are going to be exploited for the purposes of the project. Each makerspace resides at a specific location and is associated with the relevant city. Makerspaces can be used by users that have the rights to use it based on their system roles. A special type of user, the makerspace administrator, is responsible for the makerspace and has permissions to provide and change attributes of the makerspace. For instance, the makerspace administrator is responsible for listing and providing technical data for the equipment hosted in the makerspace, as well as for recording the materials that enter the makerspace for building circular products.

A makerspace is the smallest aggregation unit for monitoring the performance of Pop-Machina. KPIs will be defined on the level of makerspaces, and starting from there, they will be extended to a broader context, i.e., neighbourhood level, city level, country level or the whole Pop-Machina project. For that reason, all data required by formulas for computing quantifiable KPIs will come from the makerspaces and will be associated with the makerspace directly (e.g., the).

13.1.1.9 Workstation

A workstation takes up a room spot in a makerspace, and its attributes define whether it is a generic working bench, or it is dedicated for a specific work. It may host a piece of equipment. A workstation may be used by one or more users. It may be available at certain times or not, and this is why it must be booked by an interested user for a specific timeslot.

13.1.1.10 Service

A service is offered by users of the Pop-Machina community to other users. Services can be bought with tokens. A service can be a transformation task or a whole making process that is willing to undertake. However, offerings of expertise, guidelines or trainings are also considered to be services that can be exchanged among Pop-Machina actors. The availability of services is declared in the profiles of the users. Together with their skills, expertise and interests are used for matchmaking implemented by the social collaboration platform of Pop-Machina.

13.1.1.11 Project

A project is created by a user of Pop-Machina. It entails the making of one or more products. Ongoing or future projects are published by users and they can form the ground for collaboration among community members.

13.1.1.12 Educational content

The open knowledge tool of Pop-Machina hosts a collection of informative and educational pieces of content, which are available to all Pop-Machina users. Guidelines for making products, designs and legislative material are examples of such content. Educational content may be associated with materials, products, equipment, transformation tasks or whole making processes.

13.1.1.13 Proposal

Pop-Machina actors perform various activities in the community that follow specific procedures and follow rules imposed by legislation and established city practices. Users of the system may suggest modifications to existing processes or suggest new ones. These proposals may be open for discussion in the community through the Pop-Machina platform, which may end with voting about the proposal.

13.1.2 Relationships

13.1.2.1 Use

Pop-Machina users *use* materials and equipment for making products.

13.1.2.2 Make

Pop-Machina users *make*, in the context of one of their projects, intermediate or final products from materials.

13.1.2.3 Buy

Pop-Machina community members *buy* products made in makerspaces. Makers *buy* materials for making products. Makers *buy* services from community actors. Each *buy* action has a value in tokens.

13.1.2.4 Sell

Makers *sell* products made in makerspaces. Pop-Machina members *sell* services to other community actors. Each *sell* action is associated with a price in tokens.

13.1.2.5 Donate

A user of Pop-Machina *donates* a resource (e.g., a material) to the community or a specific actor.

13.1.2.6 Book

A Pop-Machina user *books* a workspace for a specific date and time. A Pop-Machina user *books* certain equipment for a specific date and time. A user group *books* a makerspace for a specific project.

13.1.2.7 Offer

A Pop-Machina user *offers* a service (making process, instructions, education, etc.) to other Pop-Machina members.

13.1.2.8 Publish

A user *publishes* a project or her intent for starting a project.

13.1.2.9 Certify

A certificate *certifies* a material, a product or a making process.

13.1.2.10 Membership

A user is a *member* of a user group.

13.1.2.11 Propose

A user *proposes* a proposal.

13.1.2.12 Vote

A user *votes* in favour or against a suggested proposal.

13.2 Logical model

The logical model of the Pop-Machina platform has been designed in its initial form. It is expected to evolve in parallel with the implementation progress of the system. The deliverables D4.7 and D4.8 of the data collection and analytics module will report its state until its finalised version. However, the basic concepts and relationships are already captured already from its initial definition.

The logical model of Pop-Machina defines the schema of the database that can accommodate the conceptual model described in the previous section. The database of Pop-Machina is going to follow the relational model. Relational models are naturally visualised through Entity-Relationship (ER) diagrams. Figure 8 illustrates the Pop-Machina ER diagram.

The Pop-Machina relational model includes all Pop-Machina concepts and relationships. Each concept is defined as a table with a set of informative attributes for the corresponding concept instances. The attributes describe an object, together with its properties, and further enable the system for data processing as imposed by the Pop-Machina user requirements. For instance, the system offers capabilities like search for materials, products, stakeholders based on their properties, or aggregation of objects for extracting statistics and insights on the Pop-Machina usage (e.g., material amount aggregations per makerspace).

Relationships among concepts in the relational model are reflected either by the attributes of a concept (e.g., the *city* attribute of a *makerspace* reveals a connection between a makerspace and a particular city), or by foreign key constraints (e.g., reference from the *user* attribute of the *member* table to the *id* attribute of the *user* table). The lines of Figure 8 denote the relationships defined between pairs of Pop-Machina concepts. A foreign key constraint ensures the integrity and consistency of data, besides simply connecting different concepts. This way, relevant non-functional system requirements regarding the quality of data are met, and the integration aspects of the system are supported.

Figure 8. Pop-Machina ER model

14. KPIs addressed by Task 2.5

The project KPIs which are relevant to this deliverable are the following:

- KPI-9. Urban metabolism and productive systems analysed and optimised based on the project outcomes: 7;
- KPI-10. Socio-economic contexts analysed and optimised based on project outcomes: 7;
- KPI-12. Legislative, governance and taxation contexts analysed and optimised based on the project outcomes: 7.

These KPIs are relevant to the whole second work package. They are mainly covered by the rest of WP2 tasks, but T2.5 indirectly addresses them through the analysis of the city profiles, user requirements and use cases.

In particular, the urban metabolism, the productive systems and the socio-economic contexts of the pilot cities were analysed in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, while the legislative, governance and taxation contexts in Task 2.4. However, in this deliverable, the seven Chapters 4 - 10 contain an extended analysis of the context of the cities, mainly in terms of the goals of each city in relation to Pop-Machina. A description of the city profile is given, stakeholders and current circular economy initiatives are reported and the goals of each city are reflected in its business and user requirements as well as the use cases that the city is going to implement in the scope of the project.

As a result, the 7 contexts of the aspects required by KPIs 9-11 are fully covered from an abstract and practical aspect in this deliverable.

15. Conclusion and next steps

In this deliverable, the foundations for the Pop-Machina platform were laid. Pilot cities, pilot supporting partners, academic partners and technical partners of the consortium collaborated for extracting the Pop-Machina platform business, user and system requirements. As a result of this analysis, which was conducted in multiple cycles and was supported by physical and virtual meetings, a comprehensive and detailed list of requirements was produced. This work led to the design of the Pop-Machina data model that comprises all the concepts and relationships among Pop-Machina entities.

The theoretical background created by the work of this task will form the basis for the implementation of the Pop-Machina system, in the scope of WP4. Pilot and academic partners provided a rich list of requirements that correspond to functionalities and user interface features that will be implemented during the development of the SCP, DCAT and OKT modules of the Pop-Machina platform. The technical partners will proceed from this point in appropriately designing the detailed system architecture, which will be presented in the deliverables of WP4. The system requirements, emerging from the user requirements collected in this task, will be prioritised and will probably be enhanced by new user requirements that may come up during the system's implementation and the pilot operation. This process will result in the final set of features that will be supported by the Pop-Machina platform.

At the same time, this work constitutes the starting point for the evaluation and impact assessment of the project that will be realised by the actions of WP7. The use cases described in this deliverable will form the basis of designing appropriate test scenarios for each pilot. Executing these test scenarios repeatedly and taking advantage of the data input functionalities that will be offered by the Pop-Machina platform (see Tables 24, 26 and 28), base data of the Pop-Machina activities will be produced and monitored. Appropriately defining the computation method of Pop-Machina quantifiable KPIs will then lead to the assessment of the impact of the project in the pilot cities' environments. The visualisations exposed through the DCAT user interface and the sophisticated reports, which Pop-Machina users will be enabled to export, will complete the impact assessment toolkit of the project.

appendix 1 Business requirements guidelines

Pilot area X

1 Introduction

Give an introductory description of the area and its profile. Explain, in an abstract way, why the area can benefit from Pop-Machina.

2 Current situation

2.1 Overview

Describe the area and its Pop-Machina relevant properties. Mention initiatives regarding the maker community and relevant subjects to the project (e.g., waste management, resources management) in the pilot area.

2.2 Current business process models

Describe existing processes of the city and designate the entities, units and departments responsible for each one of them. What are the responsibilities of the city authorities regarding the issues to be addressed by Pop-Machina? How makers and citizens interact with the city authorities and other external entities, as well as with each other? Are there any software systems that participate in the relevant business processes?

2.3 Stakeholders' identification

List the various user groups that interact for purposes relevant to the project in the city. For example, city authorities, makers, citizens, makerspaces administrators, managers of resources and materials, companies, etc. What is the role of each one of them? For describing the roles, you may also refer to the processes described in Section 2.2.

2.4 Challenges and problematic areas

What are the challenges falling in the scope of the project that the city faces? What problems does Pop-Machina have the potential to solve?

3 TO-BE scenario

3.1 Overview

Describe the vision for the city, considering the benefits that Pop-Machina can offer. Identify new business processes, which are desirable to be supported. Designate additional stakeholders to Section 2.3, who may be assigned with new roles in the envisioned situation of the area.

3.2 Business requirements

List the business requirements for the envisioned Pop-Machina platform in a table of the form shown below. Each requirement must contain the following:

- the problem or challenge to be addressed (referenced in 2.4) or the vision (referenced in 3.1) to be served;
- the business process(es) that is(are) affected (referenced in 2.2 or in 3.1);
- the stakeholders involved (referenced in 2.3 or in 3.1);
- the module of the platform (social collaboration, data analytics or open knowledge base) that is targeted by the specific requirement. If you cannot decide, leave it blank.

Problem/Challenge/Vision	Business process	Stakeholders	Platform module
...	
...

appendix 2 User requirements guidelines

Pilot area X

The user requirements are defined in terms of the user stories that express the desired functionalities by each group of users. Following the business requirements analysis, each pilot must create a set of user stories that will fulfil each business goal identified in Section 3.2 of the business requirements document. The result will be a user story table, as shown in the example at the end of the page. A user story comprises three parts:

1. User Role
2. Goal
3. Benefit

It is reflected by a sentence of the following form:

'As a <user role>, I want to <goal>, so that <benefit>'

Consider the following example of a business requirement:

Problem/Challenge/Vision	Business process	Stakeholders	Platform module
Lack of detailed information about processes and locations of materials and stakeholders of the maker ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trading and buying secondary raw materials - Trading and buying circular products, certified for circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local governmental authorities - Makers - Start uppers - Citizens/residents - Makerspaces administrators - Managers of resources and materials - Social Cooperatives 	Data collection and analytics module

A set of user stories (not exhaustive, of course) emerging from the above business requirement could be:

As a ... (role)	I want to ... (goal)	So that ... (benefit)	Platform module
Maker	Search for secondary raw materials by type	I can decide if I can make a product	Data collection and analytics module
Manager of resources and materials	Have an overview of the missing materials	I can take care of procuring them	Data collection and analytics module
Citizen	See what circular products are available	I can buy them	Data collection and analytics module
...
...

appendix 3 Academic and technical user requirements guidelines

Academic/technical partner X

The user requirements are defined in terms of the user stories that express the desired functionalities by each group of users. The functionalities are required by one of the three modules of the Pop-Machina platform:

1. SCP (social collaboration platform): requirements that are relevant to (i) user/makerspace identification, profiles, communication/collaboration, (ii) blockchain transactions and certification of materials/products and (iii) tokenisation of materials/products/effort/resources;
2. DCAT (data collection and analytics tool): requirements that are relevant to collecting data, recording metrics, monitoring changes of metrics in time/space, presenting visualisations of statistics and analysing data to produce new insights;
3. OKT (open knowledge tool): requirements relevant to sharing educational material, regulatory/legislative material and promotional material of initiatives, events, as well as requirements on disseminating activities and organising/attending trainings.

The source for a user requirement, beyond the pilot requirements, may be among others a specific research interest, a specific requirement that would assist decision making by any partner of Pop-Machina for a specific project task or a KPI. The resulting requirements must be formed in a user story table in an excel file, as shown in the example at the end of the page. A user story comprises three parts:

1. user role;
2. goal;
3. benefit.

It is reflected by a sentence of the following form:

'As a <user role>, I want to <goal>, so that <benefit>'

Consider the following example of a KPI:

KPI-1. Demonstrated reduction of secondary raw material consumption in pilots: > 50%

A set of user stories targeting this KPI could be:

1. as a researcher, I want to see what was the yearly/monthly/daily secondary material consumption during the last 5 years in each pilot city, so that I can conclude if there was an improvement in secondary material exploitation in each city;
2. as a researcher, I want to know the amount of secondary material consumed per day/week/month for each makerspace, so that I can see if my methodologies for citizens engagement work;
3. as a researcher, I want to be able to see a graph comparing secondary material consumption in the past and during Pop-Machina pilot run, so that I can compute KPI-1.

In the requested table format, accordingly, they would be recorded as follows:

As a ... (role)	I want to ... (goal)	So that ... (benefit)	Platform module
Researcher	See what was the yearly/monthly/daily secondary material consumption during the last 5 years in each pilot city	I can conclude if there was an improvement in secondary material exploitation in each city	DCAT
Researcher	Know the amount of secondary material consumed per day/week/month for each makerspace	I can take care of procuring them	DCAT
Researcher	Be able to see a graph comparing secondary material consumption in the past and during Pop-Machina pilot run	I can compute KPI-1	DCAT
...
...

About Pop-Machina

Pop-Machina aims to demonstrate the power and potential of the maker movement and collaborative production for the EU circular economy. We draw from a number of cut-edge technologies (factory-of-the-future, blockchain) and disciplines (urban planning, architecture) to provide the support necessary to overcome scaling issues; a typical drawback of collaborative production; to find the areas more in need of our intervention and to reconfigure unused spaces. We put forth an elaborate community engagement program to network, incentivize and stimulate through maker faires and events existing and new maker communities in all our municipalities. We build upon the current informal curriculum for maker skills development by nurturing the social side and we put educators and makers together to exchange ideas on the training modalities. A particular focus on the skill development of women and vulnerable groups will aim to empower these (underrepresented) segments to partake actively in collaborative production. In every pilot area we will demonstrate business oriented collaborative production of feasible and sustainable concepts from secondary raw material or other sustainable inputs, based on the needs and preferences of the local stakeholders. A thorough impact assessment framework with increased scope (e.g. social) will be codesigned with stakeholders after short basic assessment trainings and will be used in the assessment of our pilot work. Based on the findings we will kick-start a series of policy events to discuss openly – without pushing our results – the tax and legal barriers that hamper collaborative production.

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